

Strategic Conservation Plan for Wet-Grassland Breeding Birds in Germany

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It is important to note that this document is the result of multiple years of research and analysis. While minor updates related to new regulations or shifts in the political landscape may have occurred since its completion, we do not anticipate that these changes will significantly affect the validity or applicability of the recommendations provided herein.

The findings and conclusions presented in this report are the result of independent analysis and do not necessarily reflect the views or policies of the organizations to which the contributors are affiliated. The creation of this document was co-financed by the European Union's LIFE programme: LIFE IP GrassBirdHabitats (LIFE19 IPE/DE/000004).

Title photo: The Common Snipe *Gallinago gallinago* by Christopher Marlow.

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II. List of recurrent abbreviations

AEWA	Agreement on the Conservation of African-Eurasian Migratory Waterbirds
AECM & AUKM	Agri-Environment Climate Measures
BR	UNESCO biosphere reserve
BioIV	Erhalt und Entwicklung der Biologischen Vielfalt/Conservation and Development of Biodiversity
BMEL	German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture
BGA KLARA	Regionaler Begleitausschuss für Klima, Landwirtschaft, Artenvielfalt, Regionale AkteurInnen
BfN	Bundesamt für Naturschutz/Federal Agency for Nature Conservation
BUKEA	Die Hamburger Behörde für Umwelt, Klima, Energie und Agrarwirtschaft
CAP	European Common Agricultural Policy
DDA	Dachverband Deutscher Avifaunisten/The Umbrella Association of German Avifaunists
EAF	The East Atlantic Flyway
EAFI	The East Atlantic Flyway Initiative
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
EELA	Erhalt und Entwicklung von Lebensräumen und Arten/Conservation and Development of Habitats and Species in Rural Landscapes
EU-VSG	EU-Vogelschutzgebiete
FFH	Fauna-Flora-Habitat-Richtlinie/Special Area of Conservation
FVK	Feldvogelkullisse, Bavaria
GLÖZ	Guter Landwirtschaftlicher und Ökologischer Zustand/Good Agricultural and Environmental Condition
HB	Bremen
HH	Hamburg
HS	Horizon Scanning survey
IBA	Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas
IKI	Die Internationale Klimaschutzinitiative/The International Climate Initiative of the German Federal Government
IWC	The International Waterbird Census
ISSAP	International Single Species Action Plan

ISMP	International Single Species Management Plan
KULAP	Das bayerische Kulturlandschaftsprogramm/The Cultural Landscape Program, Bavaria
LANUV/LANUK	The Federal State Agency for Nature, Environment, and Consumer Protection, North Rhine-Westphalia
LBV	Landesbund für Vogel- und Naturschutz in Bayern
LSG	Landschaftsschutzgebiete/Landscape Protection Area
LC	Least Concern
LfU	Landesamt für Umwelt/The Federal State Agency for the Environment
MEKUN	The Ministry of Energy Transition, Climate Protection, Environment and Nature, Schleswig-Holstein
MOIN	Michael-Otto-Institut im NABU
MP	Management plan
NP	National park
NLWKN	Lower Saxony Water Management, Coastal Protection and Nature Conservation Agency
NI	Lower Saxony
NNatSchG	Niedersächsisches Naturschutzgesetz
NT	Near Threatened
NRW	North Rhine-Westphalia
NSG	Naturschutzgebiete/Nature Protection Area
NSG	Nature Protection Areas
ÖR	Öko Regelungen/Eco-Schemes
PEP	Pflege- und Entwicklungspläne/Care and Development Plans
SCP	Strategic Conservation Plan
SH	Schleswig-Holstein
SPA	Special Protection Area
SAB	Special Species and Biotope Conservation
UNB	Untere Naturschutzbehörde im Landkreis
VU	Vulnerable
VNS	Vertragsnaturschutz/Contractual nature conservation
WSFI	The Wadden Sea Flyway Initiative
WBK	Wiesenbrüterkulisse, Bavaria

1 Summary

This multi-species Strategic Conservation Plan (SCP) for wet-grassland breeding birds in Germany proposes a framework for preserving and restoring biodiverse wet grasslands and meadows for future generations. It provides an inclusive framework for the conservation of wet-grassland biodiversity in general, and promotes healthy ecosystems capable of supporting diverse bird communities.

This SCP aims at advancing the conservation of 11 target species emblematic of wet-grasslands. Those include the Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa*, the Common Redshank *Tringa totanus*, the Common Snipe *Gallinago gallinago*, the Eurasian Curlew *Numenius arquata*, and the Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus*, among others. Thus, the SCP provides an overview of the main instruments available to tackle wet-grassland bird conservation. Those include legal instruments, financial instruments, and management instruments. A quantitative analysis and a critical assessment of these instruments are also provided when possible. Further, the SCP provides the results of a Horizon Scanning survey conducted in 2022 that summarizes the opinion, expertise, and evaluation of the wider nature conservation community across Germany.

The SCP includes sections specific to Lower Saxony and Bremen, Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg, North Rhine-Westphalia, and Bavaria. These sections represent major Federal States leading in wet-grassland and meadow bird conservation across the Atlantic and Continental biogeographic regions of Germany. These sections were developed in cooperation with major stakeholders from these states, including state agencies, biological stations, and NGOs (see the list of contributors above). While we did not create a specific section for each of the 16 Federal States, participants from across Germany were able to express their opinions in the Horizon Scanning survey.

To illustrate the know-how and expertise of conservation practitioners in Germany, the SCP presents 11 representative successful case studies. These include studies on: 1) holistic integrative approaches for wet-grassland bird conservation, 2) political agreements to advance nature conservation, 3) result-based payment models of agricultural services on public land, 4) predation management in SPAs, and 5) telemetry studies to assess bird movement and breeding success, among others. These case studies highlight the diverse strategies and effective practices deployed in conservation efforts.

Lastly, the SCP provides a roadmap for the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds in Germany. It outlines the steps and key milestones needed to achieve long-term sustainable conservation. The roadmap offers an assessment of the main conservation practices, valuable insights, future outlooks, and key recommendations to move forward. Overall, the roadmap provides clarity and alignment among the views of stakeholders who participated in its development. It aims to guide efforts toward achieving long-term conservation goals and reversing the trend of wet-grassland biodiversity loss in Germany.

2 Zusammenfassung

Dieser artübergreifende Strategische Schutzplan (SSP) für Feuchtgrünland-Brutvögel in Deutschland schlägt eine Strategie vor, um biodiverse Feuchtgrünländer und Wiesen für zukünftige Generationen zu erhalten und wiederherzustellen. Er bietet einen umfassenden Rahmen für den Erhalt der Biodiversität im Feuchtgrünland im Allgemeinen und fördert zudem intakte Ökosysteme, die in der Lage sind, vielfältige Vogelgemeinschaften zu beheimaten.

Der SSP zielt darauf ab, den Schutz von elf Zielarten, die für Feuchtgrünländer charakteristisch sind, voranzutreiben. Dazu gehören unter anderem die Uferschnepfe *Limosa limosa limosa*, der Rotschenkel *Tringa totanus*, die Bekassine *Gallinago gallinago*, der (Große) Brachvogel *Numenius arquata* und der Kiebitz *Vanellus vanellus*. Der SSP bietet einen Überblick über die wichtigsten Instrumente, die für den Schutz von Brutvögeln im Feuchtgrünland zur Verfügung stehen. Dazu gehören rechtliche Instrumente, finanzielle Instrumente und Managementinstrumente. Eine quantitative Analyse und eine kritische Bewertung dieser Instrumente werden ebenfalls, wo möglich, bereitgestellt. Darüber hinaus enthält der SSP die Ergebnisse einer Horizon-Scanning-Umfrage aus dem Jahr 2022. Diese Umfrage fasst die Meinungen, das Fachwissen und die Bewertungen eines weit gefassten Personenkreises aus dem Bereich Naturschutz zusammen.

Der SSP enthält Abschnitte, die speziell Niedersachsen und Bremen, Schleswig-Holstein und Hamburg, Nordrhein-Westfalen sowie Bayern behandeln. Diese Bundesländer sind führend in der Erhaltung von Feuchtgrünland und Wiesenvögeln in den atlantischen und kontinentalen biogeografischen Regionen Deutschlands. Die Abschnitte wurden in Zusammenarbeit mit wichtigen Interessengruppen aus diesen Bundesländern entwickelt, darunter Behörden, biologische Stationen und NGOs (siehe die Liste der Mitwirkenden oben). Obwohl wir keinen speziellen Abschnitt für jedes der 16 Bundesländer erstellt haben, konnten Teilnehmer:innen aus ganz Deutschland ihre Meinungen in der Horizon-Scanning-Umfrage zum Ausdruck bringen.

Um das Know-how und die Expertise von Naturschutzpraktiker:innen in Deutschland zu veranschaulichen, präsentiert der SSP elf repräsentative erfolgreiche Fallstudien. Diese umfassen unter anderem Studien zu: 1) ganzheitlichen integrativen Ansätzen für den Schutz von Vögeln im Feuchtgrünland, 2) politischen Vereinbarungen zur Förderung des Naturschutzes, 3) ergebnisbasierten Zahlungsmodellen für landwirtschaftliche Dienstleistungen auf öffentlichem Land, 4) Prädationsmanagement in Vogelschutzgebieten und 5) Telemetriestudien zur Bewertung von Vogelbewegungen und Bruterfolg. Diese Fallstudien heben die vielfältigen Strategien und effektiven Praktiken hervor, die im Wiesenvogelschutz eingesetzt werden.

Schließlich bietet der SSP einen Zukunftsplan für den Schutz von Brutvögeln im Feuchtgrünland in Deutschland. Er skizziert die Schritte und die wichtigsten Meilensteine, die erforderlich sind, um diese Vögel langfristig und nachhaltig zu schützen. Der Zukunftsplan liefert eine Bewertung der wichtigsten Schutzpraktiken sowie wertvolle Erkenntnisse, Ausblicke und wichtige Empfehlungen für das weitere Vorgehen. Er findet Zustimmung bei allen Interessengruppen, die an seiner Entwicklung beteiligt waren. Er zielt darauf ab, Schutzbemühungen zu leiten, um langfristige Erhaltungsziele zu erreichen und den Trend des Biodiversitätsverlustes in Feuchtgrünländern in Deutschland umzukehren.

3 Introduction

3.1 Rationale

The multi-species Strategic Conservation Plan (SCP) for wet grassland breeding birds in Germany proposes a framework for preserving and restoring biodiverse wet grasslands for future generations. It targets primarily wet-grassland breeding waders of the Atlantic biogeographic region of Germany, however, it provides an inclusive framework for the conservation of wet-grassland biodiversity in general across Germany and promotes healthy ecosystems capable of supporting diverse bird communities. The SCP is presented in separate chapters for the Federal States of Lower Saxony and Bremen, Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg, North Rhine-Westphalia, and Bavaria, in addition to a Germany-wide Horizon Scanning survey covering all Federal States in the German continental biogeographic region.

The SCP builds on extensive efforts deployed in Germany for the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds and aims at providing a clear overview of accomplishments and drawing a conservation strategy for the next decades. Its goals are aligned with the European Biodiversity strategies for 2030 to safeguard our biodiversity and reverse its loss (European Commission 2020), and the German National Strategy on Biological Diversity.

This SCP is developed in the framework of the LIFE IP GrassBirdHabitats (LIFE 19 IPE/DE/000004) having the objective to advance the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds and their habitats in the Atlantic region of Europe.

3.2 Wet-grassland Breeding Birds

Wet grasslands, including floodplains, peatlands, mires and wet meadows, are increasingly threatened by the intensification of land-use and agriculture practices all over Europe (Donald et al. 2001). Since the 1950s, widespread practices like the extensive use of pesticides and fertilizers, the lowering of water tables to increase arable land productivity, and the overgrazing of pastures are behind a generalized fragmentation and degradation of wet grasslands across Europe, and Germany is no exception. Krause et al. (2011) estimated a loss of 85.2% and 83.6% of wet and mesic meadows, respectively, in northern Germany in only half a century (1950/1960s to 2008).

The European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is largely the main driver behind wet grassland degradation across Europe. The resulting negative impacts of the CAP on biodiversity in general, and the biodiversity of wet grassland breeding birds more specifically, led to several reforms and the development of the Agri-Environment Schemes (AES). The AES provide important financial resources to encourage farmers to undertake environmentally friendly practices and eventually halt the loss of biodiversity and attain the objectives of a sustainable agriculture. However, a comprehensive assessment of EU-wide impacts of AES on wet grassland biodiversity is still missing. This is mainly because there are multiple AES with a wide range of goals established separately by each Member States and regional governments to address specific, and often local, conservation goals (Díaz and Concepción 2016; Tarjuelo et al. 2021). Franks et al. (2018) in a rare review providing a quantitative assessment of the effectiveness of policy and management interventions used in Europe to improve population and demographic metrics of grassland-breeding waders,

identify positive outcomes for wader population trends and productivity associate with AES. Yet, it is important to mention that the effectiveness of AES have been also shown to be largely dependent on the structure and overall management of the landscape surrounding the area of implementation of AES (Batáry et al. 2015). This calls to develop more synergies between protections areas (e.g., Natura 2000 sites) and areas of implementation of AES.

Wet grassland breeding birds are a very diverse group of species that includes mainly passerines (Passeriformes), water-fowls (Anseriformes), and waders (Charadriiformes). Waders, like the ones included in this SCP, are considered umbrella species of high conservation value and often selected for making conservation-related decisions. The umbrella effect allows the protection of an assemblage of species that constitutes the ecological communities of wet grasslands.

Populations of wet-grassland breeding birds sharply and alarmingly declined across Europe in the past decades (Roodbergen et al. 2012; Thorup 2000; Wilson et al. 2004). This decline is due to a combination of factors, including 1) the generalized destruction of clutches and loss of chicks because of early cropping and mowing practices, amplified by an extensive use of heavy agriculture machinery; 2) the loss of suitable bird habitat due to the lowering of water tables intended to increase arable land productivity. Habitat quality degradation is also due to widespread monocultures and reduced habitat heterogeneity; 3) the decrease of food quality and quantity for chicks as a direct consequence of an extensive use of chemicals and pesticides; and 4) the increased predation of eggs and chicks due to high predator density in degraded grasslands and the unavailability of refuge associated with habitat homogenization. Other factors also contribute to the decline of populations, including climate change, and will be further discussed in the SCP.

Germany is no exception to the loss of grassland biodiversity. Overall trends of grassland bird populations continue to decline across Germany (Kamp et al. 2021) driven by an ever-increasing agricultural land-use intensification (Jerrentrup et al. 2017; Busch et al. 2020; Deutsche Ornithologen-Gesellschaft 2019). The alarming, and still accelerating, decline in populations of wet-grassland breeding birds in Germany is due to the same reasons listed above. Breeding populations of flagship species like the Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* and Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa limosa* lost 93% and 78% over a 36-year time-period (nationwide, based on 2019 estimates, data source DDA/BfN). Few localized conservation success stories where populations of wet grassland breeding birds recovered exist, those will be also presented in this SCP in the section “framework for interventions” providing, therefore, lessons learned and successful conservation experiences to build on.

3.3 The East Atlantic Flyway

A flyway is a route regularly used by migrating bird species to accomplish their annual biological cycle. It includes breeding areas, wintering areas, and all intermediate resting and feeding areas. The terminology of wintering areas becomes obsolete when considering cross-equatorial migratory species and can lead to confusion; hence, it is usually preferable to use the terminology of non-breeding areas instead.

A flyway can be defined at multiple scales. A single-species flyway is the migratory route of one species, a multi-species flyway is the overlap of migration routes of multiple individual populations and species, and a “geopolitical flyway”, is a term sometimes used to

define an area containing species with similar migration routes that are subject to shared international conservation conventions and activities (Boere 2007; Boere and Stroud). For example, the African-Eurasian Migratory Waterbird Agreement (AEWA) is an intergovernmental treaty dedicated to the conservation of migratory waterbirds and their habitats across an area that contains the migration routes of all migratory waterbirds that occur between Africa and western Eurasia. The most widely used terminology for a flyway is still the multi-species flyway (Figure 1), and eight of those have been identified globally (Boere and Stroud 2006). Thus, five flyways connect Eurasia to Oceania and Africa (the East Atlantic flyway, the Mediterranean-Black Sea flyway, the West Asia-Africa flyway, the Central Asia-Indian sub-continent flyway, and the East Asia-Australasia flyway), and three connect the northern and southern American continents (the Pacific Americas flyway, the Mississippi Americas flyway, and the Atlantic Americas flyway).

Figure 1: Map showing the eight main identified global flyways. After Boere & Stroud 2006.

The East Atlantic Flyway (EAF) is a major route for birds migrating between their northern breeding grounds across north-western Europe, Iceland, Greenland, and western Siberia to their wintering grounds in western and southern Europe, and along the coastline of West Africa, from Morocco to South Africa. The EAF covers a total area of more than 45 million km², and is used by 297 migrating bird species (BirdLife International 2022). The EAF groups multiple migration routes where the total length of the flight, the flight path and schedule, and the number of stopovers can vary greatly between species. Some migrations can be relatively short, for example, populations of the Godwit subspecies *Limosa l. islandica* breeding predominantly in Iceland winter in Ireland, and the British Isles. While others can be much longer, for example, populations of the subspecies *Limosa l. limosa*, breeding across north-western Europe winter as far south as the coasts of Senegal and The Gambia. Thus, the EAF links discontinuous breeding and wintering grounds and several important staging grounds and stopovers where migrant birds rest and refuel. This migration of birds can follow different strategies. Piersma (1987) described these strategies as “hop, skip, and jump

strategies”, where bird species migrate over relatively short distances, frequently, or “hop”. Other species fly over greater distances to cross, for example, ecological barriers, or “skip”, and others fly over truly long distances crossing large stretches of continents, or “jump”. The EAF is, therefore, composed of multiple overlapping migration systems and strategies of individual bird populations and species.

Breeding, staging, and non-breeding grounds of many bird species migrating along the EAF are not restricted to the coasts. In addition, to major coastal migrating bird hubs of the EAF, like the Wadden Sea (The Netherlands, Germany, and Denmark), the Tagus Estuary (Portugal), or the Banc d'Arguin (Mauritania), many breeding, staging, and non-breeding grounds occur inland. For example, the charismatic Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa Limosa*, Eurasian Curlew *Numenius arquata*, Ruff *Calidris pugnax*, Redshank *Tringa totanus*, and Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus*, just to name a few, breed primarily inland in wet grasslands of northwestern Europe (e.g., in the Netherlands and Germany). Some of them have also their non-breeding grounds inland along major rivers, lakes, and wetlands of West Africa (e.g., the Black-tailed Godwit is found along the floodplains of the Senegal and Gambia Rivers). Thus, the EAF combines a network of coastal and inland breeding, staging, and non-breeding grounds which are used by different assemblages of migrating bird species.

Flyways, like the EAF, integrate the ecological condition of bird habitats across large biomes of our planet by connecting distant northern and southern environments. They provide an exceptional opportunity to observe the ecological integrity and health of very distant ecosystems and constitute a challenge for conservation where holistic strategies are necessary for successful long-term conservation schemes.

3.4 Germany's Pivotal Role in the East Atlantic Flyway: Key Programs, Initiatives, and Conservation Projects

Germany is an integral part of the East Atlantic Flyway (EAF). It provides essential habitats for breeding, feeding, and resting, supporting populations of numerous species that depend on the flyway for their annual migration. Conservation efforts in Germany are crucial for protecting these birds and their habitats along the flyway. Germany's strong institutional involvement in many flyway-scale programs, initiatives, and projects underscores its crucial role in the conservation of the species considered in this conservation plan. Further, Germany spearhead multiple global species-specific initiatives for the conservation of migratory species, among those the Black-tailed Godwit (*Limosa l. limosa*), as demonstrated recently by major flyway-scale projects.

We present here an overview of the major programs and initiatives dedicated to the conservation of wet-grasslands and wetland birds across the EAF. These programs and initiatives play a direct and crucial role in safeguarding the species highlighted in this conservation plan. By addressing key challenges and promoting sustainable practices, they contribute significantly to the preservation of vital habitats and the protection of threatened species.

Furthermore, we spotlight four recent major projects operating at the East Atlantic Flyway scale. These projects are poised to deliver essential information and insights that will substantially enhance conservation efforts for the species included in this SCP. Through

innovative research and collaborative efforts, these projects aim to provide actionable data that will inform and strengthen future conservation strategies, ensuring the long-term survival and resilience of wetland bird populations along the EAF.

- BirdLife International has established the East Atlantic Flyway Initiative (EAFI) to facilitate the monitoring of bird populations and critical sites, identify conservation priorities, and enhance local capacities in countries along the EAF. The EAFI encompasses all migratory bird species, with a particular focus on waders, and prioritizes countries where BirdLife partners are actively engaged.

Through the Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas (IBA) program, BirdLife aims to identify and safeguard a network of sites that are essential for the long-term survival and viability of bird populations.

- Wetlands International has established the International Waterbird Census (IWC) as a global monitoring program, active in over 143 countries, including most along the EAF. The IWC is significantly supported by volunteer birdwatchers, making it one of the largest citizen-science initiatives worldwide. In many countries, the census is coordinated by professionals who also contribute substantially to the fieldwork on a voluntary basis.
- The Agreement on the Conservation of African-Eurasian Migratory Waterbirds (AEWA) is an international policy agreement operating under the Convention on Migratory Species (also known as the Bonn Convention). Focused on migratory waterbirds, the AEWA plays a crucial role in coordinating flyway-level activities between Africa and Eurasia. The Black-tailed Godwit and the Eurasian Curlew, both featured in this conservation plan, benefit from dedicated AEWA species-specific working groups. These groups meet regularly and are actively involved in several critical activities, including 1) Coordinating Conservation Efforts: They facilitate the implementation of International Single Species Action and Management Plans (ISSAPs and ISMPs), ensuring that conservation strategies are effectively executed across range states. 2) Monitoring and Research: The working groups are tasked with monitoring the populations of these species. Additionally, they support essential scientific research that informs and enhances conservation strategies, ensuring that efforts are data-driven and impactful. 3) Fundraising and Support: The groups assist in raising funds for the implementation of action plans and support range states in developing national action plans. And 4) Communication and Reporting: The working groups facilitate internal and external communication, ensuring that information is shared among stakeholders. They also regularly report on the implementation of action plans to the AEWA Meeting of the Parties.
- The Trilateral Wadden Sea Cooperation serves as the unified framework for the protection and sustainable management of the Wadden Sea as a cohesive ecological entity. Under this umbrella, the Wadden Sea Flyway Initiative (WSFI) provides regular strategic frameworks, with the latest covering the period from 2022 to 2029. These frameworks guide the future activities of WSFI partners along the EAF, aligning with the WSFI flyway vision.

The WSFI frameworks aim to:

- Identify key conservation objectives and targets.
- Prioritize specific actions to achieve these goals.
- Propose timelines for the implementation of these actions.
- Provide rough estimates of the potential costs involved.

- The Migratory Birds for People program is a network of approximately 30 wetland visitor centers across Europe and West Africa, strategically positioned along the flight paths of numerous migratory wetland bird species. Led by the Dutch Staatsbosbeheer, Wetlands International, and Wetlands International West Africa, the program fosters collaboration among these centers to share best practices and innovate new approaches for communicating the importance of wetland conservation to visitors.

Since 2021, MBP has co-organized the East Atlantic Flyway Youth Forum in partnership with the Common Wadden Sea Secretariat and Youth Engaged in Wetlands. This initiative brings young people together virtually to enhance their skills and engagement as future wetland conservationists within the Flyway.

- The Global Flyway Network (GFN) is a collaborative partnership among researchers worldwide dedicated to long-term studies of long-distance migrating waders. By leveraging comparative demographic studies, the GFN aims to understand and analyze the factors influencing wader populations in a rapidly changing world.

In practice, the GFN works to address significant gaps in fieldwork coverage for the world's most threatened wader species. A substantial portion of the GFN's research is focused on the EAF, reflecting the critical importance of this region for migratory bird conservation.

Further, we present a non-exhaustive list of major flyway-scale projects deemed to make substantial impact for the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds along the EAF:

- The project Climate Resilience for Critical Sites for Migratory Birds and People along the East Atlantic Flyway. This project is funded under the International Climate Initiative (IKI), a key funding instrument of the German government to fulfill its commitments within the framework of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). The project identifies existing and potential climate change-driven threats, demonstrates nature-based solutions, and builds capacities for their implementation, benefiting both birds and people. The project is led by the Common Wadden Sea Secretariat, in a consortium formed BirdEyes (University of Groningen), Birdlife International (BLI), Instituto da Biodiversidade e das Áreas Protegidas (IBAP) – Guinea Bissau, Banc d'Arguin National Park (PNBA) – Mauritania, Regional Partnership for Coastal and Marine Conservation (PRCM), Wetlands International (WLI), Omulamba – Angola, Centre for Biodiversity Conservation Research (CBCR) – Ghana, Guinee Ecologie – Guinea, Groupe de Recherche pour la Protection des Oiseaux au Maroc (GREPOM) – Morocco, Namibian Nature Foundation – Namibia, Nigerian Conservation Foundation (NCF) – Nigeria, Conservation Society Sierra Leone (CSSL) – Sierra Leone, BirdLife South Africa (BLSA) – South Africa. This project subscribes in the Wadden Sea Flyway Initiative (WSFI), and further information can be found on the International Climate Initiative website: <https://www.international-climate-initiative.com/en/>.
- The LIFE Integrated Project GrassBirdHabitats (LIFE19IPE/DE/000004) entitled: Conservation of wet-grassland breeding bird habitats in the Atlantic region (01.11.2020 – 31.10.2030). The protection of birds of wetlands and wet-grasslands, such as the Black-tailed Godwit, Lapwing, and Curlew, and their habitats is at the heart of this project funded by the European Union under the LIFE program. The objectives of this project are multiple and transdisciplinary. They include: 1) The restoration and management of

habitats necessary for breeding across Lower Saxony in Germany and the Province on Friesland in the Netherlands), 2) the development of guidance and business models for a more bird friendly sustainable agricultural practices, 3) the development of a multi-species conservation plan along the EAF, and 4) capacity building of stakeholder along the flyway, primarily with a focus on Senegal and The Gambia.

The Ministry of the Environment of Lower Saxony, acts as the coordinating beneficiary, and has tasked the national agency for bird conservation of the Lower Saxony Water Management, Coastal Defense and Nature Conservation Agency (NLWKN) with implementing the project. The partners in Lower Saxony are the Lower Saxony Wadden Sea National Park Authority and BIO-CONSULT OS. The project partners in the Netherlands are the Province of Friesland, the University of Groningen, as well as the agricultural cooperative Collectief Súdwestkust and the nature conservation association Bond Friese VogelWachten. In Senegal, cooperation was established with the Université Gaston Berger, Nature Communauté Développement (NCD), and the National Park authorities. More information about the project can be found on the website <https://www.grassbirdhabitats.eu/>.

- The LIFE GodwitFlyway (LIFE22NAT/DE/101113618) entitled: Conservation of the Black-tailed Godwit along the flyway (01.07.2023 – 31.10.2030). This project target primarily the conservation of the Black-tailed Godwit (*Limosa limosa limosa*) and aims at creating optimized habitats for this species along the East Atlantic Flyway. This includes measures in the most important breeding sites in Lower Saxony, Germany, in staging sites in Portugal, and in wintering sites in The Gambia, West Africa.

The Ministry of the Environment of Lower Saxony, acts as the coordinating beneficiary, and has tasked the national agency for bird conservation of the Lower Saxony Water Management, Coastal Defense and Nature Conservation Agency (NLWKN) with implementing the project. The project partners include the Natur- und Umweltschutzvereinigung Dümmer e.V. in Germany, the University of Groningen in the Netherlands, the Campanhia das Lezirias, the Universidade de Aveiro and the Centro de Estudio do Ambiente e do Mar in Portugal, and the Gambia Department of Parks and Wildlife Management. More information about the project can be found on the website <https://www.godwit-flyway.eu/>.

- East Atlantic Flyway Ecological Network for Coastal Waterbirds. This project aimed to develop detailed, layered maps and a database to identify critical conservation areas for threatened coastal waterbird species along the East Atlantic Flyway. Utilizing cutting-edge network analysis methodologies, the project highlights ecological connectivity and restoration needs, focusing on flagship species, for which there are sufficient data: Black-tailed Godwit and Eurasian Curlew. By providing comprehensive recommendations, the project served as a cornerstone for stakeholder collaboration to ensure the future of these migratory species. The maps produced under this project illustrate protection status, management quality, and gaps in conservation, supporting global biodiversity goals and offering a model for other migratory species and flyways.

This initiative is a joint effort between the RSPB, VBN, BirdLife, in consultation with various intergovernmental agreements, aiming to mobilize resources and enhance conservation capacity. Initial results from this project (see, Beal et al. 2025) demonstrate a promising flyway-scale management perspective, emphasizing the interdependence of priority sites used by migratory species like the Black-tailed Godwit.

3.5 Objectives and Blueprint of the Conservation Plan

The multi-species Strategic Conservation Plan (SCP) for wet-grassland breeding birds in Germany is a comprehensive conservation initiative. It focuses on 11 priority bird species that are central to national conservation efforts. The SCP primarily targets the five federal states located within Germany's Atlantic biogeographic region, which are critical habitats for most wet-grassland breeding birds. The plan also includes Bavaria, where significant conservation efforts have been implemented to protect meadow-breeding bird species.

The key objectives of the SCP are:

1. **Identify and analyze** the primary challenges threatening the conservation of these bird species.
2. **Assess and document** current conservation practices and strategies across Germany.
3. **Develop a strategic framework** for action, presented as a roadmap for targeted interventions.

The multi-species Strategic Conservation Plan (SCP) for wet-grassland breeding birds in Germany is structured into three complementary components (Figure 2). The **General Component** introduces the plan's objectives, presents a detailed overview of the ecology and biology of umbrella species, and analyzes the major threats and challenges they face, including habitat loss, agricultural intensification, climate change, predation, and human disturbances. The **Regional Component** focuses on the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds across Germany, featuring Federal State-specific chapters that examine population status and trends, document prevalent conservation practices, and incorporate findings from a Germany-wide Horizon Scanning Survey—which assesses strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. This section also highlights 11 case studies that demonstrate successful conservation strategies. Finally, the **Roadmap for Action** provides a strategic framework for future efforts, offering an assessment of current conservation practices, synthesizing valuable insights and future priorities, and outlining a clear path forward with actionable goals, habitat protection strategies, policy recommendations, and research priorities.

Developed in collaboration with the wider conservation community, the SCP ensures that its recommendations are feasible, relevant, and supported by those responsible for their implementation. Ultimately, the plan aims to provide a comprehensive, science-based, and actionable blueprint to safeguard wet-grassland breeding birds in Germany, ensuring their long-term survival and the preservation of the ecosystems they depend on.

Figure 2: Blueprint of multi-species Strategic Conservation Plan (SCP).

4 The Ecology and Biology of Umbrella Species

A total of eleven species of wet grassland breeding birds grouped in two species groups are included in this SCP. The species consists mainly of wet-grassland breeding waders including, the Baltic Dunlin *Calidris alpina*, the Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa l. limosa*, the Common Redshank *Tringa totanus*, the Common Snipe *Gallinago gallinago*, the Eurasian Curlew *Numenius arquata*, the Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus*, the Ruff *Calidris pugnax*, syn. *Philomachus pugnax*, the Eurasian Oystercatcher *Haematopus ostralegus*, the Golden Plover *Pluvialis apricaria*, and the Whinchat *Saxicola rubetra*, and the Corncrake *Crex crex* (Figure 3).

The majority of wader species constitute umbrella species having largely comparable biological and ecological requirements and, therefore, occurring in similar habitats and would benefit from related conservation measures. Other species like the Whinchat *Saxicola rubetra* and the Corncrake *Crex crex* have high conservation value, however, displaying more diverse biological and ecological requirements and few particularities.

Eleven bird species at the heart of bird conservation in Germany

Black-tailed Godwit
Uferschnepfe
Limosa l. limosa

Eurasian Curlew
Brachvogel
Numenius arquata

Northern Lapwing
Kiebitz
Vanellus vanellus

Common Snipe
Bekassine
Gallinago gallinago

Golden Plover
Goldregenpfeifer
Pluvialis apricaria

Redshank
Rotschenkel
Tringa totanus

Oystercatcher
Austernfischer
Haematopus ostralegus

Baltic Dunlin
Alpenstrandläufer
Calidris alpina

Ruff
Kampfläufer
Calidris pugnax

Whinchat
Braunkehlchen
Saxicola rubetra

Corncrake
Wachtelkönig
Crex crex

Figure 3: The 11 species of wet-grassland and meadow breeding birds targeted in this multi-species Strategic Conservation Plan (SCP)

4.1 Distribution Range

All species included in this SCP are important migrators of the East Atlantic Flyway and show a strong overlap in their breeding grounds, and for many also in their wintering grounds. Their European breeding grounds include wet grasslands of western and northern Europe, often expanding into Iceland and the Faroes Islands. The East Atlantic Flyway migration route connects their breeding grounds to their wintering grounds in southern Europe, and North and West Africa. We provide below a brief description of their distribution range, the distributions of subspecies when they differ, and some insight into their known distribution in Germany. All of these species are witnessing a dramatic and ongoing decline in their European populations. More information on population trends will be presented later on in this SCP. Distribution ranges shown below (Figures 4 to 14) show the geographic extents of a species range. They are used to present bird distributions on the BirdLife Datazone, the IUCN Red List website, and for assessment of individual species' Red List status (BirdLife International and Handbook of the Birds of the World 2021).

The **Baltic Dunlin** *Calidris alpina* is a small wader breeding in arctic and sub-arctic regions. Populations of the subspecies *C. a. schinzii* breed mainly in Iceland, the Faroes Islands, the British Isles, Scandinavia, and the Baltic, in opposition to the subspecies *C. a. alpina* that breeds in the arctic tundra of northern Scandinavia and northern Russia (Wennerberg 2001). Dunlin pairs breed inland exclusively on short vegetated wet grasslands. In winter, they are highly gregarious birds, found in large flocks on sand beaches, estuaries, and mudflats. They are considered long-distance migrants flying to their wintering grounds in south-western Europe and north-western Africa. About 45,000 dunlins were reported wintering in Portugal in the late 90s (Costa and Rufino 1997), while most birds migrate to more southern wintering grounds on the west coast of Africa. Zwarts et al. (1998) estimated a wintering population of more than 900,000 Dunlins at the Banc d'Arguin in Mauritania. On the west coasts of Europe and Africa, the two subspecies *C. a. schinzii* and *C. a. alpina* show a system of chain migration (Wennerberg 2001). Populations of *C. a. alpina* which breed furthest to the north often winter furthest north in north-western Europe, whereas populations of *C. a. schinzii* breed more to the south, winter even further south in south-western Europe and north-western Africa (Figure 4).

In Germany, Tiedemann (1999) argued that the population of Dunlins of the Wadden Sea includes more birds of the subspecies *C. a. schinzii* in autumn (September) than in spring (Mai) based on mtDNA sequence variation. Wennerberg (2001) did not confirm that, and no clear assumption of the relative occurrence of the two subspecies can therefore be made. Small breeding populations of Dunlin are reported on the German Baltic coast (Thorup et al. 2009).

Figure 4: Plot A shows the European and African distribution range of the Baltic Dunlin *Calidris alpina* during their life cycle. Plot B shows the extent of their distribution during the breeding season in Germany. Data source BirdLife International 2021.

The **Black-tailed Godwit** *Limosa limosa* is a large long-billed wader with a breeding range stretching across northern Europe and some areas of central Asia. The subspecies *L. l. limosa*, often called European or continental Black-tailed Godwit, is distinct from the Icelandic Black-tailed Godwit *L. l. islandica* which breeds primarily in Iceland, and the Asian Black-tailed Godwit *L. l. melanuroides* which breeds primarily in Mongolia, northern China, and Siberia. More recently, a new subspecies, *L. l. bohaili*, has been described by Zhu et al. (2021) and is assumed to breed in the Russian Far East. Godwits breed in wet grasslands, fens, wet meadows, and bogs. The largest breeding population of Godwits in Western Europe is in the Netherlands, with fewer breeding populations in neighboring countries, including Germany. Godwit populations breeding in the Netherlands and Germany (i.e., *Limosa limosa limosa*) often migrate to their wintering grounds in West Africa following the East Atlantic Flyway (Bocher et al. 2013; Delany et al. 2009b; Kirby and Scott 2009). The main stopovers along this annual migration route are wetlands, estuaries, and rice farms of the Iberian Peninsula (Spain and Portugal). Fewer Godwits have been reported to migrate following more eastern routes with stopovers in the south of France (Camargue area) and northern Italy before crossing the Mediterranean Sea and then the Sahara Desert towards their wintering grounds. The main wintering grounds for Godwits are West African estuaries, wetlands, and rice farms in Senegal, the Gambia, and Guinea-Bissau (Figure 5).

In Germany, the largest breeding population of Godwits is found in Lower Saxony with two main populations in the nature conservation areas of Dümmer and Lower Elbe

(Untereibe). Smaller populations are reported in Schleswig-Holstein and North Rhine-Westphalia.

Figure 5: Plot A shows the European and African distribution range of the Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa* during their life cycle. Plot B shows the extent of their distribution during the breeding season in Germany. Data source BirdLife International 2021.

The **Common Redshank** *Tringa totanus* is a medium-sized wader, widespread breeder across much of western and northern Europe, Asia, and Siberia (Figure 6). Six subspecies are identified globally with two occurring in Western Europe, *T. t. robusta* breeding in Iceland and the Faroe Islands, but also found in the British Isles and western continental Europe, and *T. t. tetanus* breeding in western and northern Europe. Redshanks breed on salt marshes, freshwater marshes, wet grasslands, and moorland. Breeding sites are primarily coastal, with fewer breeding sites found in inland wet grasslands. Breeding populations of western Europe winter in southern Europe, around the Mediterranean basin, and along the coasts of West Africa (Piersma et al. 1990). Outside the breeding season, Redshanks are mainly found on shores and salt marshes.

In Germany, the largest breeding populations of Redshanks are found in Schleswig-Holstein and Lower Saxony where saltmarshes of the Wadden Sea support a substantial breeding population (Thyen et al. 2008).

Figure 6: Plot A shows the European and African distribution range of the Common Redshank *Tringa totanus* during their life cycle. Plot B shows the extent of their distribution during the breeding season in Germany. Data source BirdLife International 2021.

The **Common Snipe** *Gallinago gallinago* is a medium-sized stocky wader. It is a widespread, but declining, species breeding in lowland wet grasslands throughout much of Eurasia (Figure 7). The subspecies *G. g. gallinago* breeds in central and northern Europe, and across Asia, while the subspecies *G. g. faeroensis* breeds mainly in Iceland and the Faroe Islands. The migratory patterns of populations of Snipes is rather complex. Migrations is composed of two mutually non-exclusive types, a parallel migration of populations along a latitudinal gradient, and a leap-frog migration along a longitudinal gradient (Minias et al. 2010). Populations breeding in northern and more eastern breeding areas of Europe have their wintering grounds in the western parts of the continent, and others with a more southern distribution migrate to even more southern wintering grounds on the Mediterranean basin and in sub-Saharan Africa.

In Germany, Snipes used to be common in wet-grasslands, wetlands, bogs, and marshes. A sharp population decline has been reported all over Germany, and the breeding populations of Snipe have stabilized recently at a very low level, for example in North Rhine-Westphalia (Jöbges et al. 2012).

Figure 7: Plot A shows the European and African distribution range of the Common Snipe *Gallinago gallinago* during their life cycle. Plot B shows the extent of their distribution during the breeding season in Germany. Data source BirdLife International 2021.

The **Eurasian Curlew** *Numenius arquata* is a large wader emblematic of the wet grasslands of much of Europe and Asia (Figure 8). Three subspecies are recognized, *N. a. arquata* has a breeding range across western, central, and northern Europe, and two other subspecies (*N. a. orientalis* and *suschkini*) occurring primarily in Siberia and Central Asia. Only a small population of Curlew has been reported to breed in Galicia, Spain, constituting the most southern known breeding population of the species (Rodrigues et al. 2019). The vast majority of European breeding Curlews migrate to their wintering grounds in southern Europe or West Africa. Smaller populations of Curlew are found year-round in western Europe and the British Isles.

In Germany, both important breeding grounds and staging grounds occur. Inland wet grasslands are a common breeding habitat for Curlew. Migrating populations from more northern locations use the Wadden Sea (e.g., Hamburger Hallig, eastern German Wadden Sea) as an important resting site along the East Atlantic Flyway (Schwemmer et al. 2016).

Figure 8: Plot A shows the European and African distribution range the Eurasian Curlew *Numenius arquata* during their life cycle. Plot B shows the extent of their distribution during the breeding season in Germany. Data source BirdLife International 2021.

The **Northern Lapwing** *Vanellus vanellus* is a migratory medium-size wader common to European grasslands. It is a wader that often breeds on arable land and short vegetated wet grasslands. During most of the 20th-century Lapwings were able to adapt to agricultural intensification, however, more recent extensive agricultural practices (since the 1980s to date), and additional factors that we will discuss below in this SCP, lead to a European-wide decline of populations (Both et al. 2005). Populations breeding in northern and western Europe mostly winter in more southern grounds in the UK, France, and Spain before returning the year after. More southern breeding populations migrate further to southern breeding grounds for winter, including North African wintering grounds (Figure 9). Thus, Lapwings are migratory over most of the species range (Gillmor and Shrubb 2009), and are still hunted along their migratory routes in Europe and North Africa (Petersen and Trollet 2009).

In Germany, the vast majority of Lapwings occur on arable land where specific conservation measures have been deployed. Measure such as the Lapwing islands and the clutch-and-chick protection have to date yielded limited effects, and did not contribute significantly to limit the decline of this species in Germany. Below in this conservation plan we discuss these measures and provide a comprehensive discussion on their effect.

Figure 9: Plot A shows the European and African distribution range of the Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* during their life cycle. Plot B shows the extent of their distribution during the breeding season over Germany. Data source BirdLife International 2021.

The **Ruff** *Calidris pugnax*, Syn. *Philomachus pugnax* is a medium-sized wader with widespread breeding grounds stretching across most of northern Eurasia (Figure 10). The largest breeding population is in Russia, followed by Scandinavia, while Germany, the Netherlands, and the UK constitute the species most southern breeding range of the species. The vast majority of West European Ruff populations migrate towards their wintering grounds in sub-Saharan Africa, and fewer to the Mediterranean basin. Only a small breeding population of Ruff is found in Western Europe (Germany, the Netherlands, and the UK). During the breeding season, Ruffs are found inland in wet grasslands and fens, while during the non-breeding season, Ruffs can be found in salt and brackish marshes, wetlands, rice farms, and wet grasslands (Del Hoyo et al. 1996).

In Germany, the breeding population of Ruff is primarily confined to floodplains of the the Elbe, Oder, and Weser.

Figure 10: Plot A shows the European and African distribution range of the Ruff *Calidris pugnax* during their life cycle. Plot B shows the extent of their distribution during the breeding season in Germany. Data source BirdLife International 2021.

The **Eurasian Oystercatcher** *Haematopus ostralegus* is one of the largest wader species breeding in European wet grasslands. It is a migratory species over most of its range with four subspecies recognized globally. The subspecies *H. o. ostralegus* breeds mainly in Iceland, Scandinavia, the British Isles, and western Europe, while the three others (*H. o. longipes*, *H. o. buturlini*, and *H. o. osculans*) have more eastern breeding grounds, extending from Ukraine and Turkey to central Asia, China, and the Korean Peninsula. Breeding areas of western European populations cover coastal areas (Figure 11) and extend inland for up to 400 km (Goss-Custard et al.). In the second half of the 20th century, many inland breeding areas were colonized driven by a successful adaptation to breeding on moist and well-fertilized arable land (van de Pol et al. 2014). West European populations of Oystercatcher migrate to more southern wintering grounds in Europe and along the Atlantic coast of West Africa, however, breeding and wintering grounds overlap. Some Oystercatchers winter in the British Isles and along the European Atlantic coast (van de Pol et al. 2014).

In Germany, the Wadden Sea provides important roosting and feeding grounds for wintering Oystercatchers (Scheiffarth and Becker 2008). Breeding couples are found primarily inland in the wet-grasslands of Lower Saxony, Schleswig-Holstein, and North Rhine-Westphalia. Also, the Wadden Sea is home to a resident population of Oystercatchers found year-round.

Figure 11: Plot A shows the European and African distribution range of Eurasian Oystercatcher *Haematopus ostralegus* during their life cycle. Plot B shows the extent of their distribution during the breeding season over Germany. Data source BirdLife International 2021.

The **European Golden Plover** *Pluvialis apricaria* is a small wader with a breeding range stretching across the arctic tundra, from Iceland to the west to Scandinavia and central Siberia to the east. The most southern breeding populations are found in the northern parts of the British Isles, in Scotland and Northern Ireland. The wintering range of Plover stretches south across France and the Iberian Peninsula to northwestern Africa. Few other wintering populations are found around the Mediterranean basin. Plovers are upland breeding waders breeding primarily in moorland habitats. Breeding pair occurrence is often driven by the presence of their favorite prey, including crane flies (*Tipula spp.*), Coleoptera, and march flies (Whittingham et al. 2001). Like Lapwings, flocks of wintering Plovers can be found foraging on inland arable land during the non-breeding season (Gregory 1987; Fuller and Lloyd 1981).

In Germany, the only breeding population in Lower Saxony is considered at high risk of extinction. In 2003 only 12 pairs were accounted for (Exo 2005), while the most recent Red List census in 2020 did not account for any remaining breeding pairs (census conducted by NLWKN 2021). A nationwide census showed an ongoing decline of Plover populations (e.g., -12% decline between 2003 and 2008 (Hötker 2004; Gillings et al. 2012). Most wintering Plovers are found in Schleswig-Holstein, Lower Saxony, and Mecklenburg-Vorpommern on arable land, grassland, saltmarshes, and coastal sand- and mudflats (Gillings et al. 2006; Hötker 2004). Surprisingly these wintering populations are not depicted in the data obtained from Birdlife (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Plot A shows the European and African distribution range of the European Golden Plover *Pluvialis apricaria* during their life cycle. Plot B shows the extent of their distribution during the breeding season in Germany. Data source BirdLife International 2021.

The **Whinchat** *Saxicola rubetra* is a small migratory passerine with a breeding distribution range covering most of Europe and western Asia (Figure 13). Breeding Whinchats can be found predominantly in the British Isles, central, northern, and eastern Europe. Their wintering grounds are primarily in sub-Saharan Africa stretching across the African continent from Senegal to the west to Kenya to the east, and further down the Great Rift Valley to Zambia. Whinchats favor open landscapes with scattered small shrubs and used to be common birds of upland and Alpine open grassland and lowland wet grasslands of Europe. Whinchat is one of many species that are currently witnessing an alarming sharp decline in populations across Europe.

In Germany, breeding Whinchat pairs can be found across all Federal States in temperate Atlantic and Continental climates. Due to the short breeding season between April and August, and often only one possible annual brood, successful breeding is all the more important. And this unfortunately becomes all the more difficult the fewer habitats the Whinchat has left.

Figure 13: Plot A shows the European and African distribution range of the Whinchat *Saxicola rubetra* during their life cycle. Plot B shows the extent of their distribution during the breeding season over Germany. Data source BirdLife International 2021.

The **Corncrake** *Crex crex* is a medium-sized ground-living bird species associated with grassland, wet-grassland, and floodplain habitats. It breeds primarily in western, eastern, and northern Europe, and across central Siberia and western China (Figure 14). Only a few populations are found on the British Isles. Migrating Corncrakes can be found around Mediterranean North Africa and migrate following a more eastern flyway along the Nile valley through Africa. Non-breeding grounds include North Africa, and East and South East Africa. Like the Whinchat, populations of Corncrake have shown a decline across Europe, however, important inter-annual fluctuations have been reported (Bellebaum et al. 2016).

In Germany, Corncrake pairs breed in all Federal States but they are most abundant in northern and northeastern plains (Bellebaum et al. 2016). The species was considered primarily inhabiting wet grasslands, floodplains, and other open habitats, however, more recently, intensively managed arable areas have also been shown to support important populations in North-Rhine Westphalia (Joest and Koffijberg 2016). Populations in arable land have been found to succeed primarily due to the presence of preserved vegetated strips and increased habitat heterogeneity.

Figure 14: Plot A shows the European and African distribution range of the Corncrake *Crex crex* during their life cycle. Plot B shows the extent of their distribution during the breeding season over Germany. Data source BirdLife International 2021.

4.2 Ecological Requirements

4.2.1 Breeding and Nesting Habitats

Breeding and nesting habitat requirements for wader species are to a large extent comparable. These requirements include the availability of wet grasslands sustained by high groundwater levels with temporarily flooded areas. Open shallow ponds and muddy depressions are also important in the breeding habitat at the beginning of the breeding season. Quality breeding areas should be composed of a mosaic of bare and grass patches providing shelter for fledglings when needed, however, vegetated field margins and field hedges are usually avoided as they provide hideouts for predators. Breeding landscapes should remain open without any vertical structures like trees, buildings, and wind turbines. The fragmentation of open landscapes leads to a loss of breeding habitat quality, and many of these species keep away from vertical structures by at least 100 to 300 m (e.g., Northern Lapwing (Barkow et al. 2020)). Species with elaborated courtships, like the Ruff, might require slightly elevated areas with very short to no vegetation.

All species nest on the ground on dry or damp soil in low vegetation (Figure 15). Nests are usually well hidden in the vegetation in densely overgrown areas (e.g., Common Redshank or Common Snipe) or covered by some vegetation collected by the breeding pair

(e.g., Ruff). The majority of species nest in sparse colonies, e.g., Black-tailed Godwit, or in larger more dense colonies, e.g., Northern Lapwing, and therefore nesting areas should be large enough to sustain large colonies of nesting pairs.

Figure 15: Nests of Black-tailed Godwit (A), Curlew (B), Redshank (C), Lapwing (D) and Snipe (E). all photos are taken in the Dümmer SPA. Photo credit: A: Christopher Marlow, B and C: Andreas Barkow, D: Johannes Melter, E: Verena Rupprecht.

The Northern Lapwing is among the few species that are capable of nesting in intensively used arable land when the crops are in their early stage of growth (e.g., maize, cereal, and sugar beet fields). However, breeding success in such habitats is very low and not sufficient to maintain a viable breeding population (Milsom 2005; Sudmann et al. 2014).

The Corncrake nests in vegetated areas with medium to high grass in fallow land and grasslands, usually late spring or early summer. It tolerates the presence of low bushes, field hedges, or even individual trees. The corncrake nests individually with a territory of around a 100-m radius. The Golden Plover nests in tundra landscapes in relatively undisturbed moorland. Nests are often shallow depressions lined with lichen, moss, grass, or leaves. The Oystercatcher breeds in open landscapes with sparse vegetation, similar to species in Group-I, however, it has also been observed to nest on vegetated and naturalized building rooftops. Roof-breeding populations of Oystercatchers have been recorded (at least) in the UK, the Netherlands, Belgium, and Germany. Whinchats build well-hidden nests in depressions in the ground often at the foot of tall herb stalks, fence posts, and small bushes. Nests are also found at the edges of pathways, ditches, and field hedges. In that, they differ from the other species included in the SCP by their preference for more densely vegetated landscapes.

4.2.2 Staging and Wintering Habitats

Staging and wintering habitats are fundamental components of the migratory flyway (Figure 16). Birds spend the majority of their annual cycle in these habitats where they find shelter for roosting and food necessary to restore their energetic reserves and accomplish their annual migrations towards their breeding grounds. In the EAF, the main staging and wintering habitats occur primarily in southern Europe and western Africa. These are wetlands of large-river deltas, coastal inland wetlands, mud flats (i.e., tidal flats), and rice farms. Staging and wintering habitats of the Whinchat *Saxicola rubetra*, and the Corncrake *Crex crex* greatly differ from those of the other wader species included in the SCP by being not necessarily aquatic and spreading much more inland across the African Continent. The Corncrake, for example, is mostly found in grass-dominated wintering habitats mirroring their habitat preferences in their breeding grounds (Walther et al. 2013).

The conservation of the integrity of staging and wintering habitats is fundamental for the conservation of these migratory birds. Wetlands in South Europe and West Africa are increasingly facing water stresses due to climate change. In a few cases, this is accompanied by changes in agricultural practices where rice farming is being replaced by other crops less water-dependent. The loss of these artificial (i.e., man-made) wetlands can jeopardize the conservation of some species, like the Black-tailed Godwit, that benefit from rice fields in Spain and Portugal. Also, the industrialization of rice farming practices in many places in West Africa (e.g., Senegal) is contributing to the loss of habitat suitable for wintering waders. Many, benefited from the traditional unmechanized farming of rice.

Figure 16: Drone-captured aerial view of over 15,000 Black-tailed Godwits at the EVOA (Espaço de Visitação e Observação de Aves) lagoon, Portugal, on November 6, 2024. Credit: University of Aveiro.

4.2.3 Diet of Chicks, Juveniles, and Adults

All juveniles or chicks of wader species included in the SCP are nidifugous and able to leave the nest shortly after hatching and to feed on their own (Figure 17). They are never fed by their parents (except the Oystercatcher, see below) and often, after hatching, one of the parents departs (usually the female) leaving the chicks with the other parent (usually the male) to be guided in foraging on insects and other arthropods found in wet grasslands. Thus, insects, terrestrial arthropods, and worms are the main food items for chicks. Their high density and biomass in breeding grounds are vital to ensure breeding success and the fast development of juveniles before migration. Adult birds, having more developed bills and legs, are perfectly specialized to feed in different habitats and on different food sources. For example, Curlews are specialized to feed in mudflats, where the bird probes deep into the mud to catch worms, crabs, and mollusks. Lapwings, having medium-length bills, are able to eat invertebrates both on and under the surface ground, including worms, insects, and snails. Adult birds often flock together in staging and wintering grounds where they feed in shallow wetlands, salt marshes, mudflats, shorelines, and rice farms.

Figure 17: Newly hatched Black-tailed Godwit chicks. Photo: Andreas Barkow.

Chicks of Oystercatchers are actively fed by their parents, who collect and bring prey items to them. Undoubtedly, this is one reason behind the ability of Oystercatchers to breed on roof-tops where natural food items are scarce (pers. Com. Barkow). Whinchat chicks, like all passerines, are altricial nidicolous relying on their parents for food and protection. Prey items are primarily insect larvae and imagos. Plover and Corncrake chicks are nidifugous independent feeders foraging on insect larvae and adults including flies and beetles, however, relying on different protection techniques. Plover chicks rely on camouflage featuring muted colors suited to fit in their environment, while Corncrake chicks hide in medium-to-tall grass. Adult whinchats and Corncrake are largely insectivorous, feeding mainly on terrestrial insects, and consuming other invertebrates including spiders, snails, and worms (Arbeiter et al. 2020), often in medium-to-tall vegetated wet-grasslands and often in arable land.

4.3 Conservation and Management Requirements for Migratory Bird Species

The conservation of migratory species often requires intensive international collaboration and alignment of objectives. Many treaties, agreements, and conventions provide a strong framework for bird conservation along the EAF. Those, include the Ramsar Convention, constituting an international treaty for the conservation and sustainable use of wetlands globally. The Bern Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats provides a binding international legal instrument for Nature Conservation and covers European and few West African countries. The European Union's Birds Directive and the Habitat Directive, together provide the backbone of nature conservation across Europe and form a network of protected sites across the European Union called Natura 2000. Most recently, the Agreement on the Conservation of African-Eurasian Migratory Waterbirds (AEWA) established an international treaty to coordinate efforts for the conservation of bird species migrating between European and African nations. This agreement focuses on bird species that depend primarily on wetlands for at least a part of their lifecycle and cross international borders in their migration patterns.

The 11 species included in this SCP are all considered inter-continental migratory species. Their conservation requires implementing actions in their respective breeding, staging, and wintering grounds and the failure to secure adequate habitats along their migratory routes can result in a loss of specific populations or even the loss of species. A key recommendation of the International Multi-Species Action Plan for the Conservation of Breeding Waders in Wet Grassland Habitats in Europe published in 2018 (Leyrer et al. 2018) is the urgent need to develop additional action plans that address conservation challenges in non-breeding seasons. Therefore, broad-scale initiatives addressing the conservation of migratory birds in their breeding and non-breeding (i.e., staging and wintering) grounds, coupled with site-based specific interventions, is key to achieving long-lasting conservation success.

5 Threats and Challenges

Threats to the conservation of grassland breeding birds are numerous and many are well-known. Their types and intensity can vary along the EAF and their impacts on the populations of bird species included in this SCP are diverse. Such impacts depend on the birds' life cycle and the availability of alternative habitats and resources. Here we provide an overview of the main threats and challenges to the conservation of migratory grassland breeding birds and we provide, when possible, examples that relate to the species included in this SCP.

5.1 Farming Intensification and Practices

The intensification of farming is undoubtedly the main driver of wet-grassland bird population declines along the East Atlantic Flyway. It is the main cause of habitat degradation, and nest and chick losses in breeding grounds across Europe, and is increasingly being identified as a major threat in wintering and staging grounds in southern Europe and all across West Africa. Here we provide an overview of current farming practices that have direct negative consequences on bird populations and we discuss their implication for bird conservation.

5.1.1 Monocultures

Widespread monocultures are a direct consequence of agricultural intensification that creates species-poor landscapes with homogenized habitats for bird, insect, and mammal species. This homogenization affects grassland breeding birds by decreasing food availability, diminishing shelter for chicks, reducing nesting opportunities for breeding pairs, and often enabling increased predation. Kentie et al. (2013) found that chicks of Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa l. limosa* hatched on monocultures had lower growth and survival rates than chicks on meadows, indicating that these chicks suffer a higher risk of starvation and/or predation. They argue that the provision of herb-rich meadows with high groundwater tables is essential to increase the survival rates of chicks. Kentie et al. (2015) reiterate by showing that nest survival is higher in herb-rich meadows than in monocultures and that increased predator density is an increased threat during the nesting stage only if habitat quality is low, a habitat condition often associated with monocultures.

5.1.2 Mechanization, and early and frequent mowing

The increased mechanization of agriculture with a greater emphasis on higher productivity and yields per hectare, increased silage production, and the development of new automated harvesting techniques had severe consequences on nest and chick survival of grassland breeding birds across Europe.

Early mowing is the main cause of the mechanical destruction of nests and chicks of wet grassland breeding birds. It affects mainly wader species that start breeding relatively late in taller grass, such as the Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa* and Redshank *Tringa totanus*, than species that nest in short grass such as the Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* and the Oystercatcher *Haematopus ostralegus* (Kruk et al. 1996). Mowing has also been documented to affect Corncrake *Crex crex* and Whinchat *Saxicola rubetra* populations, where earlier and more frequent mowing, associated with a switch from hay to silage production, has caused high rates of nest, adult, and chick mortality and nest loss (Vickery et al. 2001; Tome et al. 2020).

In addition to the timing, the frequency of mowing has a negative effect on bird populations. More frequent mowing affects the availability and abundance of insects and arthropods available as food items for chicks (Schekkerman and Beintema 2007a; Kleijn et al. 2010b). In a foraging experiment conducted by Schekkerman and Beintema (2007a), captive-raised godwit chicks ingested 31% fewer prey per unit time when foraging in cut agricultural grasslands than in uncut reserve fields. This difference is considered large enough to compromise chick growth and survival. In comparison, chicks from wild broods chose to stay in reserve fields (i.e., uncut grass), especially after agricultural fields had been cut, and traveled towards reserve fields over distances up to more than 0.5 km. This preference for reserve grasslands declined from early June onwards when chicks reached a certain size.

Single-brooded bird species can lay replacement clutches, however, when mowing is more frequent, it can affect the fitness of a species by producing late, and often weaker, fledglings that have fewer chances to survive the upcoming winter season.

5.1.3 Excessive drainage of wet grasslands and wetlands

Lowland wet grasslands of northern Europe (e.g., in the Netherlands and Germany) are characterized by shallow water tables (Dietrich et al. 2021). They have been extensively and excessively drained in the last century to optimize agricultural net production. This had a detrimental impact on the availability of breeding habitats for many inland breeding waders (e.g., Northern Lapwing or Black-tailed Godwit), and greatly reduced the number and range of breeding wader species across western Europe (Eglington et al. 2010). Wader chicks require wet invertebrate-rich foraging habitats and most drained wet grasslands, transformed into arable land, are currently too dry to support sustainable breeding populations.

Excessive drainages affect also wetlands along the East Atlantic Flyway. Wetlands and marshes in Mediterranean countries, like Spain and Portugal, have been to a large extent lost to agriculture or to coastal urban development. For instance, the Doñana Wetlands National Park in South West Spain only constitutes the remaining 54,252 ha of the original 180,000 ha of marshlands in the Guadalquivir delta (Green et al. 2016). It includes 30,000 ha of seasonal marshes heavily dependent on surface flow and particularly important for migrating waders and other bird species. However, recently, these marshes have been severely affected by extreme droughts and are still threatened by additional water abstraction for agricultural and urban uses (Navedo et al. 2022). Mediterranean and West African wetlands are expected to suffer greatly due to climate change and currently major efforts are being deployed to address this threat. Among those efforts, is the climate-resilient site network in the African-Eurasian flyway, funded by the International Climate Initiative (IKI) of the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU).

5.1.4 Extensive use of fertilizers and pesticides

The use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides to increase the net primary production of grass- and arable land is perhaps the most significant human intervention that shaped our landscapes in the last century. This was accompanied by the development of monocultures and the loss of biodiversity below and above the surface of soils. The extensive use of fertilizers modified the feeding and nesting habitats for wet grassland breeding birds. For instance, the rapid growth of grass and vegetation as a consequence of fertilizers, particularly in spring, can affect the foraging efficiency and the availability of nesting sites for waders. The Northern Lapwing prefers relatively short vegetation for nesting and may abandon sites when the vegetation gets taller than 10 to 15 cm. Other species like the Common Snipe *Gallinago gallinago* and the Redshank *Tringa totanus*, tend to prefer sparse taller vegetation, however, when tall grass is too dense it can affect prey accessibility for bird species that detect prey visually, like the Northern Lapwing, or that probe for prey like the Common Snipe.

The use of fertilizers and pesticides affects the topsoil and vegetation fauna. It affects both the biodiversity and abundance of bird prey items like arthropods and worms. There is also evidence that high inputs of fertilizer and intensive grazing or mowing may be particularly detrimental to larger insect species (Beintema et al. 1990). A foraging experiment in the Netherlands combining the examination of fertilizers and mowing (Schekkerman and Beintema 2007b) showed that Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa* chicks ingested one-third fewer prey items per unit-time when foraging in managed grasslands (i.e., high fertilizer input and 2-3 cuts starting early to mid-May), in comparison to unfertilized and uncut reserve

fields. A difference that is considered large enough to compromise the growth and survival of chicks.

The use of fertilizers and pesticides is increasingly affecting West African wintering grounds, where habitats created by traditional rice farms are considered essential to sustaining wintering populations of many wader species included in this SCP. A shift from traditional rice farming practices to more mechanized ones, coupled with the extensive use of fertilizers and pesticides, can jeopardize the survival of these birds. In addition to being potentially toxic and lethal to the birds, the use of pesticides (Parsons et al. 2010) affects the availability of prey items, and therefore the capacity of adult birds to build energy reserves necessary for their migration to breeding grounds on the European continent.

5.2 Predation

Predation is a natural ecological process. When a predator kills a prey, this does not necessarily have long-term consequences on the population of the prey. In natural and healthy ecosystems, predators kill primarily the weak or sick individuals that often do not contribute to the breeding success of a species. Predators also prey on nests and weak fledglings, however, many ground-nesting wader species have developed elaborate defense behaviors and mechanisms to limit the effect of such predation on populations. For example, the Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* protects its nest by aggressively attacking predators in proximity (Kis et al. 2000), while other species, like the Golden Plover *Pluvialis apricaria*, feign injury to distract the predators from the location of their nests or chicks.

Here we discuss predation in its excessive and extensive forms often driven by habitat degradation, the alteration of food webs, and the introduction of invasive predator species. However, it is important to remember that predation is a conservation issue only if it occurs at a sufficient level to reduce the size of a breeding population at a site.

Nest predation is a recurrent issue in the conservation of grassland-breeding birds in Europe. It is a leading cause of reproductive failure and is often one of the main drivers of bird population decline. Nest predation has a disproportionate impact on vulnerable bird populations, especially within the context of habitat fragmentation and agriculture intensification. For example, intensive agriculture can reduce the protective cover for chicks making them more vulnerable to predators (Schekkerman et al. 2009), can affect food availability and drive chicks into risk-taking behavior exposing them to predators, or provide habitat conditions where predators can thrive and, as a consequence, increase predation pressure. Landscape vegetation structure has been shown to have disparate effects on predation on wader species. Laidlaw et al. (2015) found that predation rates of the Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* nests increased significantly with distance from patches of taller vegetation (> 15cm), and decreased with increasing areas of taller vegetation within 1 km of the nest, whereas the effects of landscape vegetation height did not influence nest predation probability of the Common Redshank *Tringa totanus* which breeds at much lower densities and hide their nests in vegetation. They argue that lower predation of Lapwing nests in a landscape with taller heterogeneous vegetation could result from increased availability of small mammal prey associated with habitats with taller vegetation (e.g., voles and mice). The presence of small mammal prey reduces the need for predators to search in open fields for wader nests. However, it is important to acknowledge that the presence of tall vegetation could also attract predators who can seek shelter in tall grass, and by an effect of spill-over,

end up affecting the reproductive success of wet grassland breeding birds. This example illustrates the complexity of prey-predator interactions affecting wader bird species and urges to first understand these processes that can be different at each conservation site, and from year to year.

Predators of both chicks and eggs of ground-nesting grassland breeding birds comprise a range of generalist predators native to Europe, including mammals like the Red Fox *Vulpes vulpes*, Stoat *Mustela erminea*, Weasel *Mustela nivalis*, Badger *Meles meles*, Polecat *Mustela putorius*, Stone Marten *Martes foina*, Pinemarten *Martes martes*, and avian species like the Grey Heron *Ardea cinerea*, Marsh Harrier *Circus aeruginosus*, and many species of corvids, particularly the Carrion Crow *Corvus corone*. Other introduced predator species include the Common Raccoon Dog *Nyctereutes procyonoides*, American Mink *Neogale vison*, and Raccoon *Procyon lotor*. Predator species and densities can differ between areas and are often conditioned by landscape features (e.g., vegetation structure, the presence of nearby waterbodies, or the presence of woody plants and vertical structures) and proximity to other habitats. Mammal and avian predators have also different impacts on the nest and chick survival. Butcher and Smart (2009) in a study examining predation on Northern Lapwing nests and chicks in wet grasslands in southern England and the Netherlands, showed that mammalian predators prey primarily on Northern Lapwing nests, while chicks are preyed on primarily by avian predators.

Before any generalized predator management prescriptions (both active - e.g., hunting or trapping - and passive - e.g., fencing - predator management) for the conservation of nesting areas of wet grassland breeding birds, it is important to determine the assemblage of predators affecting the target area, the bird species to protect, and the mechanisms by which the landscape structure and predator density and distribution affect prey-predator interactions as those can greatly vary among locations (Bolton et al. 2007; Laidlaw et al. 2015). Culling of predators is a complex and expensive intervention, it is controversial in many countries and often used as a last option to stabilize or increase the reproductive success of localized endangered populations.

Predation on adult birds is less of a concern for conservation in general. Few localized events occur when, for example, Peregrines falcon *Falco peregrinus* nests are installed too close to breeding sites. Such events can be avoided with adapted management, and the main predators for adult birds are still humans. This aspect will be discussed in the following section Hunting and harvesting.

5.3 Hunting and Harvesting

Many of the species included in the SCP are still hunted and harvested (i.e., for subsistence, monetary value, or recreational) today along the flyway. In their European breeding grounds, only two species (Dunlin *Calidris alpina* and Corncrake *Crex crex*) are listed under Annex I of the European Birds Directive (DIRECTIVE 2009/147/EC), granting them special conservation measures concerning their habitat in order to ensure their survival and reproduction in their area of distribution. The other eight species, with the exception of Whinchat *Saxicola rubetra*, are listed under Annex II and can still be potentially hunted in some European countries along the EAF. However, hunting is forbidden during their return migration to nesting areas, during their reproduction period, and when they are raising chicks. Additionally, the harvesting of eggs is strictly prohibited in all European Member States. Some species, like

the Black-tailed Godwit initially subject to hunting in France, have seen their hunting suspended due to the vulnerable status of the species (since 2008 for the Black-tailed Godwit). Other species like the Northern Lapwing and the Golden Plover are still hunted in large numbers. In France alone, an estimated 97,700 and 12,600 Northern Lapwing and Golden Plover individuals, respectively, were hunted during the 2013-2014 hunting season (Trolliet et al. 2018). The impact of hunting on populations of wet grassland breeding birds is an ongoing debate. Some studies argue that hunting is not a significant contributor to the large-scale decline of populations (see, REF for the Northern Lapwing populations (Souchay and Schaub 2016), while others argue that hunting accelerates the current decline of several species with unfavorable conservation status, such as the Northern Lapwing (Hirschfeld and Heyd 2005).

Studies on hunting and harvesting grassland breeding birds in Africa are still very rare. A recent survey by Deniau et al. (2022) on hunting and harvesting of birds in seven main Sahel-Saharan wetlands from West to East Africa showed that waterbird harvesting is a widespread practice, however, Afrotropical species were more hunted than Palearctic species, and migratory birds represented only a limited part of the harvested populations. Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa* accounted for 3.94% (7,264 individuals) of the harvested birds in the Inner Niger Delta between 2018 and 2019. Kleijn et al. (2010a) also reported that the overall number of Black-tailed Godwit shot annually in their core wintering range in West Africa stayed relatively low.

Other species included in this SCP are also subject to legal or illegal hunting and harvesting in North and West African countries, however, few studies provide quantitative assessments of the impact of such activities on bird populations. The persistence of many species of grassland breeding birds along the EAF depends on high adult survival. Indeed, reproductive successes are currently very low in Europe, and the maintenance of European grassland breeding bird populations to a large extent is a factor in high adult survival and return rates. The impacts of hunting and harvesting pressure need to be more clearly evaluated as any changes in adult survival rates are expected to have severe consequences on the conservation of the EAF populations.

5.4 Climate Change

Climate change is a major threat to wet grassland breeding birds and represents a particularly complex challenge in the context of a flyway approach (NAGY et al. 2021). Many species, like waders, are particularly susceptible to climate change as they migrate for their annual cycle between multiple biomes and climate zones. Further, species are expected to be affected directly by climate-related events (among others, extreme temperatures, unexpected rain, and storm events) or indirectly through the loss or degradation of their habitat. We summarize here the main challenges facing the conservation of grassland breeding birds and present a few examples, when available.

- 1) **Changes related to phenology**, i.e., the timing of seasonal life-cycle events. In a study examining 80 years of data by Petersen et al. (2012) on the arrival time of wader species in their breeding grounds in Denmark, they found that species like the Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa*, Common Redshank *Tringa totanus*, and Ruff *Calidris pugnax* are arriving now 13, 14 and 42 days earlier, respectively. The time of arrival was associated with changes in local temperature and precipitation as well as winter conditions (i.e., North

Atlantic oscillation Index). The observation of the breeding initiation of the same three species and the Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* in the same locations showed that the Northern Lapwing and the Common Redshanks advanced their breeding initiation by about a week, while in contrast the Black-tailed Godwit and the Ruff did not advance their egg-laying time leading to significantly prolonged pre-laying period (Meltofte et al. 2018). Converging results have also been reported in the Netherlands (Musters et al. 2010), where the analysis of ringing dates on more than 35,000 Black-tailed Godwit and 112,000 Northern Lapwing chicks between 1960 and 2004 showed that the Northern Lapwing breeding earlier than in 1960 while the Black-tailed Godwit did not exhibit significant earlier breeding. A reservation on the “non-response” of Black-tailed Godwit to changing climate was published in 2018, where Kentie et al. (2018) predicted a slight advance in the egg-laying dates of about 2 days in low agricultural land and 3 days in fields with higher land-use intensity. They argue that this change may be too modest to be empirically detected in previous studies, particularly as variation in laying dates between years can be large, however, it shows a notable interaction between climate and habitat degradation on the phenology of Black-tailed Godwit.

- 2) **Changes in the distribution range.** In a general warming trend, the distribution of many terrestrial organisms is shifting to more northern latitudes (Chen et al. 2011; Amano et al. 2020). This statement is now supported for waders and grassland breeding birds by a growing body of literature showing changes in the climate envelope of species in response to changes in climate. Godet et al. (2011) examining a 33-year dataset of wintering waders in France showed a significant shift in migratory bird assemblage composition in response to climate change. They found consistent changes in species more dependent on high temperatures and an important reassembly of wader assemblages in their coastal wintering grounds. Across northern Europe, the center of gravity of many wader species has been also reported to be substantially shifting in a general North-East direction, however, this shift appears to be predominantly driven by range expansion rather than an overall range shift (Maclean).
- 3) Climate change can directly affect the **vital rates of migratory birds**. Adverse weather and unexpected extreme weather events can affect the survival of weakened migrating waders directly by increasing the rates of heat loss for the bird’s body or by exhausting the bird’s energetic reserves. There is a lack of studies examining how climate change directly affects the vital rates of migratory wader species, however, a recent study by Loonstra et al. (2019) shows that adverse wind conditions during the northward Sahara crossing of the EAF migratory Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa limosa* significantly increased in-flight mortality. Further, they argue that it is likely that climate change-related fluctuations in wind conditions will have future negative consequences on migratory birds.
- 4) **Loss of breeding, staging, and wintering habitats**, and the degradation of habitat quality. Climate change is expected to greatly affect the availability of wetlands along the EAF. Rising sea levels and an increased frequency of extreme weather events are likely to degrade coastal wetlands, estuaries, and salt marshes, through a change in their extent or changes in environmental variables important for waterbird habitat quality (e.g., salinity levels). Inland wetlands and wet-grasslands are also likely to be affected by changes in temperature, rainfall patterns and timing, and variations in the cyclic inundation regimes. For example, heatwaves or early rainfall can drive a decoupling between insect emergence and egg hatching, jeopardizing therefore the survival of wader

chicks that depend heavily on insects as a food source. Wetlands International (BREINER et al. 2022) in a comprehensive assessment of habitat suitability of Critical Sites for bird conservation in the African-Eurasia Waterbird flyways, estimated a 57% reduction of habitat suitability by 2050. Critical Sites for waterbirds were identified under the Wings over Wetlands project using Important Bird and Biodiversity Area data from BirdLife International and International Waterbird Census data from Wetlands International. Climate-related changes are also expected to increase human-wildlife conflicts where the scarcity of aquatic resources in African and Mediterranean countries will increase the pressures on natural aquatic resources for agricultural and human needs.

It is important to acknowledge that climate change might have adverse impacts where certain species will profit from a distribution range expansion or access to new more favorable breeding and staging grounds. This has been suggested by Maclean et al. (2008) examining the distribution of waders in 35,000 sites over 30 years covering a major portion of western Europe. Thus, they discuss that with warming temperatures hitherto unsuitable habitats in northern Europe will host increasingly important wader populations, however, this might not match the population declines elsewhere. It is unlikely that overall wetland and wet grassland breeding birds will benefit from climate change as wetlands are among the most threatened habitats due to climate change.

5.5 Other Threats

- **Interspecific competition**, or the competition between individuals of different species, can occur naturally among species occupying the same habitat. Individuals from different species can compete for space or resources. This is most problematic when species of high conservation value are affected or when the populations of introduced or invasive species start to negatively affect native species. Geese, e.g. the Greylag Goose *Anser anser*, are among the species that witnessed a significant population growth in inland breeding habitats of waders. They are potentially in direct competition with species like the Eurasian Oystercatcher *Haematopus ostralegus*, Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus*, Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa*, and Common Redshank *Tringa tetanus* in their breeding habitats. However, to date, there is no consensus on whether breeding, wintering, or foraging geese have a negative impact on wet grassland breeding birds. In the Netherlands, Greylag Goose *Anser anser* densities between 33 to 458 individuals per 100 ha have been reported by Kleijn et al. (2011) with no significant negative effects on grassland breeding birds. In a more recent study, Tamis and Heemskerk (2020), reported a negative correlation between geese density and densities of wet grassland breeding birds (the four species cited above), while Madsen et al. (2019) found no significant adverse impact of spring grazing Barnacle Goose *Branta leucopsis* on the nesting densities of the same four species, with an only slight negative effect on the population of Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa*.
- **Disease outbreaks** in waders and birds, in general, are common. For example, links between the avian flu and migratory waders are well documented. Waders are considered a major reservoir for low pathogenic avian influenza (Olsen et al. 2006), and the relatively high virus prevalence in waders occurring in wetlands may be due in part to the efficient transmission through the fecal-oral route via surface waters (Webster et al. 1978). Also, the dissipation of disease among different populations of wader species is

facilitated by their gregarious behaviors during their migratory cycles and flocking in staging and feeding grounds. Disease outbreaks can lead to significant mortality in bird populations, however, it constitutes only a conservation issue when populations of high conservation value species are affected.

- **Light and noise pollution** alter how animals interpret environmental signals. In natural and semi-natural wetlands these pollutions are expected to have limited direct effects on bird populations, however, effects can be more significant in areas close to heavily urbanized spaces. A study accounting for six wader species in the Tagus Estuary (Santos et al. 2010) showed that artificial light favors visual foragers at night, improving rate intake by up to 83%, however, the light drew the birds to degraded and developed areas potentially exposing them to higher predator pressure. Loud noise deters birds from their feeding and resting grounds and is expected to have negative effects on birds by increasing their stress levels and disturbing their activities.
- **Wind farms** can potentially impact bird populations through collisions, habitat degradation, avoidance and barrier effects, displacement, or exclusion from breeding or foraging grounds, although as shown below impacts vary greatly among sites and species. Hötter et al. (2006) in a report reviewing 127 studies on the impacts of wind farms on birds and bats, concluded that there is a tendency for wader species nesting in open landscapes to be displaced by wind farms. However, with the exception of the Northern Lapwing, the Black-tailed Godwit, and the Common Redshank, most bird species nested relatively close to wind turbines (minimal distance between the birds and the pylons rarely exceeded 100 m). In the non-breeding season, many species of open landscape avoided approaching wind parks. The distance at which the disturbance could be noted increased with the size of the wind turbine (e.g., in the case of the Northern Lapwing). Pearce-Higgins et al. (2009) examining the distribution of breeding birds around upland wind farms in the UK found that the levels of turbine avoidance suggest that breeding bird densities may be reduced by 15 to 53% within a 500-m range of the turbines. Among the species affected are the Golden Plover *Pluvialis apricaria*, the common snipe *Gallinago gallinago*, and the Eurasian Curlew *Numenius arquata*. In contrast, Douglas et al. (2011) found no effect of an operational wind farm on the abundance and distribution of upland breeding Golden Plover *Pluvialis apricaria*.

The impacts of wind farms have been insufficiently researched and contrasting results can be found across the literature, however, the potential impact of wind farms can be minimized through strategic planning to avoid areas with high densities of vulnerable species and reduce uncertainty over the magnitude of wind farm effects.

- **Major infrastructure** can significantly affect the conservation of wet grassland breeding birds in their breeding, staging, and wintering habitats. The most recent example is Portugal's plan to build a new airport over a peninsula at the heart of the Tagus estuary, a major wetland in the EAF. The Tagus estuary plays a central role in linking Eurasian breeding grounds to African wintering grounds and is visited by more than 300.000 waterbirds yearly (Alves and Dias 2020). The interconnectivity between breeding, staging, and wintering habitats of migratory birds along the flyway means that damage to major wetlands like the Tagus estuary will undoubtedly have major repercussions beyond Portugal, affecting bird conservation in Europe and jeopardizing efforts and resources spent on bird conservation in northern and western Europe, and beyond.

6 Wet-grassland Breeding Birds in Germany

Germany plays a major role in the life cycle of the 11-bird species included in this multi-species conservation plan. The lowlands of northern Germany (i.e., Atlantic biogeographic region, Figure 18) are exceptionally important breeding areas for many species and concentrate the majority of the German populations. Simultaneously, German agriculture is highly intensive, extensively mechanized, and relies heavily on pesticide and nutrient inputs.

The distribution of wet-grassland breeding birds is uneven across Germany. The majority of bird populations are in the Atlantic biogeographic ecoregion, while sporadic populations are found across the continental biogeographic region. Few exceptions exist, for example for widespread species like the Northern Lapwing.

Figure 18: Biogeographic regions of Europe. Germany fall within the Atlantic and Continental biogeographic regions. Source www.eea.europa.eu, downloaded October 2023.

We dedicated in this conservation plan three sections for the Federal States within the Atlantic biogeographic region, namely one chapter for North Rhine-Westphalia, one chapter for Lower Saxony and Bremen, and one chapter for Schleswig Holstein and Hamburg. We dedicate a fourth chapter to the Federal States in the continental biogeographic region, where we summarize the main activities and ongoing strategies and efforts.

Each section is structured in four parts: A) A description of population status and trends for the 11 species. B) A description of the main conservation practices and instruments. C) The results of the Horizon Scanning survey conducted to assess the current status and future perspectives for wet-grassland bird conservation, and D) A selection of the most relevant case studies.

6.1 Funding Opportunities

Funding programs for the implementation of nature conservation projects are available at five administrative levels: European, National, Federal State, Municipal, and Non-governmental. The available budgets, time frames, and funding program objectives can differ, and are constantly changing in line with European, and national strategies (e.g., biodiversity conservation strategies, and climate change mitigation strategies). Co-financing is often required for the majority of funding schemes, so that, for example, European funding programs can be co-financed by other programs (i.e., from other administrative levels) or own funds.

1. European Funding Opportunities

LIFE is the European Commission's main funding instrument for implementing nature conservation measures in Natura 2000 areas. LIFE funding can finance conservation measures, personnel costs, land acquisition, machinery acquisition, and infrastructure construction. Project duration can be up to 10 years. Available funds can be of several Million euro with 60 to 75 % funded by the European Commission, and 40 to 25% to be co-financed. Academic research per se is not eligible for LIFE funding.

In 2022, €380 Million were approved for 168 projects across Europe. Eight were located in Germany with a total of €20 Million contributed from the European Union.

Significantly higher funding is available through EAFRD and ERDF funds. The funding framework for EAFRD and ERDF funds is negotiated each seven years within the Member States as part of the CAP. The main objectives of these funds are primarily to support the agricultural sector and promote the development in rural areas. In the programs set up by the Federal States, many nature conservation measures can be financed in the respective funding periods (usually always designed for 7 years).

a. ERDF (European Rural Development Fund, German: EFRE)

For the funding period 2021-2027, around €800 Million are available in Lower Saxony via the ERDF funds. Part of the funding is earmarked for the priority "Greener and lower CO2 in Lower Saxony".

The funds are distributed via the state's own programs, in Lower Saxony for example

- ERDF-LaWe - Landscape values
- ERDF-KliMo - Climate protection and peatland development

b. EAFRD (European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development, German ELER)

For the period 2014 to 2022, Germany received around €9.44 Billion in European funding from the EAFRD (i.e., an average of €1,35 billion per year), which has also been increased for the last two years. On average, about 21% of EAFRD funding is spent annually on agri-environmental and climate measures in Germany (Figure 19, BMEL - EU-Förderung - Umsetzung der ELER-Förderperiode 2014 bis 2022 für ländliche Räume in Deutschland). The remaining funding is not prioritized for nature conservation. The agri-environmental and climate protection measures (Agrarumwelt- und Klimaschutzmaßnahmen) for species conservation are discussed below and their effectiveness is also addressed. These funds are

accessible to farmers who want to implement biodiversity and nature conservation friendly measures, e.g., they can be used for nest protection and predation management. Also, in some cases, EAFRD funds can provide financial support for small localized restoration measure, e.g., when measures are included in a regional development concept.

Figure 19: Use of EAFRD funding (with reallocation) and national co-financing funds (rounded) 2014 - 2020 by measure in Germany (total funds of approx. 14.1 billion Euro); Status: May 2015; source: Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture, after BMEL - EU-Förderung - Umsetzung der ELER-Förderperiode 2014 bis 2022 für ländliche Räume in Deutschland

EAFRD funding runs through specific programs in the Federal States. In Lower Saxony, the funding guideline for nature conservation is called EELA (Conservation and Development of Habitats and Species) and serves to improve biodiversity in Natura 2000 areas. Other funding programs co-financed by EAFRD apply to special species and biotope protection (SAB) and landscape conservation and site management (LaGe). In contrast to the annual direct subsidies of €4,85 billion to farmers in Germany, EAFRD funding must be co-financed with Federal State, or municipal budgets.

c. Other EU Funding Opportunities

Additional European funding opportunities that can be utilized for conducting research, monitoring, or implementing measures in Natura 2000 sites and other conservation areas are outlined below. It is important to note that these funding programs are not intended to finance major conservation measures, such as habitat optimization or Special Protection Area (SPA) management measures. However, they can serve as complementary funding sources alongside other programs, such as LIFE projects, and assist in addressing specific challenges.

- The **Interreg B program**, also known as the Interreg B transnational cooperation program. It is part of the European Union's cohesion policy and aims to promote cooperation among regions from different European countries to address common challenges and opportunities. The "B" in Interreg B stands for "transnational," indicating that these programs involve cooperation across national borders within the EU. The Interreg B supports cross-border cooperation between regions and cities that affect everyday life, including on energy and climate change, and environmental and resource protection.
- The **Horizon program**, a key funding initiative by the European Union to support research and innovation. It is designed to drive economic growth and create jobs by fostering scientific excellence and addressing societal challenges. The Horizon program has evolved over several phases, with Horizon Europe being the current framework for 2021-2027. Funding usually covers 100% of eligible expenses, however, the main focus of the program is on research and not on implementation.
- The **COST Action** is a funding instrument that supports the creation of research networks, known as COST Actions, in Europe and beyond. COST, which stands for European Cooperation in Science and Technology, is an EU-funded program that enables researchers, engineers, conservation practitioners, and scholars to collaborate on a specific topic for a period of four years. The overall goal of a COST Action is to strengthen the scientific and technological basis of Europe by promoting collaboration and knowledge sharing among stakeholders (including, researchers, NGOs, conservation practitioners, ...). This, in turn, can lead to new discoveries, innovations, and advancements in various fields.

2. German National Funding Opportunities

The National Agency for Nature Conservation (Bundesamt für Naturschutz, BfN) provides funding for nature conservation projects through five national programs.

- Large-scale nature conservation projects ("Naturschutzgroßprojekte" chance.natur) to promote particularly the conservation of valuable, characteristic, and representative habitats. The aim is the permanent conservation of natural landscapes, the protection and development of cultural landscapes with outstanding habitats, and the conservation of animal and plant species in need of special protection. Since 1979, a total of 88 projects have been funded under this program. The current available funding is around € 14 million p.a.
- National Biodiversity Program: Since 2011, this program has been used to implement the National Strategy for the Conservation of Biological Diversity. Accordingly, the funded measures are to contribute to halting the decline of biodiversity in Germany and reversing it into a positive trend in the medium to long term. Selected projects must serve the protection and sustainable use of biodiversity as well as the development of biodiversity beyond the legally required objectives.

Five funding priorities have been identified:

1. Species for which Germany has a special responsibility (responsible species; for example, the project "Sympatieträger Kiebitz" was funded under this priority)

2. Hotspots of biological diversity in Germany
 3. Ensuring ecosystem services
 4. Urban nature and biodiversity
 5. Further measures of particularly representative importance for the national biodiversity strategy
- National Species Survival Program (Nationales Artenhilfsprogramm): This program, which was adopted by the German Bundestag in 2022, will allocate around €82.4 Million until 2026. It is intended to provide long-term protection for species affected by the expansion of renewable energies, including their habitats.
 - Testing and development projects: The aim of testing and development projects (Erprobungs- und Entwicklungsvorhaben, E+E-Vorhaben) is to realize promising nature conservation ideas and to implement important research results in nature conservation practice. E+E funding enables exemplary testing and further development of new methods and procedures in nature conservation. A nationwide impetus should emanate from E+E projects. Therefore, the practical application of an innovative idea or concept is the focus of the projects. It is accompanied by scientific investigations. These serve to derive reliable recommendations for the widest possible transferability.
 - Blue Ribbon Germany (Blaues Band): This program aims at the renaturation of national waterways and their floodplains. The BfN is responsible for the supervision and management of funding projects under the "Floodplain Funding Program".

The National Agency for Nature Conservation (BfN, Bundesamt für Naturschutz) maintains a funding database (<https://www.foerderdatenbank.de>).

6.2 Prevalent Conservation Practices and Instruments

The conservation and protection of grassland breeding birds in Germany benefits from multiple strategies, instruments, and methods to protect clutches and chicks, and restore habitats necessary for the birds' life cycles. We present here a comprehensive overview of the main conservation practices and available instruments, highlighting their efficiencies and limitations when such information is available. Further, in the following sections dedicated to the Federal States, more detailed and specific information is provided. Disparities between the information provided for the different Federal States is mainly due to disparities in the availability of such information or in the implementation of wet-grassland bird conservation.

1. Natura 2000 sites, SPAs, and other Protected Areas

The EU Birds Directive (Council Directive 2009/147/EC on the conservation of wild birds) obligates Member States to ensure the legal protection of designated bird sanctuaries. This is done across Germany by designating different areas dedicated to nature conservation in four categories: 1) nature protection areas (NSG), 2) landscape protection areas (LSG), 3) national parks (NPs), and 4) biosphere reserves (BRs). A fifth category, Naturpark, is sometimes given, however, Naturpark overlap with NSGs and LSGs, and this category does not provide concrete regulations. The level of protection across these categories differs. For example, the NPs are primarily designated for the protection of biodiversity (i.e., economic exploitation should be abandoned on 75 to 100% of the park area), whereas, BRs provide relatively lower ecosystem conservation as the sustainable use of nature and natural

resources constitute a criterion for the designation of these areas. The surface area of the four categories listed above constitutes about 36% of Germany (Table 1), however, it is important to note that a large portion of conservation areas do not have any effective protection status. (Scherfose) (2016) estimates that only 64% of the 36% have some sort of strict protection status.

Table 1: Number and area of the different types of terrestrial protected areas in Germany and their proportion in relative percentage. Source: www.bfn.de, October 2023.

Category	Number	Surface area (ha)	Relative percentage	Status
Nature protection area (NSG)	8,676	1,378,410	3.9	12/2014
Landscape protection area (LSG)	8,531	10,017,634	27.9	12/2014
National parks (NP)	16	214,558	0.6	11/2015
Biosphere reserves (BR)	17	1,311,636	3.7	02/2016

When available, we provide below at the Federal State level the relative distribution of these categories of nature protections area relevant for wet-grassland bird conservation.

In a recent paper on the contribution of private land conservation to the 30X30 conservation objectives in Germany, Kopsieker and Disselhoff (2024) argue that Private Protected Areas (PPAs) can significantly complement the network of public protected areas. Together, foundations, nature conservation associations, conservation-minded private landowners, and churches own more than 1M ha of land that can be used for conservation. While they conclude that PPAs are unlikely to receive legal recognition under the current German laws due to various legal hurdles, they consider that PPAs can still make an important contribution to Germany's 30X30 pledge (aim to protect 30% of its land and sea by 2030), and can be recorded in the World Database on Protected Areas by non-governmental entities.

2. Management Plans for Protected Areas

Management plans (MPs) are essential instruments for grassland-breeding bird conservation and habitat improvement. Both Habitats (Council Directive 92/43/EEC) and Birds Directives (Directive 79/409/EEC) encourage Member States to set MPs for protected areas. Article 6 of the Habitats Directive requires that for Special Areas of Conservation, Member States shall establish the necessary conservation measures involving if need be, appropriate management plans (or similar instruments) specifically designed for the sites or integrated into other development plans. The Birds Directive does not explicitly mention the need to prepare MPs for SPAs, but Article 4 of the Birds Directive requires the Member States that species mentioned in Annex I shall be the subject of special conservation measures concerning their habitat in order to ensure their survival and reproduction in their area of distribution.

In 1996, the EU formulated recommendations on the necessary content of a good MP:

- A policy statement with reference to Article 6 of the Habitats Directive
- A site description including an analysis of previous land use patterns
- Recording and evaluation of the current status of the protected assets
- Definition of the conservation objectives to be achieved in the short and long term
- Description of the obstacles and actors that stand in the way of these objectives
- Compilation of realistically implementable measures for the conservation and development of the area and the protected assets
- Time and cost plan including possible financing instruments
- Proposals for monitoring effects and success
- A concept for the information and participation of the public

The necessary conservation or restoration measures specified in the MPs must be geared towards the protection and conservation of species and habitats. The main objective must always be to achieve a favorable conservation status for these habitat types and species at the biogeographical level. The implementation of measures and their impact must be reported to the EU every 6 years as part of the reporting and monitoring process.

The development of MPs and the update of existing ones is heterogeneous across Germany. The existence of such plans for conservation areas relevant to grassland birds depend on the availability of financial and human resources. The majority of MPs are developed in the framework of LIFE funded projects.

3. The European Common Agricultural Policy

The intensification of agriculture in the main driver of the decline of wet-grassland breeding bird populations across Germany. The European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), thus, significantly determines the development of German agriculture and the direct decline of many bird populations in agricultural land.

The new funding period (2023-2027) of the CAP proposes a new architecture around three environmental instruments, two of them funded under Pillar I: enhanced conditionality and the new eco-schemes, and the Agri-Environment-Climate-Measures (AECMs) funded under Pillar II (see following sections). Similar to AECMs, eco-schemes are voluntary for farmers, but Member States (MS) have much more freedom in their design (Pe'er et al. 2022). MS are required to invest at least 20% of Pillar I payments in eco-schemes in 2023-2024 and this percentage should increase to at least 25% after 2025. The minimum share of AECMs payments should also be increased from the last funding period to 35% after 2023.

Germany's strategy is aimed at ensuring the sustainable competitiveness and resilience of farms and, at the same time, at improving the protection of natural resources and the climate. It also aims to boost the quality of life in rural areas through investments, knowledge transfer, and innovation. Germany has designed a strategy that combines national and regional elements. This will provide support to farmers across the country with a fair approach while considering the specificities of the Federal States. Legislative or financial tools at the national and/or regional level, which complement the actions of the CAP plan, have also been accounted for to facilitate the implementation of the strategy. Around 30,74 billion Euros of EU-fund are earmarked for Germany's CAP-Strategy for the period 2023-2027. Those can be divided into 22,2 billion Euros as direct payments, 8,23 billion Euros for

rural development, and 310 million Euros for sectorial support. In addition to EU funding, National funding of 3,7 billion Euros is earmarked for the CAP strategy.

In order to receive the basic premium support from the CAP (i.e., direct payments to farmers), all farmers have to respect the statutory management requirements (SMR) that include EU rules on public, animal, and planet health, on animal welfare, and on the environment. In addition to the statutory management requirements, farmers receiving CAP support have to respect EU standards on good agricultural and environmental condition of land (GAEC). These standards are designed to: 1) Prevent soil erosion by defining minimum soil cover and minimum land management practices; 2) Maintain soil organic matter and soil structure; 3) Maintain permanent grassland; 4) Protect biodiversity and ensure the retention of landscape features through, for example, a ban on cutting hedges and trees during the bird breeding and rearing season; And 5) protect and manage water through the establishment of buffer strips along water courses, authorization on water for irrigation and protection of ground water from pollution. Detailed information can be found directly on the commission's website: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/income-support/cross-compliance_en#gaec

The basic premium support from the CAP is reduced from 171€/ha in 2021 to around 155€/ha in 2023 and 2024.

Eco-schemes are set to play an important role in the European Union's CAP post-2022 for the delivery of environmental and climate benefits and enhanced animal welfare. In Germany, seven eco-schemes are identified. Those, in addition to what is commonly known as the redistribution premium are targeting the support for small and medium-sized farms in particular. Further, farmers under the age of 40 will receive financial support for up to 5 years when they establish their own farm.

Starting in 2023, seven voluntary nationwide individual eco-schemes (**Eco-scheme 1 to 7**) are offered in the first pillar of the CAP. These are not to be confused with the AECM funded under the 2nd pillar.

Eco-scheme 1: Provision of land to improve biodiversity and preserve habitats.

Increase in non-productive areas, in addition to the 4% (compliance to receive basic premium CAP funding):

1%: 1300 €/ha, i.e., 4% to 5%

2%: 500 €/ha, i.e. from 5% to 6%, there is a premium of 500 €/ha

3 to 6%: 300 €/ha, i.e. for the other higher three percent of 7 to 10%, an additional premium of 300 €/ha.

Additional flower strips on eco-scheme 1 areas: 150 €/ha

Flower strips in permanent crops: 150 €/ha

Maintain old grass strips/areas of permanent grassland (max. 6% of permanent grassland):

1%: 900 €/ha

2 to 3%: 400 €/ha

4 to 6%: 200€/ha

Eco-scheme 2: Cultivation of diverse crops: Cultivation of at least five main crops in arable farming, each covering 10 to 30% of the arable land. This include having a least 10% of legumes and a maximum of 66% cereals.

Premium: 45 €/ha

Eco-scheme 3: Maintain an agroforestry management method on arable land and permanent grassland. Two to 35% wooded area, at least 2 wooded strips (3 to 25 meters wide) distant of a minimum of 20 m and a maximum of 100m.

Premium: 60 €/ha

Eco-scheme 4: Extensification of the entire permanent grassland of the farm.

Premium: Year 2023: 115 €/ha, from 2024: 100 €/ha

Eco-scheme 5: Result-oriented extensive management of permanent grassland areas with beneficial evidence of at least four regionally characteristic (key) species.

Premium: Years 2023, 2024: 240 €/ha, year 2025: 225 €/ha, year 2026: 210 €/ha

Eco-scheme 6: Cultivation of arable or permanent crop areas on the farm without using chemical-synthetic pesticides in certain periods, which differ according to crop type.

Premium: Year 2023: 130 €/ha, from 2025: up to €110/ha for summer cereals, field beans and maize, and 50 €/ha for green fodder.

Eco-scheme 7: Application of farming methods determined by conservation goals on agricultural land in Natura 2000 areas.

Premium: 40 €/ha

4. Agri-Environment-Climate Measures

The European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) funding instruments are essential for achieving the European environmental objectives in biodiversity and sustainability. These instruments aim to preserve and increase biological diversity in agricultural land. In practice, farmers are compensated financially through these instruments when they take active action for the conservation of biodiversity, and more specifically in this case, for the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds.

The Agri-Environment-Climate Measures (AECMs) are funded under Pillar II of the CAP. AECMs are tools designed at the national or regional level to achieve specific agri-environmental objectives. Although these are mandatory for national and regional administrations, they are voluntary for farmers. Usually, farmers using AECMs receive an annual fee per hectare, in exchange for the commitment either to undertake management practices considered to be environmentally friendly or to waive the use of production techniques considered harmful to the environment (Armsworth et al. 2012). AECM payments

can cover only those commitments going beyond the mandatory standards established for conventional production (funded under the so-called Pillar I).

Around 30,74 billion Euros of EU-fund are earmarked for Germany's CAP-Strategy for the period 2023-2027. Those can be divided into 22,2 billion Euros as direct payments, 8,23 billion Euros for rural development, and 310 million Euros for sectorial support. In addition to EU funding, National funding of 3,7 billion Euros is earmarked for the CAP strategy. The minimum share of AECM payments in Pillar II should be 35% for the funding period 2023-2027.

5. Social and Political Initiatives

Grassroots social and political initiatives for the conservation of nature are common in Germany. Those are often targeting wider conservation or climatic pressing issues and benefit directly or indirectly wet-grassland bird conservation.

Such initiatives can benefit bird conservation on multiple levels. Among those, raising the profile of conservation case studies, mobilizing financial and institutional resources for habitat restoration, and adopting bird conservation on higher-scale agendas, e.g., national and European levels. We include in the sections dedicated to Federal States the most significant initiatives and discuss briefly their impacts.

6. LIFE-funded Projects: Development and Implementation

The LIFE program (LIFE for L'Instrument Financier pour l'Environnement) is the European Union's funding instrument for the environment and climate action. The general objective of LIFE is to contribute to the implementation, updating and development of EU environmental and climate policy and legislation by co-financing projects with European added value. LIFE began in 1992 and to date there have been six phases of the program (LIFE I: 1992–1995, LIFE II: 1996–1999, LIFE III: 2000–2006, LIFE+: 2007–2013, LIFE 2014–2020, LIFE 2021-2027). During this period, LIFE has co-financed some 4600 projects across the EU, with a total contribution of approximately 6.5 billion Euros to the protection of the environment and of climate.

For the next phase of the program (2021–2027) the European Commission proposed to raise the budget to 5.45 billion Euro to fund 4 sub-programs: Nature and biodiversity, circular economy and quality of life, climate change mitigation and adaptation, clean energy transition.

As of 2023, the LIFE Program has funded 422 projects in Germany (Table 2), over 317 coordinating beneficiaries, with total project costs of €1,193 m, of which the EU contributed €524 m (CINEA review report February 2023; www.cinea.ec.europa.eu).

Table 2: Overview of the number of LIFE projects funded in Germany since 1992, the total investment, and the EU contribution. The projects are clustered by sub-programs.

	Number of projects	Total investment	EU contribution € Million (%)
Nature & biodiversity	152	485.5	275 (56.6%)
Circular economy & quality of life	216	614.5	201 (32.7%)
Climate change mitigation & adaptation	16	57	31 (54.4%)
Clean energy transition	5	4	3.8 (95%)
Other: NGOs, preparatory, technical assistance projects	33	32	13.5 (42.2%)

7. Clutch-and-chick Protection

The clutch-and-chick protection (Gelege und Kükenschutz) are an instrument aiming to protect grassland breeding birds during their nesting period. It is often recommended in agricultural landscapes in areas having a relatively high proportion of private agricultural parcels and in intensively used arable land. The instrument consists of identifying the location of birds' nests so they can be marked, made visible, and avoided by agricultural machinery to limit the physical destruction of nests, chicks, and incubating adults. This instrument is based on the voluntary cooperation between farmers and conservation practitioners to protect the clutches and chicks of meadow birds. Usually, clutches are marked with bamboo sticks so that during subsequent agricultural activities the clutches can be avoided (usually a few square meters are spared per clutch). In grazed areas, protective grazing baskets are used to prevent the clutches from being trampled by cattle.

The instrument is widespread across Germany, and is primarily used for species with a wide distribution across large agricultural areas where instruments like fencing are costly and not applicable.

8. Predation Management

There is no uniform strategy for predation management in wet-grassland breeding bird sanctuaries, SPAs, and other conservation areas across Germany. Large-scale coordinated approaches exist only in a few focal areas such as the SPA Dümmer, in Lower Saxony, or the islands of Borkum, Langeoog, and Norderney (historically predator-free islands), part of the Wadden Sea National Park.

Predation management is applied to different extents and in different ways across conservation areas. It usually consists of a mix of habitat management measures, measures to keep predators away of breeding areas, and measure to reducing the populations of mammalian predators.

We can categorize predation management into three main categories:

1. **Active predation management through the removal (lethal or non-lethal) of predators:** Hunting is carried out using various methods including trapping and the physical removal or elimination of predators. Such methods target primarily native and introduced mammalian species, including the red fox, beech marten, badger, pine marten, polecat, stoat, raccoon, and raccoon dog, and can be applied to limit eggs and chick predation during the breeding period. These practices are often applied in large conservation areas, and hunting is usually carried out in cooperation with local hunters. Professional hunters are employed only in a few existing large-scale projects or usually have an advisory role.
2. **Passive predator control using exclosures** (i.e., protection fences to deter predators): Exclosures are often used as immediate protection measures, deployed in breeding sites in areas with small remnant populations of birds to protect them from ground predators. Exclosures can involve the fencing of individual nests as well as larger breeding areas for single or multiple species.
3. **Habitat optimization and management** can be used to limit or reduce predation pressures in breeding habitats: Habitat optimization allows the reduction of predator densities to moderate levels so that natural predator avoidance strategies of the meadow breeders can take effect. Unfortunately, habitat optimization to reduce predation pressures has so far only been achieved in a few areas. For the most part, the measures are limited to the removal of structural elements from the landscape, such as trees or old buildings that can provide cover, or shelter for predators.

The creation and maintenance of suitable bird habitats is a basic requirement for the preservation and resettlement of breeding bird populations. Extensive wet habitats with few trees offer predatory mammals few opportunities to establish significant populations. Wet grasslands have generally few hiding places, and provide predators with relatively few preys that are available year-round. However, since habitat optimization in agricultural landscapes can only be carried out at a small scale, the establishment of a sustainable well-functioning ecosystem where predator populations are naturally low is practically impossible. The edge effects are often too high and have significant effects on the density of predators within SPAs and conservation areas.

9. Monitoring

Wet-grassland breeding bird populations are monitored across Germany in SPAs and outside. However, this monitoring is carried out by the Federal States where disparities exist in financial, institutional, and human capacities. The Federal States communicate their counts data to the Umbrella Association of German Avifaunists (DDA, www.dda-web.de), a non-profit association of all national and regional ornithological associations in the Federal Republic of Germany. The DDA plays a significant role in centralizing the data of bird counts and for the creation of the Red Lists of breeding birds in Germany. The association also plays a leading role in the creation of the Atlas of German Breeding Bird Species.

Bird population monitoring within SPAs

The monitoring of bird populations in SPAs across Germany is a government task (LAG VSW et al. 2011), required to be carried out every six years and accounting primarily for the so-called trigger species (i.e., species listed in Annex I of the EU Birds Directive, and regularly occurring migratory species requiring special conservation measures). State authorities have, therefore, a particular responsibility to ensure that sufficient financial resources are available to ensure that both inventory and trends of bird populations in SPAs are effectively carried out. In practice, the Federal States have created state-specific organizational structures (or are striving to set up such structures) for the management of SPAs and bird population inventories. A recent evaluation of the monitoring efforts of breeding bird populations in SPAs across Germany (Busch et al. 2022) showed that data availability on bird populations in German SPAs is overall still not satisfying. However, major disparities exist between Federal States and some states have more financial and institutional capacities to carry out bird population monitoring. Busch et al. (2022) continue by saying that “the recent developments of the national bird monitoring schemes offer a good chance to address the current monitoring deficits: the German Rare Breeding Bird Survey (GRBBS) is currently restructured, to gain the capacity to considerably contribute to the bird monitoring inside SPAs.”

Bird population monitoring outside SPAs

Targeted monitoring of wet-grassland breeding bird populations outside of the SPAs is conducted sporadically across Germany. When done, it relies heavily on dataset and projects conducted by consultancy agencies, academic institutions, NGOs, or to a lesser extent state-funded programs for rural development. This usually helps narrowing down areas for inspection and monitoring, where further inspections can be conducted.

10. Public Land Management via Contracts

Publicly owned land in grassland SPAs can serve as a model for nature conservation. Unlike land in private ownership, economic revenues on public land play a secondary role and substantial conservation measures (e.g., rewetting, water table optimization) can be implemented for long-term conservation strategies. Land ownership has already played a decisive role in the conservation and recovery of bird populations in some large SPAs e.g., in Lower Saxony. In contrast, conservation measures on private land in SPAs have to go through ordinances and voluntary contractual measures, both deemed unstable and insufficient, providing limited results.

11. Species specific action plans

Species-specific action plans exist for some Federal States (Ländern). Such action plans often target umbrella species like the Black-tailed Godwit, the Curlew, and the Northern Lapwing, or species with high conservation value like the Whinchat.

Such species-specific action plans are often linked to specific projects or are developed by research institutes like the Michael-Otto-Institut im NABU, or MOIN, that issued a certain number of species-specific research reports and action plans for the Black-tailed Godwit, the Curlew, the Northern Lapwing, the Whinchat, and the Oystercatcher in Schleswig Holstein. Species-specific action plans will be addressed in the chapters dedicated to their corresponding Federal States.

7 The Case of Lower Saxony and Bremen

7.1 Populations and Trends

We present here the most recent population status and trends of the 11 species (Table 3). The data is derived from the latest Red List of Birds published by Krüger and Sandkühler (2022) for Lower Saxony and Bremen, and Ryslavý et al. (2020) for Germany. For Europe, data was derived from the European Red List of Birds 2021 compiled by BirdLife International (2021). The European Red List is based on 4 international assessments carried out in 1994, 2004, 2015, and 2021.

Table 3: Table showing the populations of the 11 species considered in this conservation plan, in addition to population trends in Lower Saxony and Bremen (1996-2020), Germany (DE), and across Europe (Eur). The code color associated with the arrows indicates the gravity of population decrease: red and three downward arrows (↓↓↓) indicate a decrease of more than 50%, the yellow and two downward arrows (↓↓) indicate a decrease of more than 20%, light blue and equal sign (=) indicates a stable or slightly fluctuating population (decrease ≤ 20% or increase < 25%) over the period 1996-2020. Categories of the European Red List (Eur) are Least Concern (LC), Vulnerable (VU), and Near Threatened (NT).

Species	Population (breeding pairs)			Trends		
	1996	2014	2020	1996–2020	DE	Eur
Corncrake <i>Crex crex</i>	442	270	124	↓↓↓ -72%	↓↓	LC
Eurasian Oystercatcher <i>Haematopus ostralegus</i>	13,000	8,500	7,500	↓↓ -42%	↓↓	VU
Northern Lapwing <i>Vanellus vanellus</i>	27,000	22,000	20,000	↓↓ -26%	↓↓↓	VU
European Golden Plover <i>Pluvialis apricaria</i>	19	2	0	↓↓↓ -100%	=	LC
Eurasian Curlew <i>Numenius arquata</i>	2,000	2,000	1,200	↓↓ -40%	↓↓	NT
Black-tailed Godwit <i>Limosa limosa</i>	5,000	2,000	1,700	↓↓↓ -66%	↓↓↓	NT
Ruff <i>Philomachus pugnax</i>	20	2	1	↓↓↓ -95%	↓↓↓	NT

Species	Population (breeding pairs)			Trends			
syn. <i>Calidris pugnax</i>							
Dunlin <i>Calidris alpina</i>	0	0-1	1-2	–	–	=	LC
Common Snipe <i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	5,000	1,300	1,100	↓↓↓	-78%	↓↓↓	VU
Common Redshank <i>Tringa totanus</i>	7,000	5,000	5,000	↓↓	-29%	=	VU
Whinchat <i>Saxicola rubetra</i>	6,400	2,000	1,100	↓↓↓	-83%	↓↓↓	LC

7.2 Prevalent Conservation Practices and Instruments

The conservation and protection of wet-grassland breeding birds in Lower Saxony benefits from multiple strategies, instruments, and methods that aim at protecting primarily the breeding populations of these species, and restore habitats necessary for their life cycle development. Some instruments are common across Germany, and differ only by the mechanisms of their implementation. We present here a comprehensive overview of these instruments and methods, highlighting their efficiencies and limitations when such information is available.

1. Natura 2000 sites, SPAs, and other protected areas

In Bremen, large parts of the wet grasslands have been registered as protected areas. In total, there are nine SPAs (7,875 ha) and 15 Special Area of Conservation (SAC; 5,048 ha), which largely overlap (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Conservation areas in Bremen. Green areas are landscape protection areas (LSG), red areas are nature protection areas (NSG). Black stripes represent the areas that are designated as SPAs and the red stripes areas that are designated as SACs. Map obtained from <https://umwelt.bremen.de/umwelt/natur/vogelschutzgebiete-24122> (August 2024).

Conservation areas in Lower Saxony are designated under four categories: 1) nature protection areas (NSG), 2) landscape protection areas (LSG), 3) national parks (NP), and 4) UNESCO biosphere reserves (BR). Approximately 94% of the area of SPAs relevant to wet-grassland birds in Lower Saxony (Figure 21) are currently under legal protection, with 100% expected by the end of 2024.

A different picture emerges when looking in detail at the level (or type) of protection for the 118,000 ha of grasslands within those SPAs. As stated above, around six percent of the 118,000 ha are still without any legal protection. Of the remainder 94%, about a quarter is arable land and thus at best an auxiliary breeding habitat for grassland breeding birds. There are virtually no specific recommendations in the protected area ordinances aimed at protecting ground-nesting birds in arable land. Of the remaining 78,000 ha of protected grassland, about 47% are protected as LSG and just under a third as NSG. The Wadden Sea National Park accounts for an additional 5% and the Lower Saxony Elbe Floodplain Biosphere Reserve accounts for another 15%.

Only 18,000 ha (22%) of the protected grassland is subject to specific farming restrictions favorable for wet-grassland breeding bird protection. Of those, 1,400 ha are under strict regulation, and 16,600 ha are under partial management restriction. Most restrictions are in the form of a spring dormancy period until the 5th or 15th of June, and restrictions on the densities of grazing animals or the use of fertilizers and pesticides.

Slightly different protection measures are applied for grassland-breeding songbirds (Passerine), such as the Whinchat *Saxicola rubetra*. For example, fallow land and old grassland or vegetation strips are mown late (starting from mid-July) and sometimes only every second year. In SPAs with high importance to wet-grassland breeding birds, protected area ordinances generally promote these vegetation structures in the form of marginal structures, along watercourses, and path margins, which are difficult to quantify in terms of surface area. However, the conservation of an estimated 370 ha of such vegetation structures is guaranteed by protected area regulations, and a further 5,100 ha of grassland is under regulations for the conservation of edge and fringe structures. For the Corncrake *Crex crex*, whose selective and very dynamic distribution is mostly within the focal conservation areas of the waders, and which requires very late mowing dates (starting from mid-August) due to the late start of breeding, there are a few sporadic regulations, mostly linked to the occurrence of calling males.

In summary, most of the grassland in SPAs relevant for wet-grassland breeding birds is protected by public authorities, but less than a quarter of this area has specific and effective management restrictions specifically tailored for the protection of wet-grassland breeding birds.

**Important Natura 2000 sites
for meadow birds and
their legal protection status
in Lower Saxony**

Staatliche Vogelschutzwarte (NLWKN)
June 2023
Scale 1:1.200.000 DIN A4

Figure 21: Map of Natura 2000 sites important for wet-grassland bird conservation in Lower Saxony. Sites are categorized by their legal protection status, including National Park, UNESCO Biosphere Reserve (BR), Nature Protection Area (NSG), and Landscape Protection Area (LSG). Few sites are still (as of 2023) under no legal protection, those are marked in pink.

2. Management Plans for Protected Areas

MPs are currently being developed for all SPAs in Lower Saxony where important populations of wet-grassland breeding birds occur. Please refer to Figure 2 which shows the area codes used below in the text.

The development of MPs has been primarily supported in Lower Saxony by LIFE-funded projects. As of August 2022, complete or partial MPs have been developed for 7 important bird protection areas (SPAs, EU-VSG). Thus, MPs have been developed for the conservation areas in the Wadden Sea National Park, in parts for **V66** (Niederungen der Süd- und Mittelradde und der Marka) of 975 ha (22% of the total area) and **V10** (Emsmarsch von Leer bis Emden) of 1857 ha (46% of the total area). For the three other SPAs **V07** (Fehntjer Tief), **V09** (Ostfriesische Meere), and **V39** (Dümmer), the MP final drafts are available and are expected to be soon finalized and approved. For the SPA **V18** (Lower Elbe), the "Integration Management Plan for the Elbe Estuary" has been available since 2010. It describes the necessary actions and objectives for the entire SPA area. An action plan is currently being prepared as part of the MPs of the districts of Stade and Cuxhaven. For the Elbe estuary area of 2.722 ha, the NLWKN "Management Plan for the Elbe estuary between Cuxhaven and Freiburg" is available. The MP for **V04** (Krummhörn) is currently in progress. For another six SPAs (**V06** Rheiderland, **V11** Hunteniederung, part of **V10** Emsmarsch von Leer bis Emden, **V64** Marschen am Jadebusen, **V65** Butjadingen, and part of **V66** Niederungen der Süd- und Mittelradde und der Marka) funding has been approved and the responsible counties are currently conducting the tendering processes. The completion of all MPs is scheduled for the end of 2025.

Ongoing projects (e.g., LIFE IP GrassBirdHabitats, LIFE19 IPE/DE/000004) are providing additional financial resources and capacities to develop MPs for an additional 14 SPAs, thus with the objective to have updated MPs with concrete action plans for all SPAs in Lower Saxony.

3. The European Common Agricultural Policy

According to the German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL), more than half of the existing European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) funds are to be spent on the topics of biodiversity, environment, and climate in the future, and this should be reflected in Lower Saxony and Bremen.

The new funding for "Conservation and Development of Biological Diversity (Erhalt und Entwicklung der Biologischen Vielfalt, BioIV)" combines several previous funding for nature conservation: The Special Species and Biotope Conservation (SAB), the "Conservation and Development of Habitats and Species in Rural Landscapes (EELA)", and the NLWKN's "KliMo" program. The aim of BioIV is to fund projects for the conservation, development, and restoration of biodiversity, habitats, and landscapes, and for the improvement of ecosystem services. Table 4 provides a quick overview of budget lines in relation to BioIV for the Federal States of Lower Saxony, Bremen, and Hamburg. A full report can be downloaded here: <https://klara.niedersachsen.de>. Budget lines EL-0105 AECM Biodiversity and EL-0408 Biodiversity (Investment for nature conservation) can have direct implications for the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds.

The implementation of the European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) in Lower Saxony, Bremen, and Hamburg is carried out by the regional monitoring committee BGA KLARA (Regionaler Begleitausschuss für Klima, Landwirtschaft, Artenvielfalt, Regionale AkteurlInnen) for the period 2023-2027. This regional monitoring committee is a central forum for participation and dialogue that reviews the progress and the implementation of the EAFRD funding and discusses regional aspects of the CAP strategic plan. The BGA KLARA sees itself as a committee in which a wide range of economic, social, and environmental stakeholders, representatives of state administrations and other authorities as well as other relevant institutions work together actively and constructively to promote development in rural areas.

Table 4: Funding plan of KLARA for Lower Saxony (NI), Bremen (HB), and Hamburg (HH) for the period 2023-2027. *A comparable intervention to “summer grazing (EL-0109)” will be funded outside the EAFRD framework. ** A comparable intervention to the “coastal protection (EL-0402)” will be funded outside the EAFRD framework. * The technical assistance funds can also be used in Bremen and Hamburg. EL-0105 and EL-0408 (highlighted in green) can have direct implications for the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds.**

	EAFRD interventions	EAFRD fund in € Million		
		NI	HB	HH
Article 70	Environmental, climate and other management obligations (area- and animal-related measures)	574.77	5.37*	4.79
<i>EL-0105</i>	<i>AECM biodiversity</i>	<i>261.56</i>	<i>2.37</i>	<i>0.73</i>
Article 73	Investments	302.3**	5.89	17.93
<i>EL-0408</i>	<i>Biodiversity (investment for nature conservation)</i>	<i>44.52</i>	<i>2.00</i>	<i>0.00</i>
Article 76	Risk management instruments	15	0.11	0.40
Article 77	Cooperation	184.81	0.54	1.16
Article 78	Knowledge exchange and dissemination of information	33.51	0.02	0.39
Article 125	Technical assistance	47.79	***	***
Total		1,158.17	11.93	24.69

4. Agri-Environment-Climate Measures

In priority areas for grassland breeding bird conservation, multiple Agri-Environment-Climate Measures (AECMs, or AUKM in German) are being offered. Accordingly, the creation of “farmland bird islands” (i.e., restricted areas where birds can breed undisturbed) on arable land by temporarily taking out of agricultural use small areas where breeding birds occur till the 15th of August. This AECM is implemented in a rotating variant using fallow or sowing of legumes (**AN8**), and a variant using fallow in priority areas of meadow bird protection as the **AN9**, or so-called, Lapwing islands. For the latter, open soil is to be created by plowing in autumn, to offer suitable breeding conditions, especially for the Lapwing in the following spring. Lapwing islands have already been tested in other Federal States and are now

available for the first time in Lower Saxony. Their effectiveness was examined primarily as part of the “Sympathieträger Kiebitz” project in the Federal Biological Diversity Program. The results show that the breeding success of Lapwings can be increased through this measure. Further, Lapwing islands were particularly effective in summer and when other environmental conditions (wet spots, no isolated individual occurrences, sufficient distance from vertical structures) were also met (Cimiotti et al. 2022). In this regard, the success of **AN9** will depend on small-scale steering and management. Another AECM that can benefit the preservation of wet-grassland breeding birds is **AN3** which promotes the permanent conversion of arable fields into grasslands. **AN3** can only be applied on moorland and constitutes a 7-year commitment with a total ban on the use of pesticides and a subsequent ban on reconversion. Further, **BK1**, or “moor-friendly damming on permanent grassland” is a new AECM, that is not explicitly aimed at wet-grassland bird conservation, but as it supports increased water-level maintenance until the end of April, can also promote wet-grassland breeding bird conservation on low/raised moor grassland.

In grassland, similar to the previous measure **GL2**, a two-part measure **GN1** and **GN2** (statewide basic variant **GN1** and more far-reaching variant **GN2** in priority areas of meadow bird protection) is offered with spring dormancy as well as a ban on turning/loosening tillage and melioration measures. The periods of spring dormancy continue to be from the 21st of March to the 5th of June (**GN1**) and from the 15th of March to the 15th of June (**GN2**), respectively, during which no mechanical land cultivation/use is allowed and the permissible grazing livestock density is limited (**GN1**: 3 animals/2 GVH per ha; **GN2**: 2 animals/2 GHV per ha). What is new for the new funding period is a year-round ban on the use of synthetic chemical pesticides and fertilizers as well as a halving of the application of organic fertilizers. Further, only 10% of the protected area may be mown starting the 1st of August. The subsidy rates almost tripled in comparison to the last funding period. In addition, supplementary measures are possible, such as an extended rest period, the use of a knife bar (i.e., cutting bar) without conditioner, water retention, or additional maintenance cut in autumn. Overall, **GN2** has relatively a high potential to support grassland-breeding bird conservation and the significantly higher funding rates make this measure more attractive than its predecessor **GL22**.

The **GN4** and **NG GL** are the successor measures to **GL4** and **NG4**, respectively, and are similar. **GN4** offers additional compensation for “hardship management conditions”. Only permanent grasslands that are located in areas with corresponding protected area regulations are eligible for funding. **NG GL** provides financial provision to maintain low-disturbance in resting and feeding areas for migratory and wintering Nordic birds as well as the maintenance (or extensification) of the use of permanent grassland in meadow bird priority areas.

5. Social and Political Initiatives

“Der Niedersächsische Weg”, which translates into “The Lower Saxony Path”, is a remarkable political success where both nature conservation and agriculture are put to contribution to develop and implement state-wide sustainable management of biodiversity and natural resources in Lower Saxony that profit nature and provide the necessary compensations to agricultural losses when occurring (Figure 22). Der Niedersächsischer Weg sets the framework for significantly improving nature, species, and water protection,

including a comprehensive package of concrete measures and provision of funding. This cooperative approach is, therefore, intended to ensure that the interests of all stakeholders involved at different levels are considered and that appropriate measures are accompanied by adequate compensation for economic losses by land users. Partners of the Der Niedersächsische Weg (politicians, nature conservationists and farmers) agreed on elaborating a state-wide ambitious meadow bird conservation program that goes beyond the current status quo. It should include additional funding opportunities and enforceable mandatory measures to allow Lower Saxony to achieve its nature conservation targets.

Figure 22: Cartoon drawing showing the multidimensionality of Der Niedersächsische Weg initiative. Figure taken from www.niedersachsen.de/niedersaechsischer-weg, June 2023.

6. LIFE-funded Projects: Development and Implementation

Lower Saxony has extensively used this instrument to advance the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds. LIFE-supported projects (Table 5) enabled the implementation of major conservation measures. Among those, are habitat improvement measures, infrastructure development, heavy equipment purchases, and the implementation of predation management programs. LIFE funding also supported institutional development and land purchase into the public domain to conduct durable long-term conservation measures.

The application process for LIFE funding is relatively time-consuming, costly, and complex with uncertain success. To address these challenges, the Federal State of Lower Saxony has established a routine for submitting LIFE proposal applications. This routine relies on close cooperation between the Lower Saxony Ministry of the Environment (Niedersächsisches Ministerium für Umwelt, Energie und Klimaschutz), the Lower Saxony Water Management, Coastal Protection and Nature Conservation Agency (NLWKN, Niedersächsischer Landesbetrieb für Wasserwirtschaft, Küsten- und Naturschutz) and the

National Park Wattenmeer (Nationalpark Niedersächsisches Wattenmeer). A milestone for wet-grassland breeding bird conservation was the acquisition in 2020 of a LIFE Integrated Project (LIFE IP) dedicated to wet-grassland breeding bird conservation and for a duration of 10 years.

Indeed, LIFE IPs help develop mechanisms for long-term regional, national, or international strategies. LIFE IPs are exceptional opportunities to mobilize substantial human capacities and support the acquisition of considerable complementary funds for nature conservation. Consecutively, the development of new project applications is financed via the superordinate LIFE IPs.

Table 5: LIFE funded projects since 2000 that directly supported the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds in Lower Saxony and Bremen.

Project reference	Title	Time frame	Budget (€)
LIFE00NAT/D/7043	Wiedervernässung des Hohen Moores	01.04.2001 – 31.03.2006	645,000
LIFE02NAT/D/8456	Wiedervernässung der Westlichen Dümmerniederung	01.06.2002 – 30.04.2007	1,535,000
LIFE05NAT/D/000051	Große Pflanzenfresser zur Pflege und Erhaltung von Küstenheiden	01.10.2005 – 30.09.2009	464,498
LIFE10NAT/DE/011	Grünland-Extensivierung und Wiedervernässung für Wachtelkönig und Uferschnepfe in Niedersachsen	01.11.2011 – 31.12.2025	22,796,608
LIFE19IPE/DE/000004	Conservation of wet grassland breeding bird habitats in the Atlantic region	01.11.2020 – 31.10.2030	27,061,079
LIFE22NAT/DE/101113618	Conservation of the Black-tailed Godwit along the flyway	01.07.2023 – 31.10.2030	15,848,352
Total			68,350,537

7. Clutch-and-chick Protection

This instrument has been applied in Lower Saxony and Bremen since 2011 in the framework of European agricultural funding instruments, and other accompanying funding schemes. An evaluation of the efficiency of this instrument for the period of 2011-2018 was recently carried out using two parameters 1) population development and 2) reproductive output. The evaluation included 26 areas covering an approximate study area of 30,000 ha, where this instrument was applied. It accounted for the population development and breeding success of five grassland breeding bird species, the Northern Lapwing, Black-tailed Godwit, Eurasian Curlew, Redshank, and Eurasian Oystercatcher. The efficiency of the instrument as applied between 2011 and 2018 was partial, primarily due to the relatively small protection area established around each nest, which indeed, protects nests from direct physical destruction but does not necessarily guarantee the long-term survival of the chicks.

The clutch-and-chick protection has, therefore, undergone a thorough revision and realignment resulting in a new concept. This new concept replaces the small-scale protection of single clutches on a few square meters with more extensive measures that should improve chick survival by providing an additional area for foraging. However, small-scale measures, i.e., the old concept, can still be exceptionally used in some cases. Further, a new funding scheme was developed for financing the measures and compensating for farmer's income loss. The implementation of the new concept will start in 2024/2025 only in Lower Saxony. Bremen is expected to continue the implementation of the older concept, for now.

It is important to underline that the clutch-and-chick protection instrument has been shown to provide limited results (Plard et al. 2020) and cannot be recommended as a main instrument for breeding bird conservation, but rather as a complementary instrument when more holistic conservation efforts are being carried out. It has so far been effective in very few cases and has the potential to provide significant results locally, during the roosting phase, however, its long-term efficiency cannot be dissociated from more holistic conservation efforts where habitats of sufficient quality are needed for chicks to feed and find shelter, and where predation rates need to be controlled.

8. Predation Management

There is no uniform strategy for predation management in wet-grassland breeding bird SPAs in Lower Saxony. Large-scale coordinated approaches exist only in a few focal areas such as the SPAs Dümmer, Untereibe, Rheiderland, and the Strohauser Plate. There are also a few additional localized predation management measures, for example, in the Wadden Sea National Park where the population of hedgehogs and ferrets on the islands of Borkum, Langeoog, and Norderney were successfully reduced (see, case study VII. C). In the Elbtalaue Biosphere Reserve, the first project for predation management was initiated in 2022. Additionally, in a few areas where clutch and chick protection measures are currently being implemented, accompanying predation management activities are being carried out on a voluntary basis.

Predation management usually consists of different measures, we describe below the main strategies and their demonstrated accomplishments:

Active predation management through the removal (lethal or non-lethal) of predators is the most widespread measure for predation management in Lower Saxony. Hunting is carried out using various methods including trapping and the physical removal or elimination of predators. Native and introduced mammalian species are targeted by this measure including the Red fox *Vulpes vulpes*, Beech marten *Martes foina*, Badger *Meles meles*, Pine marten *Martes martes*, Polecat *Mustela putorius*, Stoat *Mustela erminea*, Raccoon *Procyon lotor*, and Raccoon dog *Nyctereutes procyonoides*. These practices are often applied in large conservation areas (e.g., Dümmer SPA), and hunting is usually carried out in cooperation with local hunters. Professional hunters work only on a few ongoing large-scale projects or have an advisory role.

A state-wide analysis of the effectiveness of predator removal to wet-grassland breeding bird conservation is difficult to establish due to differences in local conditions, hunting intensities, and success controls. However, long-term observations show that hunting is now necessary to achieve sufficient breeding success rates and positive

population trends in the majority of SPAs. A recent evaluation of the lethal removal of predators in the Dümmer SPA (Loonstra et al. 2024) showed that intensive year-round control of mammalian predators is associated with a significant increase in nest and chick survival of Black-tailed Godwits *Limosa l. limosa*. Thus, Loonstra et al. (2024) compared two treatments, or two intensities of predator control: 1) Low-intensity predator control described as occasional day and night hunting of mammalian predators by local hunters, and 2) intensified year-round predator control, which consisted of 1) increased hunting activity, 2) the use of baited live traps, and 3) the frequent control of known Red fox dens to remove adults and cubs. No hunting of avian raptors or corvids took place in this experiment. The results showed that, by combining the estimates of nest and chick survival, Black-tailed Godwit pairs raised between 0.97-1.12 fledglings per season when predators were controlled intensively, and only 0.09-0.18 fledglings with low-intensity predator control. Intensive predator control had the main relative effect on nest survival when compared to chick survival. However, that could be partially explained by the additive roles of habitat inadequacy, food item availability, the maintenance of avian predators in the area, or climatic events in explaining low chick survival when compared to nest survival.

Lessons from predation management in Lower Saxony show that:

1. Hunting should always be embedded together with other instruments in a holistic approach to meadow bird conservation.
2. Low predator densities during the breeding season are crucial, therefore, hunting just before/during the breeding season is most effective.
3. Hunting should cover the entire spectrum of predator species, as predation can quickly shift between species.
4. Prior evaluation and continuous monitoring of the populations of different predators are essential.
5. Given the potential risk of conflicts, it is advisable to inform and involve local actors (hunting tenants, nature conservation associations, etc.).
6. Successful predation management is systematically planned for the long term, should cover a large area, and needs continuous monitoring. This often requires significant funds and human efforts.

Passive predator control using enclosure (i.e., protection fences to deter predators) is also widely used to protect localized breeding populations in Lower Saxony.

Areas in which predation enclosure is increasingly used are primarily the SPAs **V66** (Figure 3, lowlands of the Süd- and Mittelradde and the Marka), **V40** (Diepholzer Moorniederung), **V06** (Rheiderland), **V27** Unterweser (Harrier Sand) and the BR Elbtalaue. Since 2011, experience from the SPAs Bleckriede and the Neustädter Moor in the **V40** shows that in suitable areas the hatching success of Northern Lapwing and Black-tailed Godwit can be increased by fencing off the nests. However, the predation of the chicks still represents a problem, as chicks usually leave the fenced area in search of food or can be predated within the fence by small predatory mammals, (e.g., the weasel), or by herons, birds of prey, and corvids. In addition, the effectiveness of fences is heavily dependent on their regular maintenance and, in the case of electric fences, on regular clearing. If the breeding pairs are spread out over a larger area due to the structure of the landscape or species-specific habitat requirements, passive predator control using fences is often not suitable since the maintenance effort increases enormously.

Habitat optimization and management can be used to limit and reduce predation pressures in breeding habitats. The creation and maintenance of suitable habitats is a basic requirement for the preservation and resettlement of breeding bird populations. This includes the creation of extensive wet habitats with few vertical structures (trees and man-made structures) that offer predators few opportunities to establish significant populations. Healthy wet grasslands have generally few hiding places and provide predators with relatively few preys that are available year-round. However, since large-scale habitat optimization can at the moment only be carried out at a small scale in Lower Saxony (with few exceptions, e.g., the Dümmer SPA), the establishment of a sustainable well-functioning ecosystem where predator populations are naturally low is practically impossible. The edge effects in degraded agricultural landscapes are often too high and have significant effects on the density of predators within the SPAs. Therefore, habitat optimization measures that can be implemented in Lower Saxony (and Germany, in general) have a limited effect on the population densities of native and non-native predatory mammals.

9. Monitoring

Bird population monitoring within SPAs

Bird population monitoring in SPAs in Lower Saxony and Bremen is usually conducted annually in important SPAs for wet-grassland breeding birds, and at least once every six years in all SPAs in alignment with the obligation to report on population status and trends to the EU Commission. The monitoring of breeding pairs is done by surveying breeding territories during the breeding season according to Südbeck et al. (2005). In some large SPAs, and when human capacities are limited, the surveys can be conducted in sections of the SPA over several years.

For a selected number of species that are subject to ongoing projects (e.g., Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa l. limosa*, Ruff *Calidris pugnax*, Corncrake *Crex crex*, and Snipe *Gallinago gallinago*), breeding population monitoring can be complemented by the monitoring of breeding success (number of fledged young birds per breeding pair), and birds are equipped with GPS transmitters to follow their migratory routes, habitat occupancy, and rates of returns to the SPAs.

Bird population monitoring outside SPAs

Targeted monitoring of wet-grassland breeding bird populations based on specific sampling areas outside of the SPAs is also conducted in Lower Saxony. This is usually done after a first assessment of available datasets provided by stakeholders including consultancy agencies, NGOs, or state-funded programs for rural development (e.g., PROLAND and later PFEIL for Lower Saxony, (PROLAND 2012-2017, PFEIL 2017-2023). Additionally, monitoring on a voluntary basis – sometimes coordinated by ornithological working groups – can deliver valuable data on populations and distribution. This helps narrow down areas for inspection and monitoring.

For the Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa l. limosa*, around 95,400 ha are included in the monitoring scheme outside of the SPAs with roughly 52% (49,900 ha) where birds currently occur and 48% (45,500 ha) where birds are considered extinct. Populated areas are at least

surveyed once every six years, and areas where the species is extinct, but where other grassland-breeding bird species may occur, are visited every twelve years.

10. Public land management via contracts

Land ownership has played a decisive role in the conservation and recovery of bird populations in some large SPAs in Lower Saxony, e.g., the Dümmer, Untereibe, and the Strohauser Plate. In contrast, conservation measures via contracts on private land in SPAs have been shown to provide limited long-term efficiency. Indeed, management contracts on private land have to go through ordinances and voluntary contractual measures, both deemed unstable and insufficient, therefore, providing limited sustainable long-term results.

About 43% (ca. 34,000 ha, Figure 23) of the grasslands located in SPAs in Lower Saxony are in public ownership. The term “publicly owned land” includes land owned by the Federal State domain (i.e., owned by the Federal State of Lower Saxony), counties, municipalities, and the federal government, as well as land owned by foundations, various conservation associations (e.g., NGOs), or areas dedicated to compensation measures.

**Ownership of grassland in meadow bird SPAs in Lower Saxony
(ca. 81.000 ha)**

Figure 23: Diagram showing land ownership in the 34 SPAs in Lower Saxony, considered important for wet-grassland breeding birds. Land ownership is categorized in 6 categories, one as private land, and the other 5 falling under the public ownership categorization.

Of the 21,000 ha owned by the Federal State of Lower Saxony, 49 % (10,500 ha, Figure 24) are earmarked for nature conservation and leased with usage restrictions to support nature conservation, which usually includes the protection of wet-grassland breeding

birds. An additional 19% (4,000 ha) not specifically earmarked for wet-grassland bird conservation, however, considered hotspots for breeding birds, have some limited farming restrictions. Another 21% (4,500 ha) are still without lease agreements concerning the protection of meadow birds and are in high agricultural productivity usage. On the last 11% (2,500 ha), we currently do not have enough data on the management types. Similarly, there is no overview of the management of areas owned by the federal government, counties and municipalities, and other public regional authorities. Due to these heterogeneous ownerships and other earmarked usages (e.g., flood protection), specific assessment of the proportion of these areas with actual bird-friendly management can only be approximate. However, overall, we can assume that at most two-thirds of the grasslands in public ownership are subject to one or another form of bird-friendly management obligation (NLWKN, unpublished data).

**Grassland owned by the federal state of Lower Saxony
(ca. 21.000 ha)**

Figure 24: Diagram showing the surface areas of grasslands owned by Lower Saxony under some sort of bird friendly farming management restrictions. The colors symbolize which Ministry is responsible for managing the areas. Striped green: Ministry for Environment; Striped red: Ministry for Agriculture; Solid blue and red are managed by different agencies (Agencies responsible for the domain management and for peatland management within the Ministry for Agriculture).

8 The Case of Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg

8.1 Populations and Trends

We present here the most recent population status and trends of the 11 species in Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg (Table 6). The data is derived from the latest Red Lists published by Mitschke (2019) for Hamburg, Kieckbusch et al. (2021) for Schleswig-Holstein, and Ryslavý et al. (2020) for Germany. For Europe, data was derived from the European Red List of Birds 2021 compiled by BirdLife International (2021). The European Red List is based on 4 international assessments carried out in 1994, 2004, 2015, and 2021.

Table 6: Table showing the populations of the 11 species considered in this conservation plan, in addition to population trends in Hamburg (HH, 2017), Schleswig-Holstein (SH, 2020), Germany (DE, 2020), and across Europe (Eur, 2021). The code color associated with the arrows indicates the gravity of population decrease: red and three downward arrows (↓↓↓) indicate a decrease of more than 50%, the yellow and two downward arrows (↓↓) indicate a decrease of more than 20%, light blue and equal sign (=) indicates a stable or slightly fluctuating population (decrease ≤ 20% or increase < 25%). Categories of the European Red List (Eur) are Least Concern (LC), Vulnerable (VU), and Near Threatened (NT).

Species	Population (breeding pairs)		Trends			
	SH*	HH**	SH***	HH****	DE	Eur
Corncrake <i>Crex crex</i>	50-170	50	=	↓↓	↓↓	LC
Eurasian Oystercatcher <i>Haematopus ostralegus</i>	9,500- 10,000	110	↓↓↓	=	↓↓	VU
Northern Lapwing <i>Vanellus vanellus</i>	11,000- 12,000	300	↓↓	↓↓	↓↓↓	VU
European Golden Plover <i>Pluvialis apricaria</i>	0	0	–	–	=	LC
Eurasian Curlew <i>Numenius arquata</i>	220-280	0	↓↓	–	↓↓	NT
Black-tailed Godwit <i>Limosa limosa</i>	925	3	↓↓	↓↓↓	↓↓↓	NT
Ruff <i>Philomachus pugnax</i> syn. <i>Calidris pugnax</i>	10-60	0	=	–	↓↓↓	NT
Dunlin <i>Calidris alpina</i>	0-6	0	↓↓	–	=	LC
Common Snipe	250	100	↓↓↓	↓↓	↓↓↓	VU

Species	Population (breeding pairs)		Trends			
<i>Gallinago gallinago</i>						
Common Redshank <i>Tringa totanus</i>	5,000	34	=	↓↓	=	VU
Whinchat <i>Saxicola rubetra</i>	900-1,100	3	↓↓	↓↓↓	↓↓↓	LC

*Population status as of 2020

**Population status as of 2017

***Short-term trend over 26 years (1994-2020)

****Short-term trend over 25 years (1992-2017)

8.2 Prevalent Conservation Practices and Instruments

1. Natura 2000 sites, SPAs, and other protected areas

The Umweltportal of **Schleswig-Holstein** (<https://umweltportal.schleswig-holstein.de>) provides user-friendly comprehensive maps where relevant areas of wet-grassland breeding birds can be displayed (Figure 25), in addition, users can display other relevant information for bird conservation, e.g., the location of SPAs (Figure 26) and other protected areas. Maps on the Umweltportal are periodically updated.

Figure 25: Wet-grassland and meadow bird breeding areas in Schleswig-Holstein as displayed by the Umweltportal (Mai 2024). Breeding areas are the dotted areas the red dotted terrestrial areas.

Figure 26: SPAs (EU-Vogelschutzbrutgebiete) in Schleswig-Holstein as displayed by the Umweltportal (Mai 2024). The red areas represent the delimitation of the SPAs.

In total, 46 SPAs are established in Schleswig-Holstein (as of February 2019). They are part of the European Natura 2000 network, and partially overlap with existing Special Area of Conservation (FFH), Nature Protection Areas (NSG), and Landscape Protection Areas (LSG). All information about these SPAs can be obtained from <https://www.schleswig-holstein.de/DE/fachinhalte/S/schutzgebiete/vogelschutz/Vogelschutzgebiete.html?what=spa>, where a search can be conducted by SPA (identifying number, name), county, bird species, and type of habitat. For the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds, the most important SPAs are listed in Table 7.

Table 7: List of the main SPAs important for the conservation of wet-grassland and meadow breeding and staging birds in Schleswig-Holstein.

SPA	Name	Area (ha)	Relevant species for the SCP
DE0916491	Ramsar-Gebiet SH Wattenmeer und angrenzende Küstengebiete (with numerous subareas (= Teilgebiete))	463,907	All 11 species

SPA	Name	Area (ha)	Relevant species for the SCP
DE1618404	Eiderstedt	6,704	Northern Lapwing, Black-tailed Godwit, Redshank, Golden Plover*
DE1622493	Eider-Treene-Sorge-Niederung	15,014	Lapwing, Whinchat, Ruff, Black-tailed Godwit, Curlew, Redshank, Corncrake, Golden Plover*
DE2323401	Untere Elbe bis Wedel	7,556	Whinchat, Lapwing, Black-tailed Godwit, Redshank, Corncrake, Golden Plover*, Dunlin*, Snipe
DE1119401	Gotteskoog-Gebiet	892	Whinchat, Lapwing, Black-tailed Godwit, Redshank, Snipe
DE1123491	Flensburger Förde (especially Teilgebiet Geltinger Birk)	12,404	Whinchat, Lapwing, Redshank, Corncrake, Golden Plover*, Snipe
DE1423491	Schlei	8,686	Whinchat, Lapwing, Redshank, Corncrake, Snipe

* Only as staging birds

In **Hamburg**, eight SPAs are established as of 2019. However, no SPAs are considered specifically important for the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds. Species like the Lapwing often occur outside of SPAs in agricultural land.

2. Management plans for protected areas

All SPAs important for wet-grassland breeding birds in **Schleswig-Holstein** have established management plans. These plans are heterogeneous differing in their level of ambition, and quality. Some need to be updated to current population levels and necessary actions to be carried out. All management plans can be openly accessed online (<https://www.schleswig-holstein.de/DE/fachinhalte/S/schutzgebiete/vogelschutz/Vogelschutzgebiete.html?what=spa>) both for entire SPAs or for parts (i.e., Teilgebiete).

The management plans developed in **Hamburg** are integrated into the Care and Development Plans (Pflege- und Entwicklungspläne, PEP) of the underlying nature conservation areas NSGs. There are no regular updates in a fixed cycle; the PEPs are revised or recreated when necessary. The PEPs are created in a standardized predetermined form (“PEP tool”), in a way that the structure, content, map displays, etc. are comparable. The PEPs for nature reserves with Natura 2000 areas contain several chapters that address the specific requirements of this protection status e.g. “Protected object of the Natura 2000 area, measures related to European protected assets, Natura 2000 in the nature protection areas (methodology of mapping and assessment of LRT and Annex II species, inventory of species and habitat types in the area).

The current management plans or PEP can be accessed online on the websites specified in the SDB (Standarddatenbogen-standard data forms; www.hamburg.de/natura2000/). Overall, the Natura 2000 areas, with the exception of the

Hamburg Wadden Sea National Park and the moor belt (where the Corncrake *Crex crex* is found), play a minor role for the bird species considered in this conservation plan.

3. The European Common Agricultural Policy

Schleswig-Holstein is contributing to the implementation of funding from the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) with its own funding measures as part of the national CAP strategic plan.

The implementation of the European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) in **Hamburg** is carried out by a regional monitoring committee BGA KLARA acting for Lower Saxony, Bremen, and Hamburg (Regionaler Begleitausschuss für Klima, Landwirtschaft, Artenvielfalt, Regionale AkteurlInnen) for the period 2023-2027. This regional monitoring committee is a central forum for participation and dialogue that reviews the progress and the implementation of the EAFRD funding and discusses regional aspects of the CAP strategic plan. Please refer to the section on Lower Saxony and Bremen for further information.

4. Agri-Environment-Climate Measures

In **Schleswig-Holstein**, the most recent Agri-Environment-Climate Measures (AECMs or AUKM) for the funding period 2023-2027 include contractual nature conservation (Vertragsnaturschutz - VNS) as an overarching instrument of contractual nature conservation. Within this framework, the Federal State government of Schleswig-Holstein has been offering farmers various contract schemes (Vertragsnaturschutzmuster) since 1986 in order to maintain or create suitable habitat conditions for animal and plant species in the agricultural landscape. Thus, contractual nature conservation is a state-specific AECMs aimed at nature conservation with the objective to:

- Implement and support the Natura 2000 network through adapted management to promote species and habitat conservation within and outside Natura 2000 areas
- Fulfill EU law and national species protection obligations
- Implement the strategy for preserving biological diversity in Schleswig-Holstein (Biodiversity objectives 2030)

The compensation payments are intended to encourage land managers, on a voluntary basis, to adopt ecologically valuable land use practices that go beyond existing legal obligations (EU, federal, or state law). The payments serve to offset yield losses or additional expenses, including potential transaction costs, resulting from nature conservation management requirements.

The changes in land management of arable land or grassland according to the various contract schemes, as well as additional biotope enhancement measures, serve to create valuable habitat structures for numerous animal groups (including birds, amphibians, insects, mammals) and plant species. The results of accompanying scientific studies have shown that reduced grazing intensity in spring/summer, as well as year-round extensive grazing, later mowing dates, and the avoidance or reduction of fertilizers and pesticides are suitable measures benefiting the breeding success of meadow birds.

Contracts are granted within the framework of a classical public-law contract to be concluded in advance as an area-related payment per hectare of contract area and paid out

as an annual grant. The commitment period is five years and can be extended by one year at a time until the end of the funding period. The funding for contractual nature conservation comes from the "European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development" (EAFRD) as well as from the national funding instrument "Joint Task for the Improvement of Agricultural Structures and Coastal Protection" (GAK) or from Federal State funds. Contractual nature conservation is offered in FFH/SAC areas (Special area of conservation (SAC) as defined in the EU's Habitats Directive) and SPAs as well as in nature conservation areas. It is also possible to conclude a contract for areas with FFH habitat types or species listed in Annex IV of the FFH Directive (e.g., amphibian species) and bird species that breed on agricultural land (e.g., Lapwing).

The priority of the contractual nature conservation measures is grasslands. Since 2015, a so-called "Hallig program", applicable only on the Halligen (North Frisian barrier islands in the Wadden Sea), has also been offered as a contract scheme within the framework of contractual nature conservation. The Federal State has been promoting extensive agricultural use on the Halligen Langeneß, Oland, Gröde, Hooge and Nordstrandischmoor since 1987 and, to a limited extent, the Halligen Südfall and Süderoog since 2007.

For the current EAFRD funding period 2023-2027, we summarize below (Table 8) the main schemes that will directly benefit the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds (Vertragsnaturschutzmuster). All schemes can be found, with explanatory sheets, on <https://www.schleswig-holstein.de/DE/landesregierung/themen/umwelt-naturschutz/vertragsnaturschutz>. Currently, some of these schemes are being revised, especially the compensation aspects as well as the management times.

Additional schemes, like Small-scale farming (Kleinteiligkeit im Ackerbau FP 6608), Arable habitats (Ackerlebensräume FP 6609), Valuable grassland (Wertgrünland FP 6137), Grassland habitats (Grünlandlebensräume FP 6147), Conversion of arable land into grassland (Umwandlung von Ackerland in Grünlandlebensräume FP 6157), and Resting place for migratory bird species (Rastplätze für wandernde Vogelarten FP 6177), are expected to have significant effects on grassland biodiversity in general and therefore can be expected to indirectly benefit wet-grassland and meadow breeding birds.

Table 8: Main schemes (Vertragsnaturschutzmuster) under the contractual nature conservation (Vertragsnaturschutz) that are expected to directly benefit the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds in Schleswig-Holstein. Instruments are briefly described with the compensation levels. All instrument can be found, with explanatory sheets, on <https://www.schleswig-holstein.de/> under the section Vertragsnaturschutz. Data corresponds to the available information as of July 2024.

Scheme	Main management instructions	Compensation
Grazing (Weidegang FP 6600)	Aimed at preserving open grasslands through active grassland management; The current water level must not be lowered; The areas must not be plowed, grubbed or any similar process; Grazing is permitted with cattle; Mixed grazing with horses and sheep possible; Minimum of two cattle/hectare; Minimum grazing period from May to September; From October to April, exclusive sheep grazing or reduced grazing with cattle is also possible; No mowing on the areas (not even	190€: With tillage blocking period 170€: No tillage blocking period

Scheme	Main management instructions	Compensation
	<p>before grazing); maintenance mowing from June 21st allowed.</p> <p>Optionally no dragging and/or rolling or comparable soil cultivation measures in the period from April 1st. until June 20th; any new seeding measures are prohibited</p>	
<p>Pasture farming (Weidewirtschaft FP 6601)</p>	<p>The aim of the “Pasture farming” contract is to preserve and, if necessary, expand grassland on the Geest and in the Eastern Hill Country, which is divided by small structures such as bodies of water, creeks, woody plants and unused areas.</p> <p>Measures include: No fertilization of the areas; No use of pesticides; No lowering of the water level; No hauling or rolling or other soil cultivation during the period from April 1st. until June 20th; No additional feeding on the contract areas; Tolerating the presence of geese, swans and ducks.</p> <p>Variants of the measure exist, refer to the original documents in German.</p>	<p>490€: Standing pasture, max. 3 animals per ha</p> <p>470€: Mowing from June 21st</p> <p>+ additional 120€ in the case of geese resting in the area</p>
<p>Pasture farming moorland (Weidewirtschaft Moor FP 6602)</p>	<p>The main objective of the funding is on grassland areas in moorland lowlands that have been identified as breeding areas for meadow birds based on the state-wide population surveys of the Federal State Ornithological Institute. Priority will be given to contracts for grassland areas in Natura 2000 areas.</p> <p>Main requirements include: No use of pesticides; No mineral fertilization of the areas; No organic fertilization from April 1st. until June 20th; alternatively: general ban on fertilization; Use of the areas as extensively managed permanent grassland, no later than September 1st. one year; No lowering of the water level; No rolling or towing during the period from April 1st. until June 20th.</p> <p>Variants of the measure exist, refer to the original documents in German.</p>	<p>520€ (400€): Standing pasture, max. 4 animals per ha</p> <p>490€ (370€): Mowing from June 21st</p> <p>(Optional organic fertilization permitted)</p>
<p>Pasture farming marshland (Weidewirtschaft Marsch FP 6603)</p>	<p>The focus of the funding is on grassland areas on the Eiderstedt peninsula as well as other areas in the clayey marshes of the west coast and the Lower Elbe that have been identified as breeding areas for meadow birds and black terns based on the stated-wide population surveys of Federal State Ornithological Institute. Priority will be given to contracts for grassland areas in Natura 2000 areas</p>	<p>600€ (480€): Standing pasture, max. 4 animals per ha.</p> <p>570€ (450€): Mowing from June 21st</p>

Scheme	Main management instructions	Compensation
	<p>Main requirements include: No use of pesticides; No mineral fertilization of the areas; No organic fertilization during the period from 01.04. until June 20th; alternatively: general ban on fertilization; Use of the areas as grassland; No lowering of the water level; No rolling and/or dragging in time from 01.04. until June 20th; Use must be made by September 1st at the latest of the year has taken place or begun.</p> <p>Variants of the measure exist, refer to the original documents in German.</p>	<p>(Optional organic fertilization permitted)</p> <p>BGM obligatory: rewetting measures</p> <p>+ additional 120€ in the case of goose resting in the area</p>
<p>Pasture landscape marshland (Weidelandschaft Marsch FP 6604)</p>	<p>The aim of the “Pasture Landscape Marshland” contract is to support the continuation of a traditional form of grassland farming on large fenceless areas, where ditches can be used to guarantee livestock farming.</p> <p>The funding focuses on grassland areas on Eiderstedt as well as other areas in the clayey marshes of the west coast and the Lower Elbe that have been identified as breeding areas for meadow birds and black terns based on the state-wide population surveys of the Federal State Ornithological Institute. Priority will be given to contracts for grassland areas in Natura 2000 areas.</p> <p>Grassland areas are divided into a system of different management intensities (red, yellow and green areas). On at least 10% of the contract area (red areas), extensive waterlogging and extensive grazing should create particularly attractive breeding grounds for meadow birds.</p> <p>The most important requirement is the inclusion of at least 90% of a farm's grassland area within a region.</p> <p>The requirement for each category will not be detailed here, please refer to the German documents.</p> <p>At least 10% of the area is required to be in red category; obligatory BGM e.g., ditch damming; on red areas, waterlogging measures are required.</p>	<p>Green area: 130€ (160€), without specific requirements on the number of animals or mowing dates</p> <p>(Optional no dragging etc. April 1st to June 20th)</p> <p>Yellow area: 550€M; max. 4 animals/ha; Mowing from June 21st; organic fertilization allowed</p> <p>Red area: 990€; standing pasture (max. 4 animals/ha)</p> <p>+ additional 120€ in the case of goose resting in the area</p>
<p>Pasture landscape moorland (Weidelandschaft Moor FP 6605)</p>	<p>With similar objectives like the previous instrument but for moorland, the focus of the funding is on the Eider-Treene-Sorge lowlands as well as other lowlands and raised moor areas, which are identified as important breeding areas for meadow birds in the state-wide inventory</p>	<p>Green area: 270€ (110€); without specifying the number of animals or mowing.</p> <p>Yellow area: 510€</p>

Scheme	Main management instructions	Compensation
	<p>surveys of the Federal State Ornithological Institute.</p> <p>The most important requirements include, the inclusion of at least 90% of the grassland area of a company/farm within a region.</p> <p>The following applies to all areas (green, yellow, red): Use of the areas as grassland; No lowering of the water level; Tolerating the feeding of geese and swans and ducks; The implementation and toleration of biotope shaping measures on plot ditches (especially flattening of embankments, removal of trees) is mandatory; Mandatory participation in the 'collaborative meadow bird protection' (in compliance with the associated additional management requirements); The alternatives (hay pasture or pasture) must be determined bindingly for each individual area at the start of the contract for the duration of the contract.</p> <p>Additional requirements for the ref, yellow, of green areas can be found in the German documents.</p>	<p>(480€); Mowing from June 21st; Standing pasture (max. 4 animals/ha)</p> <p>930€ (900€): Temporary water retention; with or without animal number limits; Mowing from June 21st</p> <p>+ additional 120€ in the case of goose resting in the area</p>

In **Hamburg**, the AECMs are offered through the Federal State of Lower Saxony, via the regional platform KLARA for the funding period 2023-2027. See, section lower Saxony for available AECMs.

5. Social and Political Initiatives

In 2018, the Ministry of agriculture and environment of **Schleswig-Holstein** started a dialogue process “Future of Agriculture in Schleswig-Holstein (Zukunft der Landwirtschaft)”. Farmers as well as various public groups were invited to contribute and discuss their ideas on how a future-oriented agriculture in the year 2040 should be. Numerous dialogues, forums, and workshops were conducted to discuss the different perspectives, and by the end of the dialogue process “24 theses on the future of agriculture” were adopted and agreed upon by all participants. Biodiversity and the possibilities of an agricultural production which benefits biodiversity were topics of this discussion and it was agreed upon, that biodiversity of an attractive cultural landscape should be established by cooperation between agriculture and nature conservation. Additionally, biodiversity as a topic in the professional training of farmers should be promoted. It was intended to continue the dialogue to strengthen the collaborative efforts to harmonize economical, ecological, and social aspects in the future agriculture in Schleswig-Holstein.

A direct positive effect of the process on meadow birds is not expected. However, a farming approach intended to also benefit biodiversity could mid- to long-term also benefit meadow birds.

In 2022, the **Hamburg "Agriculture and Nature Conservation Dialogue"** was initiated. Representatives of the Chamber of Agriculture, farmers' associations, nature conservation associations and BUKEA representatives from the agriculture and nature conservation departments are taking part in this process. One aim of the dialog process is to formulate concrete project proposals on the four key topics of climate and moorland protection, agriculture in transition, reduction of land loss, and biodiversity protection, which are then implemented with the cooperation of the groups involved. One of these flagship projects in the area of biodiversity conservation is to be based on the above-mentioned project in Hamburg-Wilhelmsburg. From 2024, the concept is to be extended to other areas that have a constant population of field-breeding lapwings and an interlinking of arable and grassland habitats, so that at least 20% of Hamburg's lapwing population can be covered by the conservation efforts in future. Close cooperation with the farmers' association and the Chamber of Agriculture is planned.

A positive effect on the population of meadow breeders in grassland is also expected from other flagship projects, e.g. from the climate and moorland protection working group.

6. LIFE-funded Projects: Development and Implementation

Schleswig-Holstein acquired recently three major LIFE-funded projects (Table 9). Their development is often a joint effort between the Naturschutzbund Deutschland NABU (Michael-Otto-Institut im NABU), the Stiftung Naturschutz Schleswig-Holstein and the Environmental Ministry of Schleswig-Holstein (Ministerium für Energiewende, Klimaschutz, Umwelt und Natur).

The **LIFE-Wadden Sea Birds** (LIFE19 NAT/DK/000922; Restoring and managing bird habitats in the Danish and German Wadden Sea area) is a joint project between Denmark and Schleswig-Holstein with the objective to counteract six identified threats to birds, including few waders considered in this conservation plan, and their habitats in the Danish and German Wadden Sea area. The objectives include, 1) significantly increasing the number and conservation status of Pied Avocet (*Recurvirostra avosetta*), Ruff (*Philomachus pugnax*), Common Tern (*Sterna hirundo*), Arctic Tern (*Sterna paradisaea*), Little Tern (*Sternula albifrons*), short-eared owl (*Asio flammeus*), Black-tailed Godwit (*Limosa limosa*), Bluethroat (*Luscinia svecica*), Dunlin (*Calidris alpina schinzii*), and Kentish Plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus*) by improving and restoring feeding and breeding habitats; and 2) significantly increase the number and conservation status of migrating/wintering species, including Widgeon (*Anas Penelope*), Pintail (*Anas acuta*), Shoveler (*Anas clypeata*), Redshank (*Tringa tetanus*), and Curlew (*Numenius arquata*), as well as a number of Annex II species, such as Lapwing (*Vanellus vanellus*) and Oystercatcher (*Haematopus ostralegus*), and to maintain a favorable conservation status of other Annex I species.

The **Better BirdLIFE** (LIFE17 NAT/DK/000498, Improvement of natural habitats for coastal birds in the West Baltic Sea) is a joint project between Denmark and Schleswig-Holstein focused on the conservation of coastal birds and their habitats in the West Baltic Sea. Its main objectives are to: 1) improve natural habitats for 10 bird species listed in Annex 1 of Directive 2009/147/EC and 4 species of regularly occurring migratory bird species. 2) Improve conservation status for the 14 bird species targeted. 3) contribute to obtaining favorable conservation status for 10 natural habitat types listed in Annex 1 of Directive 92/43/EEC. And 4) counteract 8 identified threats toward the 14 bird species and 10 natural

habitat types. The 14 bird species considered in the project include the Corn Crake *Crex crex*, the Dunlin *Calidris alpina*, and the Ruff *Philomachus pugnax*.

The **LIFE-Limos**a (LIFE11 NAT/DE/000353, Stabilization of the core population of the Black-tailed Godwit and protection of Dunlin and Ruff) project's primary objective is to improve the situation for the last remaining core meta-populations of the Black-tailed Godwit (*Limosa limosa*) in Schleswig-Holstein by increasing the reproduction success. Secondary objectives are the implementation of measures to support the efforts to prevent the loss of the last breeding pairs of Dunlin (*Calidris alpina schinzii*) and Ruff (*Philomachus pugnax*).

Table 9 : Most recent LIFE funded projects that directly supported the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds in Schleswig-Holstein.

Project reference	Title	Time frame	Budget (€)
LIFE11 NAT/DE/000353 (LIFE Limosa)	Stabilization of the core population of the Black-tailed Godwit and protection of Dunlin and Ruff	01.10.2012 – 31.12.2023	6,106,540
LIFE17 NAT/DK/000498 (Better BirdLIFE)	Improvement of natural habitats for coastal birds in the West Baltic Sea	01.09.2018 – 01.10.2025	8,421,446
LIFE19 NAT/DK/000922 (LIFE Wadden Sea Birds)	Restoring and managing bird habitats in the Danish and German Wadden Sea area	01.09.2020 – 31.12.2026	9,289,740
Total		2012 – 2026	23,817,726

No LIFE-funded projects targeting wet-grassland breeding birds were developed recently in **Hamburg**.

7. Clutch-and-chick Protection

In the Eider-Treene-Sorge lowlands in **Schleswig-Holstein**, already in the late 1990's a clutch-and-chick protection program was established, initiated by local farmers and nature conservationists (later founding KUNO e.V. - Kulturlandschaft nachhaltig organisieren e.V.) from the regions of Meggerdof and Erfde and funded by the Federal State (also see case study).

The program aims at protecting meadow birds on conventionally farmed grassland. The approach is results-oriented and participation is voluntary, uncomplicated and simple. Volunteers and full-time site managers mark meadow bird clutches and try to observe bird families until the chicks have fledged. Site managers and farmers jointly agree on appropriate conservation measures. At the beginning of the breeding season, this includes, for example, restrictions on manure, and later in the season mainly delays in mowing. Especially in grazed meadows, sensitive areas can be protected by a mobile fence. The

Ministry of Energy Transition, Climate Protection, Environment and Nature (MEKUN) pays compensation to farmers for lost profits due to these measures. As soon as the birds have left an area, agricultural activities can resume after prior approval by the site managers. All agreements are arranged flexibly and at short notice and are only valid for one year, which makes it easier for farmers to participate. All ground-breeding meadow birds can be protected in this way, with the most common species being Lapwing, Black-tailed Godwit, Curlew, and Oystercatcher. The compensation amounts depend on the intensity of the agreed upon restriction and thus the assumed loss of profit (e.g., fodder value).

Since 2008, the species protection program “Collaborative meadow bird protection program” (Gemeinschaftlicher Wiesenvogelschutz <https://bergenhusen.nabu.de/forschung/wiesenvoegel/index.html>) is coordinated by the Michael-Otto-Institut im NABU (MOIN) and funded by the Environmental Ministry of Schleswig-Holstein. Nowadays, different NGOs organize the local support with site managers and farmers in eight different grassland-dominated regions of Schleswig-Holstein can participate (Figure 27):

- Eider-Treene-Sorge-Niederung (KUNO e.V.)
- Föhr (Bund für Natur und Umweltschutz Deutschland e.V. - BUND)
- Amrum (MOIN, Amrum Touristik & Öömring e.V.)
- Pellworm (MOIN)
- Haaler Au (Interessengemeinschaft (IG) Haaler Au)
- Langenhorn (MOIN)
- Oberalsterniederung (NABU)
- Miele- und Windberger Niederung (Bündnis Naturschutz in Dithmarschen - BNiD)

Figure 27: Location of the core areas and the areas of the species protection program in Schleswig-Holstein. Other areas are also outside of this area concerned by the program. Figure source <https://bergenhusen.nabu.de/forschung/wiesenvoegel/index.html>

Electric poultry fences have been used to protect broods of meadow birds since 2009. Since 2013, the focus of the measure has been on the curlew. When a clutch was found, it is first checked whether it is a full clutch (4 eggs). If this is the case, two electric poultry fences (each 50 m long and 120 cm high) are placed at a distance of 12.5 m around the nest. Wooden stakes are used at the four corner points to stabilize the fence. Depending on the ground conditions, at least two pegs are used to connect the electric fence to the ground on each fence section. An electric fence generator equipped with a car battery and solar panel provides the power supply. After the fence is erected, it is observed from a distance until an adult bird returns to breed. If no breeding bird returns within 120 minutes, the fence is dismantled again. In rare cases in recent years, this method has also been used on meadow bird colonies or individually breeding Black-tailed Godwits.

Additionally to the above-mentioned original scheme, variations of the program benefitting meadow song birds, Corncrake *Crex crex*, and short-eared owl *Asio flammeus* are possible. For example, strips of older vegetation (“Altgrasstreifen”) can be left standing as retreat areas for families of meadow birds and small game, as well as breeding grounds for songbirds and insects. Clutches of Stonechat *Saxicola rubicola* or Meadow Pipit *Anthus pratensis* and Reed Bunting *Emberiza schoeniclus* are often found along the edges of ditches in longer vegetation stands. The protective strips are intended to protect unknown clutches or to provide a retreat for meadow bird families that are in the area. The prerequisite for this is a minimum width of 9 m and a first cut no earlier than August 10th.

In addition, efforts to protect clutches of Lapwings in crop fields are acknowledged with a compensation payment per clutch. This is especially appealing for farmers, if a small colony of Lapwings establishes.

In **Hamburg**, there are currently 280 breeding pairs of Lapwings, and around 80% of them breed on arable land. It is therefore not possible to conserve the species in Hamburg without protecting this breeding population. A pilot project in Hamburg-Wilhelmsburg, running since the beginning of 2022, is specifically aimed at the conservation of Lapwings breeding pairs on arable land. Due to its success, the project has been spread out since then and covers recently an area of about 3.600 hectares. In order to provide consistent care for the area, the “Hamburg Lapwing Watchers” (Hamburger Kiebitz-Kieker) were founded in 2024. They act as the point of contact for all project-partners, especially farmers. Their office is run by BUND Hamburg and Nabu Hamburg and financed by BUKEA. This pilot project is a joint project effort between BUKEA, N3, BUND Hamburg and Nabu Hamburg. Lapwing clutches are being marked and documented on arable land. A close cooperation between farmers and volunteer who are dedicated to find nests, and the implementation of undisturbed areas around the clutches, accompanying measures to improve the habitat (creation of temporary shallow water bodies) have led to an increase of the breeding population of Lapwings. As in other clutch-and-chick protection measures farmers receive compensation payments for protecting the nests.

8. Predation Management

The most recent predation management concept published by **Schleswig-Holstein** in 2018 presents a comprehensive overview of the impact of predation and its management across the Federal State (accessible online: <https://www.schleswig-holstein.de/DE/fachinhalte/A/artenschutz/Downloads/PraedationsmanagementkonzeptSH.pdf>)

f?__blob=publicationFile&v=1). The concept targets mainly meadow and shore-bird conservation, e.g., Black-tailed Godwit, Lapwing, Curlew, Redshank, etc., and ground-nesting colony breeders like Gulls, Terns, Avocets, etc. It provides a baseline analysis of the impact and distribution of major mammalian and avian predators across the Federal State, including neozoa. The concept provides also a detailed description of methods and approaches used to manage predation.

Predation management in Schleswig-Holstein consists of different tools, including: 1) Habitat optimization to limit the impact of predation; 2) Predator exclusion efforts; 3) Hunting and the lethal removal of predators; and 4) other pilot and site-specific measures including hedgehog removal, rat population control, or distraction feeding (i.e., artificial feeding to ease predation pressures on breeding birds). The latter is controversial and still needs to prove valuable for bird conservation.

Habitat optimization – Schleswig-Holstein acknowledges that landscape and habitat optimization to reduce the impacts of predation are the main long-term effective measures that will guarantee the sustainable management and conservation of ground breeding bird species. This is even more relevant when almost all threatened ground-breeding species nowadays reproduce in arable land and cultivated landscapes. Habitat optimization includes 1) changes in land use, 2) water table optimization, rewetting, and temporary sporadic flooding to limit the establishment of ground predators and their main prey (reducing feeding opportunities, destruction of burrows, limiting reproduction), 3) restoring natural habitat dynamics at large scale, e.g., in floodplains and in the marshlands along the North Sea and Baltic Coasts.

Predator exclusion – The often-low remaining populations of many bird species and the poor breeding success make it necessary to intervene with immediate predator exclusion measures without losing sight of the goal to achieve a comprehensive habitat restoration and conservation approach. Predator exclusion efforts are conducted through 1) the protection of clutches and small-scale breeding sites using covers and fences with or without electricity. On the coasts, nest baskets or wire covers with a side entrance can be used primarily to protect the nests of waders and terns from seagulls. However, since nest baskets can lead to a mortality of adult birds if attacked by predators on the nest, these are not commonly used in Schleswig-Holstein. 2) Large-scale exclusion of predators. Ground predators can be kept away from certain breeding areas by permanently installing fences that can be particularly effective on peninsulas or islands that can be reached by predators by swimming or over the ice sheet in winter. Wide ditches can also be created to keep predators, e.g., foxes, away from breeding areas. 3) Hatchery island and rafts. Those artificially created rafts can provide breeding sites for tern species and cannot be reached by land predators.

Recently, three larger permanent anti-predation electrical fences were built in the Dithmarscher Speicherkoog (36 ha), the Eiderdammflächen (84 ha) and the Beltringharder Koog (34 ha) (all part of the SPA DE 0916-491 “Ramsar-Gebiet S-H Wattenmeer und angrenzende Küstengebiete”), partially financed by the LIFE Limosa project. In 2024, a three-year project started to evaluate the effect of these fences on hatching and breeding success as well as analyze the food availability for bird chicks in the areas, funded by the environmental ministry (MEKUN).

Hunting and the removal of predators – Measures aimed at lethally removing predators always require careful consideration and can be controversial with other

conservation objectives. Predator removal also includes live trapping and the relocation of predators. Live trapping is usually considered when only a few individuals are responsible for predation, e.g., Hedgehogs on Norderney.

Since autumn 2021, in the Beltringharder Koog and the Rickelsbüller Koog (both part of the SPA DE 0916-491 “Ramsar-Gebiet S-H Wattenmeer und angrenzende Küstengebiete”) a three-year pilot project evaluating the effect of professional hunting measures to reduce predation risk on breeding birds is conducted. First results show an overall positive effect on both hatching and breeding success of most birds such as Lapwings, Oystercatchers, and Pied Avocet. To determine possible mid- to long-term effects and possible effects on the population of smaller predators such as rats the project was extended for another five years until at least August 2029.

Additionally, a project funded by the Nationalparkstiftung Schleswig-Holstein assesses the influence of brown rat *Rattus norvegicus* on hatching and breeding success of meadow and coastal birds on the island of Pellworm, the Halligen Hooge, Langeness and Oland as well as the North Frisian Barrier Islands Japsand and Norderoogsand (https://www.schutzstation-wattenmeer.de/fileadmin/schutzstation/dokumente/aktuelles/Publikationen/Projektbericht_Pra%CC%88dationsmonitoring_Halligen_SW_2021.pdf). The main aim of the project is to assess the impact of brown rats on the breeding success and to develop management options depending on the differing starting conditions, e.g. rat population size, flooding regime, accessibility.

For the Wadden Sea Region, the Breeding Bird Action Plan (Koffijberg et al. 2016) which was adopted within the framework of the trilateral Wadden Sea Cooperation as a response to the ongoing severe population declines of shorebirds, established that the top priority is keeping the islands free of land predators and preventing their access to Halligen Oland and Langeness and the Hallig Nordstrandischmoor via the recently established dam connection. In addition, the restoration of the natural water regime in salt marches was also recommended on the mainland coast. The closure of artificial drainages should lead to recovering the natural flood dynamics, and promote the formation of islands thus the reduction of predation pressures.

There are currently no projects in **Hamburg** in which active predation management in the form of targeted hunting/trapping is used. Temporary protective fences are used in a few sub-areas. In the Wilhelmsburg project area, trials were carried out to protect individual nests with nest protection baskets, but these are only suitable for specific locations and conditions and are only used selectively. As the whole range of native predators can be found in Hamburg (especially the red fox), as well as raccoon dogs, raccoons, and domestic cats, some of which occur in high densities, predation is a significant factor contributing to the decline of grassland-breeding bird populations. However, appropriate measures, whether active (hunting, traps) or passive (fences, etc.), are sometimes very difficult to implement in an urban area like Hamburg.

9. Monitoring

In **Schleswig-Holstein**, on behalf of the Environmental Ministry (Ministerium für Energiewende, Klimaschutz, Umwelt und Natur) and the Federal State Ornithological

Institute (Staatliche Vogelschutzwarte des Landesamtes für Umwelt), a monitoring of wet-grassland breeding bird populations (Wiesenvogelmonitoring) is conducted and coordinated.

Breeding and resting bird populations are regularly monitored in designated areas, including SPAs and other important conservation areas. In all areas relevant for meadow breeding birds (Wiesenvogelkullisse), at least once every six years a full survey of breeding meadow birds (focus on Black-tailed Godwit, Lapwing, Curlew, Snipe, Oystercatcher, and Redshank) is conducted as required by the national monitoring scheme and EU guidelines. Additionally, data collected from NGOs and the collaborative meadow bird program are integrated in the database as well. All monitoring data are centralized at the Federal State Ornithological Institute and the current contractor for ornithological scientific support (Michael-Otto-Institut im NABU, MOIN) has access to establish population development trends across Schleswig-Holstein using TRIM models.

The monitoring of wet-grassland birds in **Hamburg** benefited from regular mapping efforts that accompanied contractual nature conservation ornithologically for decades now. Mapping is carried out within a defined mapping area that includes all important areas where birds occur. This includes areas inside and outside protected areas. If necessary, the mapping efforts can be extended according to technical criteria. The mapping is carried out annually over an area of 3,000-5,000 hectares, with sub-areas of the backdrop being surveyed at different intervals, ranging from annually to every 5 years.

Data on meadow birds is also collected as part of general breeding bird mapping. These breeding bird surveys are divided into three modules:

Module 1, SPA monitoring: The mapping and data analysis through third-party mapping is carried out annually on behalf of the BUKEA in different SPAs concerning species listed in Annex I of Directive 2009/147/EC (Birds Directive). This allows BUKEA to determine the conservation status of the species at the SPA level. Each site is assessed every 6 years.

Module 2, monitoring at the Federal State level: An assessment of the conservation status of Annex 1 species at the Federal State level is also carried out every 6 years through mapping and data analysis.

Module 3, monitoring of common breeding birds: The monitoring of common breeding birds, which has been carried out regularly every 3 to 5 years throughout Hamburg since 1992, should also be mentioned. The evaluated trends, which also include various species from this conservation plan, are available up to 2021.

This information relates to the Hamburg area excluding the national park areas of the Hamburg Wadden Sea National Park. Regular breeding bird surveys are also carried out there, but these are not included in the above-mentioned monitoring activities. The latest survey data from the Hamburg Wadden Sea National Park are added to the information in the SDS (Standarddatenbogen) for information purposes.

10. Public Land Management via Contracts

Publicly owned land lies especially in the so-called nature conservation polder (“Naturschutzköge”) at the west-coast of **Schleswig-Holstein**, and in the estuary of the Eider

river, which are part of the SPA “Ramsar-Gebiet Schleswig-Holsteinisches Wattenmeer and angrenzende Küstengebiete” (DE 0916-491) as well as along the Elbe river near Haseldorf/Hetlingen, which are part of the SPA “Untere Elbe bis Wedel” (DE 2323-402).

These areas are managed by the integrated conservation stations (Integrierte Station Westküste, Integrierte Station Untere Elbe and Integrierte Station Eider-Treene-Sorge), which are part of the Federal State Agency for the Environment (Landesamt für Umwelt, LfU). Here, the main aim especially in grassland habitats is to increase the habitat suitability for grassland breeding birds by:

- Reducing trees, shrubs, and reed areas often used as shelter and hiding places for predators
- Adjusting water management to maintain high water levels with varying depth until the end of the breeding season in combination with open wet grasslands
- Maintaining short grass sward at the beginning of the breeding season by grazing and/ or mowing
- Maintaining a plant species rich grassland with high insect diversity
- Reducing the number of predators within the scope of the predation management concept (see above).

To achieve these goals, regular management measures as well as a land-use scheme adapted to the specific requirements of ground breeding birds are necessary. Thus, contracts with local farmers on public land commonly include late mowing times or reduced grazing intensity and later starting of the grazing period, preferably with smaller and robust cattle breeds.

Additionally, to the publicly owned land, the state-foundation for nature conservation (Stiftung Naturschutz Schleswig-Holstein) owns larger areas within SPAs such as the Eider-Treene-Sorge lowlands (DE 1622-493), Eiderstedt (DE 1618-404), the Geltinger Birk (part of DE 1123-491) and the lower Elbe river (DE 2323-402) as well as adjacent grassland areas with importance for grassland breeding birds. Within these areas, the foundation carries out conservation measures such as the widening of existing drainage creeks to create mudbanks, adjusting the water management and raising water levels during the breeding season, erecting mobile electrical fences against predators and including grazing or mowing restrictions with late mowing after the 20th of June or reduced stocking densities until mid-July into lease contracts.

Some other areas within relevant SPAs are owned by the local water and soil associations, the Federal State agency for coastal defense (Landesbetrieb für Küstenschutz, Nationalpark und Meeresschutz Schleswig-Holstein) or the German Army, who often integrate conservation goals for breeding birds into their management schemes, in accordance to the management plans for the SPAs.

For areas within the SPA's which are neither publicly owned nor owned by the nature conservation foundations, participation in specific contractual conservation schemes is encouraged to increase the area on which bird-friendly management regimes are conducted.

There are currently in **Hamburg** around 1,300 hectares of grassland under contractual nature conservation primarily geared towards the needs of meadow birds with specifications for tillage dates adapted to the breeding season. Contractual nature

conservation is flanked by ornithological mapping so that a flexible response can be made to breeding activity.

9 The Case of North Rhine-Westphalia

9.1 Populations and Trends

We present here the most recent population status and trends of the 11 species (Table 10). The data is derived from two state-wide assessments in 2016 and 2022 for breeding pairs (Jöbges et al 2024). For Europe, data was derived from the European Red List of Birds 2021 compiled by BirdLife International (2021). The European Red List is based on 4 international assessments carried out in 1994, 2004, 2015, and 2021.

Table 10: Table showing the populations and population trends of the 11 species in North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany (DE), and across Europe (Eur). Population data were provided by Birgit Beckers (pers. com) and the classification in the Red-list for 2021 extracted from (Sudmann et al. 2021). The code color associated with the arrows indicates the gravity of population decrease: red and three downward arrows (↓↓↓) indicate a decrease of more than 50%, the yellow and two downward arrows (↓↓) indicate a decrease of more than 20%, light blue and equal sign (=) indicates a stable or slightly fluctuating population (decrease ≤ 20% or increase < 25%), and the upward arrow (↑) for an increase of 20% or more. Categories of the European Red List (Eur) are Least Concern (LC), Vulnerable (VU), and Near Threatened (NT).

Species	Population (breeding pairs)		Trends		
	2016	2022	NRW	DE	Eur
Corncrake <i>Crex crex</i>	NA	NA	↓↓	↓↓	LC
Eurasian Oystercatcher <i>Haematopus ostralegus</i>	NA	NA	=	↓↓	VU
Northern Lapwing <i>Vanellus vanellus</i>	12,000	5,500	↓↓↓	↓↓↓	VU
European Golden Plover <i>Pluvialis apricaria</i>	0	0	–	=	LC
Eurasian Curlew <i>Numenius arquata</i>	638	549	=	↓↓	NT
Black-tailed Godwit <i>Limosa limosa</i>	143	73	↓↓↓	↓↓↓	NT

Species	Population (breeding pairs)		Trends		
Ruff <i>Philomachus pugnax</i> syn. <i>Calidris pugnax</i>	0	0	–	↓↓↓	NT
Dunlin <i>Calidris alpina</i>	0	0	–	=	LC
Common Snipe <i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	30	16	↓↓↓	↓↓↓	VU
Common Redshank <i>Tringa totanus</i>	49	49	=	=	VU
Whinchat <i>Saxicola rubetra</i>	190	174	↓↓↓	↓↓↓	LC

9.2 Prevalent Conservation Practices and Instruments

1. Conservation of Natura 2000 sites, SPAs, and other protected areas

SPAs play a major role in the conservation of wet grassland breeding birds in North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW). In total, 29 SPAs (Vogelschutzgebiete) have been designated in NRW, spanning a wide range of areas, the smallest being 84 ha (Bruchhauser Steine, a forest-dominated site) and the largest more than 48,000 ha (Hellwegbörde). Of the 29 SPAs, 12 can be considered of major importance for the conservation of meadow and wet-grassland bird conservation (Table 11).

However, in North Rhine-Westphalia, numerous meadow birds are also breeding in protected areas outside of SPAs. Redshanks and Black-tailed Godwits predominantly breed in SPAs, while Snipe and Curlew breed in significant numbers outside the SPAs, but in nature reserves. Especially for the curlew, it is important to consider conservation efforts beyond SPAs.

Table 11: SPAs important for wet-grassland bird conservation in the North Rhine-Westphalia.

SPA	SPA ID	Area (ha)
Bastauniederung	DE3618401	2,500
Feuchtwiesen im nördlichen Münsterland	DE3810401	1,560
Hellwegbörde	DE4415401	48,378
Heubachniederung, Lavesumer Bruch und Borkenberge	DE4108401	5,076

SPA	SPA ID	Area (ha)
Lippeaue zwischen Hamm und Lippstadt mit Ahsewiesen	DE4314401	2,301
Moore und Heiden des westlichen Münsterlandes	DE3807401	2,323
Rietberger Emsniederung mit Steinhorster Becken	DE4116401	928
Unterer Niederrhein	DE4203401	25,809
Düsterdieker Niederung	DE3612-401	2,684
Oppenweher Moor	DE3417471	471
Rieselfelder Münster	DE3911401	436
Wälder und Wiesen bei Burbach und Neunkirchen*	DE-5214401	4,654,600

*The SPA Wälder und Wiesen bei Burbach und Neunkirchen protects, among others, Whinchats at upland meadow birds. Occasionally, Snipe and Corncrake also breed there.

2. Management plans for protected areas

Management plans are being developed for all Special Protection Areas (SPAs) in North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW). Among the SPAs crucial for wet-grassland bird conservation, the two largest—Hellwegbörde and Unterer Niederrhein—along with Rieselfelder Münster, have management plans implemented by the NRW Ministry of Environment in 2015, 2011, and 2019, respectively.

As of September 2024, management plans for other SPAs, such as Lippeaue zwischen Hamm und Lippstadt mit Ahsewiesen, have either been drafted or are in the planning stages.

3. The European Common Agricultural Policy

The instrument implementing the CAP in NRW of relevance to wet grassland bird conservation is contractual nature conservation (Vertragsnaturschutz) described in the next chapter.

4. Agri-Environment-Climate Measures

The guidelines for Agri-Environment-Climate Measures in North Rhine-Westphalia for the funding period 2023-2027 were published in December 2022 and include a detailed description of the contractual nature conservation (Vertragsnaturschutz). Contractual nature conservation is deployed in three comprehensive groups of packages. Group 1 provides measures specific to arable land (in particular 5010, 5024, 5025, 5033), with specific measures for the conservation of agricultural birds. Group 2 provides measures specific to grasslands (5100 to 5550), and Group 3 provides measures for maintaining and replanting

orchards. We summarize in Table 12 the measures from Groups 1 and 2 that can directly or indirectly benefit the conservation of wet-grassland and meadow breeding birds, more specifically the 11 species included in this conservation plan.

The vast majority of available measures provide support to extensify the agricultural use of pastures and meadows. This includes limiting the use of pesticides and fertilizers, and providing longer periods of management restrictions. Further, the measures were adapted to an altitudinal gradient with 200m increments, adapted to the topography of NRW. No measures specifically provide support to creating or maintaining wet grasslands and shallow wet areas (e.g., ponds or vernal pools). Further information can be obtained directly from <https://www.landwirtschaftskammer.de> and <https://vns.naturschutzinformationen.nrw.de/vns/de/start>.

Table 12: Overview of the individual measures and funding rates for arable land, grassland, and pasture under the contractual nature conservation program (Vertragsnaturschutz) in North Rhine-Westphalia. Data source <https://www.landwirtschaftskammer.de>.

Reference	Measure	Description	Funding
5010	Extensive use of arable land for the protection of meadow flora	No pesticides (fungicidal seed treatments are permitted). No weed control of any kind. No growth regulators. No liquid organic fertilizers, caustic fertilizers, and sewage sludge. No mineral nitrogen fertilizers. No undersowing (Untersaaten). Cultivation of cereals, or another approved crops, at least three times during the commitment period. No possibility of rotation to other areas.	1,145 €/ha
5024	Leaving crop stubble standing (except maize)	Until 28.02 of following year. No herbicides use on the stubble fallow. No weed control of any kind.	250 €/ha
5025	Crop abandonment	Until 28.02 of following year. A max. of 0,5 ha.	2,240 €/ha
5033	Verzicht auf Insektizide und Rodentizide	keine Kombinationsmöglichkeit mit Paketen, die bereits einen Verzicht auf Pflanzenschutzmittel beinhalten	295 €/ha
5100	Conversion of arable land to grassland	In the case of self-sowing with preparatory soil cultivation or sowing with predetermined seed mixture a) in the first year, b) in the following years. By transferring mown seeds or sowing native	a) 615 €/ha b) 440 €/ha c) 2,040 €/ha d) 440 €/ha

Reference	Measure	Description	Funding
		or organic seed c) in the first year, d) in the following years.	
5121 to 5124	Grassland extensification without time-limited management restrictions	<p>No fertilizers or pesticides of any kind.</p> <p>No reseeding and no tillage.</p> <p>Usually no winter grazing (exceptions in individual cases).</p> <p>Compensations are different for different altitude areas. Up to 200m a.s.l. a) for grazing (5121), b) for mowing (5122). Over 200m a.s.l. c) for grazing (5123), d) for mowing (5124).</p>	<p>a) 470 €/ha</p> <p>b) 415 €/ha</p> <p>c) 345 €/ha</p> <p>d) 355 €/ha</p>
5131 to 5146	Extensive pasture use: Grassland extensification with time-limited management restrictions	<p>Grazing is compulsory.</p> <p>Two levels of extensification:</p> <p>Level 1: All year-round, no liquid organic fertilizers, poultry manure, fermented residues and N fertilizers, no pesticides. Grazing is restricted in areas up to 200m a.s.l. between 15.03 -15.06, a) with 2 Livestock Units, b) with 4 LU. In areas between 200m and 400m a.s.l. grazing is restricted between 01.04-01.07, and above 400m a.s.l. grazing is restricted between 1.04-15.07. For all areas above 200m a.s.l. c) 2 LU, d) 4 LU.</p> <p>Level 2: All year-round, no N-fertilizers, pesticides, and reseeding. Grazing is restricted in areas up to 200m a.s.l. between 15.03 -15.06, a) with 2 LU, b) with 4 LU. In areas between 200m and 400m a.s.l. grazing is restricted between 01.04-01.07, and above 400m a.s.l. grazing is restricted between 1.04-15.07. For all areas above 200m a.s.l. c) 2 LU, d) 4 LU.</p> <p>Allowed maintenance and fertilization measures must be completed before the first dates specified above.</p> <p>After the periods specified above, grazing, mowing and other allowed pasture maintenance measures can generally be carried out without restriction.</p> <p>In extensification level 1, the allowed amount of nitrogen is specified in kg/ha/year.</p> <p>On very small areas under 0.5 ha, 2 LU per area are allowed, and on 0.5 to 1 ha, 4 LU per area are allowed.</p>	<p>Level 1</p> <p>a) 675 €/ha</p> <p>b) 550 €/ha</p> <p>c) 410 €/ha</p> <p>d) 370 €/ha</p> <p>Level 2</p> <p>a) 710 €/ha</p> <p>b) 625 €/ha</p> <p>c) 490 €/ha</p> <p>d) 445 €/ha</p>

Reference	Measure	Description	Funding
5151 to 5168	Extensive meadow use: Grassland extensification with time-limited management restrictions	<p>Mowing is compulsory.</p> <p>Two levels of extensification:</p> <p>Level 1:</p> <p>All year round, no liquid organic fertilizers, poultry manure, fermentation residues and mineral N-fertilizers, and pesticides.</p> <p>Below 200m a.s.l. mowing restrictions:</p> <p>a) 15.03-20.05, b) 15.03-01.06, c) 15.03-15.06</p> <p>Between 200m and 400m a.s.l. mowing restrictions:</p> <p>d) 01.04-01.06, e) 01.04-15.06, f) 01.04-01.07</p> <p>Above 400m a.s.l. mowing restrictions:</p> <p>g) 01.04-15.06, h) 01.04-01.07, i) 01.04-15.07</p> <p>Level 2:</p> <p>All year-round, no N-fertilizers, pesticides, and reseeded.</p> <p>Below 200m a.s.l. mowing restrictions:</p> <p>a) 15.03-20.05, b) 15.03-01.06, c) 15.03-15.06</p> <p>Between 200m and 400m a.s.l. mowing restrictions:</p> <p>d) 01.04-01.06, e) 01.04-15.06, f) 01.04-01.07</p> <p>Above 400m a.s.l. mowing restrictions:</p> <p>d) 01.04-15.06, e) 01.04-01.07, f) 01.04-15.07</p> <p>Allowed management and fertilization measures must generally be completed before the dates given above.</p> <p>After the first mowing, subsequent grazing, mowing and other allowed management measures can generally be carried out without restriction.</p> <p>In extensification level 1, the permissible amount of nitrogen is set in kg/ha/year.</p>	<p>Level 1</p> <p>a) 550 €/ha</p> <p>b) 580 €/ha</p> <p>c) 610 €/ha</p> <p>d) 390 €/ha</p> <p>e) 410 €/ha</p> <p>f) 440 €/ha</p> <p>g) 390 €/ha</p> <p>h) 410 €/ha</p> <p>i) 440 €/ha</p> <p>Level</p> <p>a) 610 €/ha</p> <p>b) 650 €/ha</p> <p>c) 700 €/ha</p> <p>d) 450 €/ha</p> <p>e) 480 €/ha</p> <p>f) 520 €/ha</p> <p>g) 450 €/ha</p> <p>h) 480 €/ha</p> <p>i) 520 €/ha</p>
5170	Extensive year-round	At least 10 ha of continuous grazing area	560 €/ha

Reference	Measure	Description	Funding
	large-scale grazing projects	Grazing density max. 0.6 LU/ha No fertilization and pesticides No mechanical pasture care before June 15th (pasture care possible after this in prior coordination with the licensing authority) Supplementary feeding only in case of a lack of feed during the dormant period (among other things to comply with animal welfare regulations)	
5200	Biotope maintenance through grazing	No fertilization and no pesticides The type of grazing animal, stocking density and grazing period are based on nature conservation requirements and are determined on a case-by-case basis. No winter grazing on sites sensitive to trampling	620 €/ha
5210	Biotope maintenance through mowing	No fertilization and no pesticides Mowing times and other maintenance measures (including subsequent grazing) are based on nature conservation and biotope-specific requirements and are determined on a case-by-case basis. The cuttings are to be removed.	595 €/ha
5500	Use of goats for nature conservation reasons		70 €/ha
5510	Manual labor for mowing and/or collecting cuttings		1,290 €/ha
5520	Use of “gentle” mowing technology		130 €/ha
5530	Removal of unwanted woody vegetation for conservation in grassland biotopes		900 €/ha
5550	Second mowing from 15.09.		250 €/ha

5. Social and Political initiatives

In North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW), the Ministry of Environment initiated the Wet-Grassland Conservation Program (Feuchtwiesenschutzprogramm) in 1985. The program aimed to

protect extensive wet-grassland areas crucial for breeding birds in the Federal State's lowlands. As a result, 175 sites covering a total of 33,500 hectares were formally designated as nature conservation areas (Naturschutzgebiete) during the 1980s and 1990s.

Local biological stations were tasked with overseeing the management of these sites to support wet-grassland bird populations. Additionally, these stations, along with local conservation offices (Untere Naturschutzbehörden), implement various measures to raise public awareness about wet-grassland conservation in relevant Special Protection Areas (SPAs). These efforts include installing information boards, organizing public walks and talks, and distributing printed and web-based information.

In a 2021 evaluation analysis, 56% of the sites, encompassing 80% of the total surface area, were assessed. The findings revealed that only 50% of this area is in a condition suitable for the reproduction of wet-grassland breeding birds (Beckers et al. 2021). Beyond the areas currently managed under the wet-grassland conservation program, new initiatives are underway to develop and manage additional sites. These efforts are aimed at enhancing grassland bird conservation, including within designated EU bird sanctuaries.

6. LIFE-funded projects: development and implementation

LIFE-funded projects have been instrumental in implementing large-scale conservation measures across North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW). Since 2000, over 53 million Euros from LIFE-funded projects, with varying percentages of EU contributions, have been invested to enhance the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds and their habitats (see Table 13 for details).

Prior to 2000, several other significant projects also played a crucial role in shaping wet-grassland bird conservation. Notable among these are the Rieselfelder Münster project (1997-2000), the Moors and Heaths of Western Münsterland project (1998-2003), and the Ahsewiesen project (1999-2003).

These projects were developed and implemented by biological stations working in consortia, such as Rieselfelder Münster, Zwillbrock, Soest, Niederrhein, and Steinfurt, among others. Local nature conservation associations and the Federal State Agency for Nature, Environment, and Consumer Protection (LANUV) also played significant roles in these initiatives.

Measures implemented in these projects include land purchase, the rewetting of excessively drained wet-grasslands and wetlands, the optimization of meadow bird habitats, the management of predation, and the development of business models adapted to bird-friendly agriculture. The 11 target species included in this conservation plan are often the core species group for the vast majority of LIFE projects in NRW, most notably the Black-tailed Godwit, Lapwing, Curlew, Redshank, Snipe, Whinchat, and Corncrake.

Long-term strategies shaped the acquisition of LIFE projects in NRW, as shown in a recently published comprehensive overview of LIFE-funded projects and their impacts in North Rhine-Westphalia published by Jöbges *et al.* (2024). For example, the management plan 2011 for the Lower Rhine SPA (Unterer Niederrhein, (LANUV 2011)) guided the implementation of 5 successive LIFE-funded projects between 2009 and 2027 (Table 13,

LIFE07NAT/D/000232, LIFE08NAT/D/000010, LIFE08NAT/D/000007
LIFE11NAT/DE/000347 LIFE12NAT/DE/000133 & LIFE19NAT/DE/000816).

Table 13: LIFE-funded projects since 2000 that directly supported the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds in North Rhine-Westphalia.

Project reference	Title	Time frame	Budget (€)
LIFE00NAT/D/007042	Optimization of the SPA "Düsterdieker Niederung"	07.2001 – 04.2007	2,267,216
LIFE03NAT/D/000004	Regeneration of "Grosses Torfmoor"	07.2003 – 05.2008	1,800,400
LIFE07NAT/D/000232	Habitat optimisation in a local breeding population of Black-tailed Godwits in the NATURA 2000 site "NSG Hetter-Millinger Bruch, mit Erweiterung"	01.2009 – 12.2014	1,900,917
LIFE08NAT/D/000010	Improvement of the connection between the river and the floodplain within the pSCI "Lippe floodplain between Hangfort and Hamm"	03.2010 – 08.2015	6,011,951
LIFE08NAT/D/000007	Restoration of a side channel of the river Rhine near Wesel, Lower German Rhine	01.2010 – 12.2019	2,897,526
LIFE11NAT/DE/000347	Grassland for meadowbirds	09.2012 – 12.2025	12,328,702
LIFE12NAT/DE/000133	Rhine bend in Orsoy in the bird sanctuary "Lower Rhine Area"	10.2013 – 03.2018	3,203,242
LIFE19NAT/DE/000816	Breeding and migratory low wetland meadow birds in North-Rhine - Westphalia	10.2020 – 12.2027	18,941,146
LIFE20NAT/DE/001504	Siegerland's cultural and natural landscapes	01.2022 – 12.2027	4,177,980
Total		2001 – 2027	53,529,080

7. Clutch-and-chick protection

The protection of clutches of wet-grassland breeding birds from destruction by agricultural practices is a widespread measure in NRW implemented by many Biological Stations in cooperation with the farmers and supported by the local conservation offices (Untere Naturschutzbehörden), the state government and the Chamber of Agriculture (Landwirtschaftskammer). In addition, a number of non-governmental conservation groups such as NABU carry out this activity. It is, in most cases, aimed at safeguarding clutches of Lapwing, Curlew, Black-tailed Godwit and Redshank. For this, adult birds are observed in order to find the nests. The location of nests is then marked with sticks so that farmers

carrying out mowing or ploughing can avoid the nest. Cooperation with the land owner and the local farmer is essential for the success of this measure, mainly for species occurring primarily in agricultural fields. For example, NABU-Naturschutzstation Münsterland, one of the Biological Stations, marked 120 Lapwing nests in agricultural land in 2020 in the Warendorf district alone (source: presentation of NABU-Naturschutzstation Münsterland at the annual meeting of the AG Wiesenvogelschutz NRW 2021).

For nidifugous birds, the protection of chicks is much more difficult than the protection of clutches. A key measure is to ensure that sufficient area of habitat providing refuge and food for chicks is maintained close to the breeding sites. This is best achieved in large-scale conservation projects such as LIFE projects and through AECMs. In NRW, it is also possible to create annual “bird islands” in the fields, which provide shelter and food for Lapwing families.

8. Predation management

In recent years, the loss of clutches and chicks of wet-grassland breeding birds to predators has become more widespread. This has been confirmed in many cases by the use of nest cameras. Foxes are the main predator, followed by raccoons and various species of martens. Avian predators consisted mainly of marsh harrier and buzzard, and only in one location to date Carrion Crows *Corvus corone* had a significant predation effect.

Many wet-grassland bird conservation projects in the NRW lowlands, carried out by Biological Stations, include measures to protect clutches by erecting electric fences around the breeding sites. This has proven to prevent Foxes and Raccoons from entering the sites and predate nests. The AG Wiesenvogelschutz NRW – comprises the Federal State Bird Conservancy (Vogelschutzwarte) at LANUV, the Biological Stations working on wet grassland bird conservation, and the Nordrhein-Westfälische Ornithologengesellschaft – regularly discuss the advantages and challenges of using fences. This regular exchange allows for a better fine-tuning of this conservation practice.

The LIFE project Wiesenvögel NRW is currently implementing larger-scale predation management by trapping carnivorous predators, in particular Foxes and Raccoons, at several SPAs. This is coordinated by a professional hunter employed by the project and carried out by local hunters in cooperation with the Biological Stations that manage the project sites.

9. Monitoring

The population of wet-grassland breeding birds is monitored nearly annually by a network of Biological Stations and volunteers coordinated by the NRW Federal State Bird Conservancy. The species monitored are Black-tailed Godwit, Curlew, Redshank, and Snipe and in recent years also Lapwing, the latter at sites monitored for the other species. In several districts, Lapwing populations are comprehensively surveyed at regular intervals (usually every three years), so that a state-wide overview is available every three years. The NABU Münsterland Nature Conservation Station compiles this data. Annual population counts for the four wader species mentioned above are available since 2001. In addition,

state-wide surveys from the mid-1970s and the mid-1980s complement this data set (see, Jöbges et al. 2024).

Breeding success is monitored by Biological Stations, in the framework of protected area management and particular in the framework of the LIFE project Wiesenvögel NRW.

10. Public land management via contracts

The evaluation of the status of wet-grassland conservation sites in North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW), as stated in Beckers et al. (2021) revealed that 45% of the surface area across 93 wet-grassland conservation sites is publicly owned by the Federal State, local parishes, or foundations. This public ownership facilitates effective conservation-friendly management. The conservation status of these publicly owned sites is significantly better compared to privately-owned sites.

Contractual conservation (Vertragsnaturschutz) is widely implemented on publicly owned sites and, to a lesser extent, on privately owned sites. In Special Protection Areas (SPAs) and nature conservation sites (Naturschutzgebiete), contracted farmers are typically required to manage the land in a manner that supports meadow birds.

A key conclusion from the experience of wet-grassland conservation in NRW is that bird-friendly land management is more easily established and maintained on publicly owned sites. This is partly because establishing a suitable water regime is often challenging on private sites. Consequently, conservation efforts focus on transferring as much valuable land as possible into public ownership.

10 The Case of Bavaria

10.1 Populations and Trends

Of the 11 species covered by this conservation plan, only seven breed in Bavaria. The Oystercatcher, Golden Plover, Ruff, and Dunlin have not been recorded breeding in Bavaria. Table 14 presents the latest population status based on a statewide count from 2021 (Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt 2023). Additionally, it includes population counts from 2016, which were part of the Red List of Breeding Birds of Bavaria (Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt 2016). For Germany, the data is derived from the latest Red List of Birds published by Ryslavy et al. (2020). For Europe, data was derived from the European Red List of Birds 2021 compiled by BirdLife International (2021). The European Red List is based on 4 international assessments carried out in 1994, 2004, 2015, and 2021.

In the statewide meadow breeder mapping of 2021 (Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt 2023) counts were made to include a category of “possibly breeding (or category A)”, i.e. A one-time observation or detection of a bird singing (reproductive behavior) in a suitable habitat. These observations (category A) were not automatically included in the evaluation of territory and breeding pair numbers (based on categories B and C). The Corncrake is an exception, as it is challenging to provide evidence of confirmed breeding or suspected breeding status for this night-calling species, so the category of “possibly breeding (category A)” is also included in the evaluation.

Population trends are derived from the 2016 assessment and should be interpreted with caution in light of the most recent counts. For instance, the population trends of Whinchat in Bavaria are still subject to debate and a recent sharp decline in populations is observed locally, even if not sufficiently reflected in the trends established based on the population counts from 2016 (See Table 14). Figure 28 shows an example where the population of Whinchat declined by 64% in the last 24 years (1998-2021).

Table 14: Table showing the populations and population trends of the 11 species in Bavaria (BY), Germany (DE), and across Europe (Eur). The code color associated with the arrows indicates the gravity of population decrease: red and three downward arrows (↓↓↓) indicate a decrease of more than 50%, the yellow and two downward arrows (↓↓) indicate a decrease of more than 20%, light blue and equal sign (=) indicates a stable or slightly fluctuating population (decrease ≤ 20% or increase < 25%), and the upward arrow (↑) for an increase of 20% or more. Categories of the European Red List (Eur) are Least Concern (LC), Vulnerable (VU), and Near Threatened (NT).

Species	Population (breeding pairs)		Trends		
	2016	2021	BY**	DE	Eur
Corncrake <i>Crex crex</i>	300-400	106 (174)*	=	↓↓	LC
Eurasian Oystercatcher <i>Haematopus ostralegus</i>	0	0	–	↓↓	VU
Northern Lapwing <i>Vanellus vanellus</i>	6,000-9,500	2,155 (3,790)*	↓↓↓	↓↓↓	VU
European Golden Plover <i>Pluvialis apricaria</i>	0	0	–	=	LC
Eurasian Curlew <i>Numerius arquata</i>	489 (in 2014)	531 (558)*	↓↓↓	↓↓	NT
Black-tailed Godwit <i>Limosa limosa</i>	24	19	↓↓↓	↓↓↓	NT
Ruff <i>Philomachus pugnax</i> syn. <i>Calidris pugnax</i>	0	0	–	↓↓↓	NT
Dunlin <i>Calidris alpina</i>	0	0	–	=	LC
Common Snipe <i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	600-900	261 (351)*	↓↓↓	↓↓↓	VU
Common Redshank <i>Tringa totanus</i>	6 (in 2014)	11	↓↓↓	=	VU

Species	Population (breeding pairs)		Trends		
	Whinchat <i>Saxicola rubetra</i>	400-600	420 (587)*	↑***	↓↓↓

*Populations in parentheses include the category A “possibly breeding”, based on a one-time observation of birds singing in suitable habitat.

** Population trends are derived from the 2016 assessment and should be interpreted with caution in light of the most recent counts.

*** Trend subject to discussion, see text for details.

Figure 28: Figure showing the numbers of Whinchat breeding pairs from 1998 to 2021 in the Murnauer Moos, Bavaria. Data source: (Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt 2023).

10.2 Prevalent Conservation Practices and Instruments

1. Natura 2000 sites, SPAs, and other protected areas

The delimitation of areas of interest for wet-grassland and meadow breeding bird conservation in Bavaria was conducted in multiple stages.

The Wiesenbrüterkulisse (WBK), first published in 2010 then revised in 2018, established important areas for bird conservation in grasslands. This bird distribution mapping for WBK was based on two state-wide surveys conducted in 2006 and 2014/2015. The WBK constitutes, therefore, the basis for the monitoring, assessment, and planning of interventions in grasslands and it initially included 629 breeding areas. The relative proportion of grassland is an important criterion in the selection of these areas, and was established at a 25% threshold. All areas included in the WBK have 25% or more of their surface area categorized as grasslands. Further, the identification of the 629 areas provided a spatial framework for monitoring grassland bird populations.

The Feldvogelkulisse 2020 (FVK) established important areas used by wet-grassland and meadow breeding birds in agricultural landscapes. As a first step in establishing a state-

wide network of FVK, a mapping of important areas for the Lapwing was conducted. Further species are to be included in the FVK selection, including the Partridge, Ortolan, Corn Bunting, Skylark, Quail, and Wagtail. Within the FVK, conservation measures can be adapted to specific species and thus contribute to more efficient protection of birds in agricultural landscapes. By differentiating areas dominated by grasslands and areas dominated by arable land, measures can be more specifically tailored to the needs of species of their respective habitats. The FVK Lapwing 2020 currently comprises 533 areas having a permanent grassland share below 25%. It is important to mention that the delineation of bird areas as FVK aims to promote functional connectivity between habitats for feeding, resting, and breeding. A minimum of three breeding pairs is necessary to consider an area in the FVK, and the minimum habitat for breeding pairs is established at five hectares. In fewer individual cases, smaller areas can also be included.

The latest (2021) mapping of areas important for wet-grassland and meadow bird conservation in Bavaria was based on the previously delineated areas WKB 2018 and FVK 2020, and included an additional 275 WKB and 11 recently identified. In total, 1,448 areas considered important for wet-grassland and meadow breeding birds (Figure 29) constitute the spatial framework for bird conservation in Bavaria.

Figure 29: Map showing the distribution Wiesenbrüterkulisse (WBK) and Feldvogelkulisse (FVK) across Bavaria. WBK and FVK constitute the spatial framework for wet-grassland and meadow bird conservation in Bavaria.

The most important wet-grassland and meadow bird breeding areas in Bavaria have been designated as European bird sanctuaries (SPAs). These areas are designated with the objective to preserve and restore the favorable conservation status of bird species in all or parts of the areas, with clear objectives listed for each SPA. The vast majority of SPAs overlap with WBK. However, a recent evaluation (Delany et al. 2009a; Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt 2023) of meadow bird breeding populations in SPAs shows that the majority of goals have not been achieved so far, with an overall decline in the population of many species.

2. Management Plans for Protected Areas

The Bavarian Natura 2000 Ordinance (in force since 1.4.2016) contains the conservation objectives for SPAs and for site boundaries. This ordinance replaced the original Bavarian Bird Protection Ordinance (VoGEV, 12 July 2006). The ordinance contains the respective conservation objectives for SPAs, the area boundaries defined at the scale of the cadastral map, as well as the conservation objectives specified for each area. Management plans are prepared for each site in this framework clearly identifying the measures required to maintain and restore a favorable conservation status for bird species. The management plans for Natura 2000 sites are binding for the Bavarian Free State authorities.

The management plans for SPAs relevant to wet-grassland and meadow breeding birds are almost completely available in Bavaria (only few are missing in the administrative district of Upper Bavaria). It is, therefore, a priority to implement these plans to recover bird populations.

Management plans do not impose any obligations on private landowners and land users, however, there is a prohibition of deterioration according to §§ 33 and 34 BNatSchG (Bürgerservice - BayNat2000V: § 4 Managementplanung (gesetze-bayern.de)). The forecast of future deterioration due to planned or intended measures is examined and assessed on a case-by-case by the competent authorities.

3. The European Common Agricultural Policy

According to the German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL), more than half of the existing European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) funds are to be spent on the topics of biodiversity, environment, and climate in the future, and this should be reflected in Bavaria. As of May 2024, the funding priorities and budgets under EAFRD for the new funding period were not publicly available. We provide below an overview of EAFRD funding for 2014-2022.

From 2014 to 2020, Bavaria received funding totaling around 1,516 billion euros from the EAFRD. With the EU's decision to extend the funding period until 2022, the funds were supplemented by 504.8 million euros in EAFRD and redeployment funds from the first pillar. In addition, 114.5 million euros were made available from the “European Union Recovery Instrument to Support Recovery after the COVID-19 Crisis” (EURI), bringing the total volume of EAFRD funds available in Bavaria for the 2014 - 2022 period to 2,135 billion euros.

Together with state co-financing, almost 4,9 billion euros were available for nine years to promote agriculture and the food industry, maintain and improve ecosystems and increase the economic and social attractiveness of rural areas. These funds have played a crucial role in supporting the conservation of meadows and wet-grasslands, contributing positively to the habitats of bird communities.

The following measures were programmed in the development plan for rural areas in Bavaria 2014–2020:

Priority 2: economic performance of agricultural farms:

- Agricultural Investment Promotion Program (AFP)
- European Innovation Partnership Agri (EIP)

Priority 4: biological diversity, water and soil quality

- Cultural landscape program (KULAP, partly)
- Contractual Nature Conservation Program (VNP) under the responsibility of the StMUV
- Organic farming
- Compensatory allowance (AGZ)

Priority 5: Resource efficiency and climate protection

- Promotion of market structure
- Cultural landscape program (KULAP, partly)

Priority 6: Economic and social development in rural areas

- Diversification of agricultural businesses
- Basic services and village renewal in rural areas
- LEADERS

4. Agri-Environment-Climate Measures

The offices for food, agriculture and forestry (Ämter für Ernährung, Landwirtschaft und Forsten) are responsible for implementing the funding instruments for the Contractual Nature Conservation Program (VNP) and the Cultural Landscape Program (KULAP), including compensation measures. The political, technical, and financial responsibilities for the KULAP lie with the State Ministry of Food, Agriculture, and Forestry, and for the VNP including compensation measures, with the State Ministry of the Environment and Consumer Protection. Additionally, the Free State of Bavaria actively promotes landscape maintenance measures for open land. These measures significantly contribute to the preservation and improvement of habitats for meadow birds and are an integral part of Bavaria's nature conservation strategy.

Contractual nature conservation program including compensation measures (VNP)

The Contractual Nature Conservation Program (VNP) of the Free State of Bavaria plays a central role in the protection of meadow birds. It is designed to secure and improve the sustainable performance of ecosystems and to preserve the habitats and communities of native flora and fauna. Specifically, through the VNP Meadows, targeted measures are implemented to promote habitats for meadow birds such as the Eurasian Curlew and the Northern Lapwing. Bavaria invests around 90 million euros annually in this program, underscoring the importance and commitment of the Free State to nature conservation. Thus, compensation measures are granted to support nature conservation and landscape management, and nature-friendly and sustainable agricultural and forestry management of legally protected biotope areas. In 2023, VNP measures were implemented on around 160,000 hectares of agricultural land (Figure 30). For this purpose, Bavaria, with the support of the European Union, paid around 90 million euros annually to 28,000 beneficiaries. The

focus of the measures was on the ecologically value of grasslands. The evaluation of this programs shows overall that biodiversity and/or the number of Red List species on VNP areas were significantly increased. The distribution of VNP areas across the individual biotope types (as of 2023) are: Arable land 5%, Ponds 1%, Pastures 27%, Meadows 67%.

Figure 30: Overall annual increase of areas benefiting from NVP support in Bavaria. Source <https://www.stmuv.bayern.de>.

In Table 15, we provide a quick overview of individual measures and funding rates per biotope categorized as arable land (Acker), grassland (Wiesen), and pastures (Weiden). For ponds (Teiche) please refer to www.stmelf.bayern.de for further information. The measures presented here can directly or indirectly benefit the conservation of wet-grassland and meadow bird species. Currently, the conversion from arable land to permanent grassland is subsidized at 3,300 €/ha (Table 15: G18).

Table 15: Overview of the individual measures and funding rates for arable land, grassland, and pasture under the Contractual nature conservation program (VNP) in Bavaria. Data source www.stmelf.bayern.de, 20.01.2023.

	Code	Measures	Funding
Arable land	G11	Extensive use of arable land for field breeders and wild herbs	530 €/ha
	G12	Fallowing on arable land with self-vegetation for species conservation reasons; Rest period 16.03 up to and including 31.08; Arable land: EMZ ¹ up to 6500	500 €/ha
	G13	Fallowing on arable land with self-vegetation for reasons of species protection; Rest period 16.03 up to and including 31.08; Arable land: EMZ from 6501	750 €/ha
	P11	No fertilization of any kind	190 €/ha
	P12	No mineral fertilizers, organic fertilizers (except solid manure)	150 €/ha

	Code	Measures	Funding
	Q01	Reduced seeding density	90 €/ha
	Q03	Cultivation unit max. 0,5 ha	60 €/ha
	Q04	Cultivation unit max. 0,3 ha	175 €/ha
	Q05	Stubble fallow for cereals	130 €/ha
	Q06	Annual cultivation in the fall	30 €/ha
	Q22	Annual cultivation in spring	30 €/ha
	Q07	Preservation of orchard trees	12 €/tree
	Q23	Partial crop abandonment	95 €/ha
	Q24	“Lark window” (Lerchenfenster)	50 €/ha
Grassland	G20	Conversion of arable land to grassland	400 €/ha
	G18	Permanent conversion of arable land to grassland on moorland sites	3,300 €/ha
	G/D21	Extensive mowing of habitats of nature conservation value - mowing date 01.06.	260 €/ha
	G/D/E22	Extensive mowing of habitats of nature conservation value - mowing date 15.06.	325 €/ha
	G/D/E23	Extensive mowing of habitats of nature conservation value - mowing date 01.07.	370 €/ha
	G/D/E19	Extensive mowing of habitats of nature conservation value - mowing date 15.07.	420 €/ha
	G/E24	Extensive mowing of habitats of nature conservation value - mowing date 01.08.	430 €/ha
	G/E25	Extensive mowing of habitats of nature conservation value - mowing date 01.09.	450 €/ha
	G/D26	Extensive mowing of habitats of nature conservation value - mowing up to and including 14.06., no mowing up to and including 31.08.	420 €/ha
	G29	Fallowing of meadows for reasons of species protection - no cultivation from 16.03. up to and including 01.08.	350 €/ha
	G/D30	Result-oriented grassland use Conservation of 6 indicator species	340 €/ha
	P21	No fertilization of any kind	150 €/ha
	G27	No fertilization of any kind - individual performance	360 €/ha
	P22	No mineral fertilizers, organic fertilizers (except solid manure)	120 €/ha
	P23	Maintenance fertilization for nature conservation reasons in the first year	120 €/ha

	Code	Measures	Funding
	Q03	Management unit max. 0,5 ha	60 €/ha
	Q04	Cultivation unit max. 0,3 ha	175 €/ha
	Q07/G28	Preservation of orchard trees	12 €/tree
	Q08	Use of blade mower	140 €/ha
	Q09	Special machine for mowing	150 €/ha
	Q10	Use of motorized mower	290 €/ha
	Q11	Manual mowing	700 €/ha
	Q25	Difficult removal of cuttings	100 €/ha
	Q12	Raking by hand	240 €/ha
	Q13	Additional cutting	120 €/ha
	Q14	Old grass cut to 5 - 20 %	80 €/ha
	Q34	Old grass to 5 - 20 % in EA/E	80 €/ha
	Q15	Moisture surcharge	80 €/ha
	Q26	Surcharge for high-yielding locations	80 €/ha
	Q17	Rest period from 16.03.	40 €/ha
Q27	Rest period from 01.04.	30 €/ha	
Pasture	G/D31	Extensive pasture use (sheep, cattle including water buffalo, horses including donkeys or camels)	440 €/ha
	G/D31	Extensive pasture use in combination with KULAP B/O10	340 €/ha
	G/D32	Grazing by cattle on alpine pastures/alps	180 €/ha
	G/D33	Grazing by goats	590 €/ha
	G/D33	Grazing by goats in combination with KULAP B/O10	490 €/ha
	Q07	Preservation of scattered fruit trees	12 €/tree
	Q18	Grazing with goats	70 €/ha
	Q19	Management unit max. 2 ha or more difficult grazing	100 €/ha
	Q28	Supplement for undeveloped mountain pastures/alpine pastures	20 €/ha

Cultural Landscape Program (KULAP)

With the Cultural Landscape Program, Bavaria has been granting farmers compensation payments for voluntary environmentally friendly farming measures since 1988. The new cultural landscape program is divided into measures for grassland, arable land, and special areas, such as special crops or pond farming. KULAP has the mission to further develop with

additional measures for water, soil, and climate protection as well as for the promotion of biodiversity and the preservation of the cultural landscape. A wide range of possible funding combinations - including with the newly introduced voluntary organic schemes in the first pillar of the Common Agricultural Policy - ensure that tailored solutions are possible for a wide range of farm types and practices.

The new KULAP is flanked by further agri-environmental and animal welfare measures. Specifically, these are the promotion of organic farming and measures for peatland conservation farming ("Peatland Farming Program").

- Promotion of organic farming

In line with the Free State's goal of farming 30% of land in Bavaria organically by 2030, organic farming will continue to receive strong support. This is reflected in the new premium rates as well as in the large number of possible combinations with measures of the KULAP. The support rewards for example the management of the entire farm in accordance with the principles of organic farming, and increased support is granted in the first two years of conversion.

- Peatland farming program

By rewarding the conversion from arable to permanent grassland, Bavaria provides the first cornerstone of its "Peatland Farming Program" in 2023. Further measures are still being developed. They will reward the wet use of grasslands as well as the cultivation of paludicultures. Currently, the only funding that allow the conversion from arable land to permanent grassland is included in the VNP, G18 (Table 8).

In Table 16 we summarize the main individual measures and funding rates for grasslands and arable land funded under the instrument KULAP. Further information on the different funding instruments within the KULAP framework can be found here: <https://www.stmelf.bayern.de/foerderung/foerderung-von-agrarumweltmassnahmen-in-bayern/index.html>.

Table 16: Overview of the individual measures and funding rates implemented in Bavaria for grassland and agricultural land that can directly or indirectly benefit wet-grassland and meadow bird conservation. Data source www.stmelf.bayern.de, 20.01.2023.

	Code	Measures	Funding
Grassland	K10	Extensive grassland use (1 GV/ha HFF)	110 €/ha
	K12	Extensive forage production	100 €/ha
	K14	Insect-friendly mowing	60 €/ha
	K16	Extensive grassland use. Mowing date June 15	320 €/ha
	K17	Extensive grassland use. Mowing date July 1	370 €/ha
	K18	Extensive grassland uses in sensitive areas	350 €/ha
	K20	Mowing of steep slope meadows level 1	450 €/ha
	K20	Mowing of steep slope meadows level 2	650 €/ha

	Code	Measures	Funding
	K22	Management of mountain and alpine pastures	80 €/ha
Arable land	K30	Diverse crop rotations with large-grain legumes	60 €/ha
	K31	Diverse crop rotations with old crops	85 €/ha
	K32	Diverse crop rotations with flowering crops	115 €/ha
	K33	Diverse crop rotations to maintain humus	340 €/ha
	K34	Diverse crop rotations to improve the soil structure	95 €/ha
	K40	No herbicides for winter cereals/winter oilseed rape	100 €/ha
	K42	Avoidance of synthetic chemical pesticides for winter cereals/winter oilseed rape	200 €/ha
	K44	Avoidance of intensive crops	250 €/ha
	K46	Conservation sowing methods	80 €/ha
	K48	Winter greening with wildlife-friendly seeds	80 €/ha
	K50	Erosion control strips	800 €/ha
	K51	Biodiversity strips	800 €/ha
	K52	Wild plant mixtures	450 €/ha
	K54	Use of <i>Trichogramma</i> wasp for maize	50 €/ha
	K56	Perennial flowering areas EMZ ⁱ < 3.500	400 €/ha
	K56	Perennial flowering areas EMZ 3.501 to 4.500	550 €/ha
	K56	Perennial flowering areas EMZ 4.501 to 5.500	700 €/ha
	K56	Perennial flowering areas EMZ 5.501 to 6.500	900 €/ha
	K56	Perennial flowering areas EMZ > 6.500	1,100 €/ha
	K58	Conversion from arable land to grassland	400 €/ha
K60	Field bird islands	680 €/ha	
K61	Delayed sowing	500 €/ha	

i: The yield measurement number (EMZ) is the result of the soil estimation (BodSchätzG) for agriculturally usable land.

5. Social and Political initiatives

Social and political initiatives in Bavaria are multiple. We present here only a few of the most relevant that made significant impacts on grassland ecosystem biodiversity in general and on meadow bird communities more specifically.

The referendum “Biodiversity and natural beauty in Bavaria – Save the bees”: by far, this was the most successful social initiatives in the history of the Free State of Bavaria: over 1.7 million eligible voters (18.4% of eligible voters) participated it in their town halls from

January 31st to February 13th, 2019. The citizens' vote was an expression of an obvious social expectation to halt the loss of biodiversity in Bavaria and to consistently protect it (see, www.volksbegehren-artenvielfalt.de). This initiative aimed to address various factors impacting biodiversity in Bavaria, promoting sustainable practices and enhancing the conservation of biodiversity through comprehensive measures. Those same drivers are behind the decline of meadow bird populations, and therefore, this biodiversity initiative was also beneficial to the conservation of meadow birds.

The core demands of the referendum include the massive expansion of organic farming, the maintenance of riparian strips on water bodies, the conversion of ten percent of Bavarian grassland into flowering meadows and the pesticide-free management of Free State's land. The draft law aims to open up new opportunities, especially for small and medium-sized agricultural businesses. On July 17, 2019, the legislative package consisting of the referendum law and the supplementary law was passed in the Bavarian Free State parliament. In 2020, the project group at the Nürtingen-Geislingen University of Economics and Environment derived 32 indicators from the over 80 measures adopted and anchored in law.

The effects of the referendum and the measures implemented since 2019 are gradually having an impact in some areas. For example, the creation of new orchards and agro-environmental measures such as flowering areas and extensive grassland as well as the optimization of support programs for grazing livestock farmers. The subsidized areas increased in 2022 and an increase in the premiums used was recorded. The use of total herbicides on Free State's public land was further reduced and the remaining small quantities for scientific experimentation should be further minimized in the future. However, the leased areas for which we have no data are problematic. Despite a steady increase in "late mowing" measures funded via the Contractual Nature Conservation Program (VNP) and KULAP, the percentage of 9.06% (assessment done before 2020) was still just below the target value of 10%. Further information can be found in the yearly monitoring reports www.volksbegehren-artenvielfalt.de/monitoring/.

The meadow breeder advisors (Wiesenbrüterberater): In 2013, the Meadow Breeders Species Assistance Program (AHP) was launched to protect and preserve meadow breeders. The meadow breeder agenda followed in 2015, as a further pillar of meadow breeder protection in Bavaria (the agenda can be obtained here: www.bestellen.bayern.de). The meadow breeder agenda is a comprehensive overview of the findings from 30 years of meadow breeding bird protection in Bavaria. In addition to a thorough analysis of the distribution of populations of specific species in Bavaria, concrete measures are proposed to protect meadow birds. The meadow breeder agenda serves, therefore, as guidelines for the implementation of the AHP. In this agenda, particular importance is attached to committed and intensive area support, which is to be carried out by the so-called "meadow breeder advisors".

An important task of these advisors is to protect the habitat of the meadow breeding birds and, where necessary, improve it. These advisors work on solutions, together with the land managers, to create optimal conditions for both birds and land managers. Since the nature-friendly and species-appropriate management of wet meadows is often not easy, the advisors also inform the farmers on suitable compensation, support programs, and subsidies. These advisors work on a voluntary basis, which means that their commitment, the amount of time they invest in these tasks, and their professional background vary greatly.

Since 2017, the meadow breeder advisors have been trained in multi-day courses by the Bavarian Academy for Nature Conservation and Landscape Management in cooperation with the Bavarian State Office for the Environment. The main tasks of the meadow breeder advisors are:

- Technical contact on site
- Technical advice in cooperation with the nature conservation authorities
- Involvement of farmers in meadow breeding areas as partners in nature conservation
- Assessment of the impairment of meadow breeding areas
- Initiation of area-related protection concepts and participation in their preparation and implementation
- Recording of brood stocks and breeding success as a basis for decision-making for protective measures
- Guiding visitors and educating the local population
- Provide further background information

6. LIFE-funded Projects: Development and Implementation

LIFE projects relevant for wet-grassland and meadow birds are few in Bavaria. The extensive application process and the difficulty to secure co-funding are the main hurdles to develop substantial LIFE projects for the conservation of meadow birds.

The Swabian Danube valley (LIFE06 NAT/D/000006, Schwäbisches Donautal) LIFE Nature Project (01.10.2006-31.07.2011, total budget 2,037,040 Euro). The project goals were the sustainable protection of the Donaured's bird sanctuary (SPA) by enhancing the sustainable use of grassland, the creation of wet-grasslands and wetlands, the improvement of wet habitats, and targeted public relations to limit the impact of visitor disturbances. In addition, the measures implemented were aimed to provide natural flood protection. The project area covered around 7,400 hectares and was divided into the sub-areas Donaumoos, Eppisburger Ried, Eastern Donaured, Eastern Donauauen and Mertinger Ried.

The project was supported by the Bavarian State Ministry for the Environment and Health, managed by Donautal-Aktiv e.V. and in the Donaumoos sub-area by ARGE Schwäbisches Donaumoos e.V. The project was 50% financed by funds from the European Union.

The main projected activities were to create open wet-grasslands as well as wet depressions and to open the landscape by removing vertical obstacles. The main actions involved: The purchase of 24 ha and the creation of suitable wet habitats (flooding areas, shallow ponds) on 35 ha. Within a second focal point "ditches" measures were carried to improve their hydrology and their suitability as foraging habitat (e.g., flattening of banks), and were implemented on 31 km. Finally, a public relations' campaign was carried out in order to gain support for the protection of vulnerable areas and to inform the public about the project. Various other PR measures were carried out including the development of educational trails, observation posts, information boards, and leaflets and guided tours.

Another LIFE-funded project targeting the conservation of Corncrake *Crex crex* was conducted in Südlichen Chiemgau. The project "Hochmoore und Lebensräume des Wachtelkönigs im Südlichen Chiemgau" was conducted over a period of 42 months (1997-

2001; 1,510,000 Euro), with the Landkreis Traunstein, Oberbayern, as main beneficiary. In total, 2,700 ha of habitat were optimized for the Corncrake including, the renaturation of raised bogs, the optimization and expansion of meadow breeding areas, and water retention through extensive moorland restoration measures.

7. Clutch-and-chick Protection

To protect nests and chicks from mowing, late mowing dates have been agreed on in many meadows in important breeding areas (15 June/1 July/15 July; via VNP or lease agreements with public land). In the case of meadows that are to be mown earlier, mowing can also be postponed if necessary (e.g., clutch or chicks on this field) by means of individual agreements and compensation payments. However, there is currently no Bavaria-wide regulation for this practice. In many districts, these payments are made via "Kleinstmaßnahmen" by the district office (or they are implemented in local projects) and the amount of the compensation payment is based on the VNP.

Close cooperation with farmers and effective monitoring on site are essential for the protection of nests and chicks during mowing activities. Efforts are being made to ensure adequate resources and staff to support these conservation activities. The data from Curlew chicks monitoring with radio telemetry transmitters show a large movement radius, especially when chicks are older than 3 weeks. This is often the time of year when hay is mowed. Therefore, it is likely, that there are significant losses due to mowing every year, especially when there is not enough capacity for monitoring (often needed on a daily basis).

In some areas, the agricultural land is very fragmented and many different farmers mow a relatively small area. In theory, this can be considered positive for a structural mosaic, but it poses a major challenge when it comes to mowing management.

Clutch protection fences are used in many different Wiesenbrütergebieten in Bavaria. In most cases they are used to protect Curlew breeding areas but are also increasingly being used to protect Lapwings. These are organized and financed differently in the various areas. Some are part of projects of landscape conservation associations (LPVs), nature conservation associations such as the LBV (Landesbund für Vogel- und Naturschutz in Bayern) or BN (Bund Naturschutz in Bayern) or they are organized directly by the lower nature conservation authorities.

The fences usually have a radius of 10-20 meters and consist of electric strand fences or sheep fences. They are often set up and supervised by volunteers. Area managers (Gebietsbetreuer) also play an important role here (see, <https://gebietsbetreuung.bayern/>). There are several area managers specifically responsible for the protection of meadow breeding birds (e.g., "Altmühlfranken" or "Wiesenbrüter im Donautal"). They very often carry out practical nature conservation work, such as monitoring and fencing in these areas and have very close contact with local farmers and authorities.

The Landesbund für Vogel- und Naturschutz has analyzed the hatching rates in two project areas Altmühltal and Donaumoos in 2022 and 2023 (Figure 31). All nests were located within small or large-scale protective fences. In conclusion, the results showed that clutch-protection fences can successfully protect the nests from predation (hatching rate of

71%, predated eggs 15.5%). However, the chicks are often predated after leaving the nest and fenced area.

Figure 31: Diagram showing the hatched and predated percentages of egg in the Altmühltal and Donaumoos in 2022 and 2023, where electric strand fences have been deployed to protect nests.

In some areas there are single or even several large-scale electric fences (10 ha - 90 ha). They are initiated and supported by local projects and initiatives, but there is no coordinated approach across Bavaria. These fences protect not only the nests but also the chicks. Therefore, attractive habitat within the fence is a prerequisite for success, otherwise the families will simply leave the fenced area. Large fences are currently being used in at least 12 districts. Most fences consist of 5-8 strands, but large fences made of poultry fencing have recently been used in one area with very good results so far. There are no permanent fences in Bavaria yet (as in the Wetterau in Hessen).

8. Predation Management

To date, there is no standardized concept for predation management in Bavaria. Habitat-improving measures focusing on predation avoidance are implemented in many areas through local projects and initiatives (e.g. scrub clearance). As described above, electric safety fences are used in few districts. In some areas, cooperation with the local hunting community is being expanded. For example, some fox traps are being financed. This is also organized through individual, local projects. To date, the success of these initiatives is heavily dependent on the motivation and implication of local hunters. No shooting premiums

are currently being paid and so far, and there are no professional hunters in meadow breeding areas in Bavaria. Efforts are ongoing to explore additional measures and support systems to enhance predation management in meadow breeding areas. Further, there is no coordinated evaluation of these measures to date. The LfU is expected to conduct a study on predation management in 2024 and 2025. This will certainly include a presentation and evaluation of the measures taken to date.

9. Monitoring

The monitoring of wet-grassland and meadow bird populations in Bavaria is conducted in the framework of the WBK and VFK established in grasslands and agricultural land, respectively, (see above, section 1). Monitoring is conducted by a combination of volunteer work, project-related monitoring, and contractual work.

The latest monitoring conducted in 2021 (7th state-wide monitoring) encompassed 820 breeding areas. In 51.7% (424 areas) of those, no breeding birds were detected. This number is an increase from the monitoring conducted in 2014/2015 where only 43.6% areas had no breeding birds. However, this only constitutes an overall monitoring of breeding birds, and the development of breeding populations of specific species needs to be considered separately. Further information on specific species can be found in the Landesweite Wiesenbrüterkartierung in Bayern 2021 - Bestand, Trends und Ursachenanalyse (Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt 2023).

In addition to this Bavaria-wide coordinated monitoring, the populations in almost all relevant areas for wet-grassland breeding birds are surveyed (often) annually by local projects or volunteers. This data is currently not collected or centralized systematically, but the projects are often required to report their data to the state's species database. These projects are carried out by the districts, nature conservation organisations, LPVs or on a voluntary basis.

The LBV is also tagging Curlew chicks (radiotelemetry) as part of local projects to find out more about habitat utilisation and predation risk. This has already been carried out in four project areas. Results or details about these projects can be obtained directly from the LBV. From 2017-2024, the LBV also tagged more than 40 Curlews with GPS transmitters (adults and juveniles). The aim is to investigate the habitat use in the breeding area, the behaviour and breeding site selection of Curlews in the 3rd year of life and the migration routes and wintering areas of Bavarian Curlews.

10. Public Land Management via Contracts

In Bavaria, the protection of wet-grassland and meadow breeding birds is voluntary. Only in the case of compensation areas or areas purchased for nature conservation (that belong to the LBV, for example) are there obligations via the lease agreements.

Since the mid-1980s, the number of compensation and replacement areas as well as areas purchased for nature conservation purposes has increased steadily. A database was created by LfU (Das Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt) in order to have a state-wide overview of ecologically important areas. This effort was initiated when the Bavarian Nature

Conservation Act was amended in 1998, and the LfU was given the task of setting up and maintaining a register of “ecologically significant areas”. This is how the “Bavarian Ecological Area Cadastre” (ÖFK) was created. The cadaster is publicly available here: https://www.lfu.bayern.de/natur/oefka_oeko/oekoflaechenkataster/index.htm, Figure 32. While the cadaster provides valuable information that is made public, the voluntary participation and update of information on the platform can somehow be limiting.

Figure 32: Example of data available on the Bavarian Ecological Area Cadaster (website provided above). The figure shows the distribution of SPAs (VSG) in green delineation, and in the pink the “Ecological land register (purchase)” that includes areas purchased or leased for nature conservation. Data extracted in May 2024.

11 Current Status and Future Perspectives for Wet-grassland Breeding Birds Conservation in Germany: A Horizon Scanning Approach

We present here the results of an extensive Horizon Scanning survey (HS) carried out across Germany in 2023, specifically aimed at the broad and diverse community of nature-conservation practitioners active in wet-grassland and wetland bird conservation. We conducted the HS to identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats for wet-grassland breeding bird conservation. HS has become an important tool for conservation

practitioners, policy makers, and scientists to prioritize management or research efforts and identify new areas of inquiry (Sutherland et al. 2011; Sutherland and Woodroof 2009).

We conducted the HS online using www.surveymonkey.com, and included nine questions in total.

In the first five questions, we asked participants to:

- 1) Identify themselves;
- 2) Provide the geographical extent of their expertise in four categories (Schleswig Holstein and Hamburg, Lower Saxony and Bremen, North Rhine-Westphalia, and the continental biogeographic region of Germany). The first three categories represent Federal States in the Atlantic biogeographic region of Germany where the main populations of wet-grassland breeding birds occur.
- 3) Describe their main field of activity in one of the eight pre-set answers (Conservation, Land Management, Agriculture, Rice farming, Research, Monitoring, Environmental policy, Education and capacity building);
- 4) Describe their main expertise in one of the seven pre-set answers (Ornithology, Wetland and wet-grassland ecology, Flyway ecology, Agriculture, Rice farming, Social ecology, Environmental economics);
- 5) Self-identify their level of expertise in three categories (Beginner, Intermediate, Advanced).

In questions 3 and 4, the participant had also the opportunity to provide write-in answers not provided in the questionnaire.

The final four questions (Questions 6 to 9) asked participants to share their perspectives on the **strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats** related to wet-grassland bird conservation within their respective areas of geographical expertise. We asked participants to provide answers in the format of their choice, as an essay, independent sentences, or bullet points. We conducted the HS during 6 months and the participants had the opportunity to provide their answers in German or English.

After the 6-month period, we analyzed the data, synthesized the various perspectives, and summarized the results in a cohesive text that reflects the participants' opinions and wording. The results were shared online with all participants, who had the opportunity to comment and amend the text. Additionally, a workshop was organized for each of the four geographic areas to address any remaining issues and finalize the text, which is presented in this conservation plan.

A total of 76 participants took part in this HS survey, distributed as follows: 33 from Lower Saxony and Bremen, 13 from North Rhine-Westphalia, 8 from Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg, and 22 from the Federal States in the Atlantic biogeographic region of Germany. Figure 33 illustrates the profile of the participants. The majority identified as working in nature conservation, followed by monitoring, agriculture, land management, environmental policy, and research. Participants' primary areas of expertise included ornithology, wetland and wet-grassland ecology, agriculture, and flyway ecology. Finally, most participants self-identified as having advanced expertise in their respective fields.

Figure 33: Diagrams showing the relative distribution of the 76 participants in the HS conducted in Germany.

The results of this HS survey were published in *Frontiers in Conservation Science*, an open access journal (Maasri et al. 2023), avoiding any paywall and making the results most accessible. The list of participants is provided in this report as Appendix 1. The full answers for the survey in Germany are provided in English and German as appendix in Maasri et al. (2023).

For each geographical area, the HS results will be presented in two distinct sections: Current Status and Future Perspectives. The Current Status section will summarize the strengths and weaknesses, while the Future Perspectives section will outline the threats and opportunities.

11.1 Lower Saxony and Bremen

In total, 33 participants took part in the survey for Lower Saxony and Bremen. The majority were active in nature conservation (22 participants), followed by agriculture (4), landscape planning (3), and monitoring (3) (Figure 34). The participants declared having expertise in Ornithology (17), ecology of wetlands and wet grasslands (9), agriculture (5), providing nature conservation guidance and advice to farmers (1), implementing compensation measures (1), and management of conservation areas (1). Further, the vast majority of participants identified their level of expertise as advanced.

Figure 34: Diagrams showing the distribution of responses to Q2: What is your main field of activity? and Q3: what is your main expertise? Number of participants 33.

Current status:

Strengths – Lower Saxony and Bremen benefit from an extensive network of actors involved in wet-grassland breeding bird conservation, including nature conservation district authorities (Landkreise Untere Naturschutzbehörde (UNB)), the Lower Saxon Department for Water, Coastal and Nature Conservation (NLWKN), biological stations (Biologische Stationen), and nature conservation associations (Naturschutzverbände). Further, the two Federal States benefit from a great public interest in bird conservation with many active associations advocating for nature-aware tourism.

Lower Saxony benefits from relatively large unfragmented areas of adequate habitat, including fen marshes, lowland moors, and coastal marshes. Additionally, island polders of the Wadden Sea, which are almost completely in public ownership, remote, and where predation management can be implemented sustainably, constitute areas with high potential to shelter source populations of many grassland breeding birds. This results in having relatively large areas with significant populations of many wet-grassland breeding birds where longstanding conservation efforts have been deployed to date. Publicly owned land in Lower Saxony is usually made available for the implementation of major conservation measures (e.g., large-scale water table optimization, low-intensity agricultural practices), and constitutes an additional asset for wet-grassland breeding bird conservation.

Good cooperation between nature conservation and farmers has been developed over the years by building on mutual trust and good exchange (e.g., almost 20 years of cooperation within the framework of the Cooperation Agriculture and Nature Conservation in East Frisia (Kooperation Landwirtschaft und Naturschutz in Ostfriesland)). Additionally, farmers are cooperative and willing to implement measures like clutch protection, large bird sanctuaries (Vogelschutzgebiete), and agri-environmental and climate measures (AECMs).

Further, wet-grassland breeding bird conservation benefited from the successful testing, evaluation, and implementation of new and existing approaches to wet-grassland conservation. For example, the reevaluation of livestock densities on grassland, the modification of spring grazing time, and the replacement of fences with ditches are all activities continuously under evaluation and adaptation. This culture of continuous adaptation is accompanied by an openness to test and apply a diversity of large-scale conservation approaches, some of them viewed critically in other Federal States in Germany, e.g., active predation management with the participation of professional hunters.

Lower Saxony and Bremen have a good record of implementing large EU-LIFE projects for grassland breeding bird conservation that provided substantial funding and high-profile flagship projects. This was possible because of a strong political support for nature conservation projects in general, and for wet-grassland breeding bird conservation more specifically. For example, Der Niedersächsischer Weg, is an initiative of Lower Saxony to support biodiversity by facilitating the collaborative work of policy-makers, nature conservation agencies, and farmers.

Weaknesses – Similarly to other parts of Germany, the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds in Lower Saxony and Bremen suffers from widespread intensive agriculture characterized by the excessive use of fertilizers and pesticides, widespread monocultures, and loss of habitat heterogeneity. This ever-growing intensification is maintained by the strong influence of farmer organizations. Farmers' interest in practicing low-intensity and bird-friendly grassland management in nature conservation areas is decreasing because of low financial compensation and support. Financial support is often perceived as insufficient to compensate for the poor fodder quality, low biomass yields, and difficulties to manage areas with high water levels. Further, the implementation of AECMs on privately owned agricultural land suitable for bird conservation is based on a voluntary participation principle. Often these measures are not sufficiently attractive to farmers as they are 1) inadequately compensated, 2) lack flexibility, 3) lack accompanying conservation advice, and 4) lack long term planning.

Publicly owned land where major conservation measures can be implemented still suffers, in parts, from inadequate management with 1) rigid mowing dates, 2) a limitation of grazing, 3) failure to exploit opportunities to increase water levels, and 4) inadequate predation management.

The excessive fragmentation of the landscape that used to be home to many grassland breeding birds hinders bird conservation. This fragmentation is mainly due to the construction of farming facilities, wind and photovoltaic plants, transformer stations, the expansion of residential and commercial areas, and the construction of roads and power lines. This fragmentation is also accompanied by increasing difficulties in securing suitable water levels in some areas due to climate change. Fragmented and degraded grasslands are home to unsustainable numbers of predators leading to high predation rates in many protected areas. Predation management is often done locally, at small scales, and is not sustainable for a long-term conservation strategy. Hunting, as a predation management measure, is often hindered by the territorial hunting systems (Revierjagdsystem), and the lack of professional hunters and financial resources. Further, the recent expansion of the wolf, while it does not constitute a direct threat to the birds, is increasingly becoming a problem for farmers to maintain livestock grazing in conservation areas. It is necessary to develop forecasting models for the development of grassland breeding bird populations that account for overarching and crosscutting multi-factors (übergeordneter/übergreifender Faktoren), e.g., climate change, the development of agriculture, changes in predator populations.

Contradictory conservation goals in wet-grassland breeding bird sanctuaries also exist. For example, the preservation of dry reed areas can offer shelter for predators that in turn threaten the reproduction of ground breeding species. Similarly, the development of alluvial forests can reduce and endanger meadow bird habitats, and some insect-friendly

structures (e.g., woody vegetation for example) conflict with keeping open and optimizing meadow bird habitats.

Fundamental habitat features important to the development of grassland breeding birds, like the availability of invertebrate fauna and amphibians, are not always considered in conservation areas. Often, this important biodiversity is destroyed by various maintenance measures. Additionally, the acceptance of woody plants removal to maintain open landscapes is somehow low among communities (mainly urban communities) as the presence of trees is often associated with nature conservation.

Bureaucratic obstacles in accessing European, Federal, and Federal State funding are also identified as a challenge developing wet-grassland bird conservation projects. This is accompanied by a complex organization of institutional processes with a complex assignment of responsibilities in the field of nature protection.

Often conservation measures consist of immediate, short-term, actions (e.g., nest protection in agricultural fields), instead of long-term sustainable solutions like the development of more suitable bird habitats. Further, a regional (i.e., beyond Federal State and Country limits) strategy for the conservation of grassland breeding birds is still missing. Such a strategy is needed to address conservation issues in the different phases of the life cycle of migratory grassland breeding birds. This underlines insufficient exchange and cooperation between wet-grassland breeding bird conservation projects in Lower Saxony and Bremen, especially concerning their strategic alignment, and beyond. Overall, a nationwide strategy for grassland breeding bird conservation is lacking. Many individual projects are being implemented; however, there is no overarching framework for wet-grassland breeding bird conservation across Germany.

Future perspectives:

Opportunities – Natura2000 areas in Lower Saxony and Bremen provide a good framework to further develop wet-grassland bird conservation. They constitute a valuable network of habitats where species conservation measures can be implemented and where substantial habitat optimization measures can be carried out with relatively little resistance (primarily on publicly owned land). Additionally, in Lower Saxony, ecological conservation stations (Ökologische Schutzstationen) will be established soon. Such stations are expected to enhance the management of conservation areas where conservation measures will be implemented in a more targeted and effective way.

Climate mitigation projects, including the rewetting of raised bogs and fens, are expected to have an overall positive effect on wet-grassland breeding bird populations. Developing synergies between climate mitigation measures and bird conservation is an opportunity to significantly increase funding for conservation. Further, the development of projects that utilize biomass from wet grasslands can be in some cases beneficial for wet-grassland breeding bird conservation if implemented correctly.

There is undoubtedly a shift in public opinion regarding water-table management and the need to restore wet grasslands to mitigate the effects of climate change. This accompanies a general desire in society for more ecological agriculture and a more critical approach in consumer behavior toward the impact of agricultural products. New initiatives

have been initiated to develop and implement new concepts of “nature conservation farms”, e.g., Naturschutzhöfe Ostfriesland, a DBU-Projekt.

The new recommendations for clutch-and-chick protection in Lower Saxony are expected to yield better results. These recommendations build on a recent evaluation of prior practices that was conducted across the entire Federal State. In that regard, there is a general intensification of efforts to restructure the CAP in a way to promote and support low-intensity agriculture and increase funding instruments to support nature conservation (e.g., via AUKM/AECMs).

The increasing willingness of farmers to cooperate with nature conservation measures on privately owned land is promising. An example is shown in Bremen where a program targeting wet-grassland bird conservation on farmland (Kooperativer Wiesenvogelschutz Bremen Projekt) implemented on 4,500 ha allowed the establishment of more than 1000 breeding pairs of birds that are now source populations for many species regionally. Such initiatives constitute an opportunity to expand this model in other areas of Germany. Meadow bird protection can become an alternative source of income for some farmers, and this opportunity can be demonstrated by developing the right funding instruments.

Overall, there is an increased political commitment to nature conservation and more specifically to the conservation of wet-grassland birds. This commitment is expressed through the Lower Saxony Way (Der Niedersächsisches Weg) which creates an opportunity to strengthen cooperation for bird conservation efforts across Lower Saxony.

Other aspects underline opportunities to advance wet-grassland breeding bird conservation in Lower Saxony and Bremen, including 1) the increased willingness of hunters to cooperate with nature conservation for the implementation of predation management. 2) The intensification of cooperation with neighboring Federal States and countries for a more holistic approach to bird conservation. 3) The increased acceptance of land acquisition (purchase, swapping) as an opportunity to implement long-lasting habitat optimization measures for bird conservation. This costly approach is being adopted when possible and is often co-financed by European projects (e.g., LIFE) and Federal State funding. 4) The establishment of nature conservation associations targeting meadow bird conservation that increase the participation of volunteers, e.g., Naturschutzmaßnahmen, Modellcharakter des Bremer Kooperationsprojektes.

Further, large projects (e.g., LIFE IP GrassBirdHabitats) are creating opportunities to mobilize efforts over a network of habitats across the Federal State. Further, they provide significant resources to conduct a combination of measures over a relatively long period (10 years), including land acquisition, waterlogging, predation management, and the employment of caretakers. Such large projects are undoubtedly an opportunity to advance bird conservation at a larger scale; a much-needed effort to reverse the declining populations of many wet-grassland breeding bird species.

Threats – Climate change is undoubtedly considered a major threat to wet-grassland breeding bird conservation. Lower precipitation and extended drought periods are already being observed across Lower Saxony and Bremen. Decreasing precipitations will increase competition for water allocated among nature, agriculture, and society. This competition will only be amplified by climate change and increasing drought periods (both length and frequency). Overall, the consequences of global changes (climate, land use changes, social,

political, and economic changes) on wet-grassland breeding bird conservation are still difficult to predict in the long term. This is shown, for example, in the increased pressure on nature conservation instruments in ecological priority areas due to increased prices in the food and energy sectors.

The expansion of renewable energy projects in areas important for wet-grassland bird conservation (e.g., in East Frisia, where the development of wind farms and associated infrastructure and power lines) is leading to an irreversible loss of valuable bird habitat. As a consequence, birds are restricted to isolated “islands” increasingly susceptible to predation and other disturbances. This contributes to the decreasing connectivity between habitats that is affecting the range of many species. There is a real risk of regional extinction of many species due to the “islandisation” of the last remaining populations with a short- and medium-term risk of further local populations becoming extinct.

Pressures for more productive agriculture practices continue unabated, resulting in further intensification and the impoverishment of the landscape with the loss of complex habitats. Modern agriculture machinery produces, and requires, homogeneous surfaces without depressions and puddles, very important for grassland birds. Low-intensity farming practices continue to be economically unattractiveness. This is increasingly creating a disconnection between sustainable agriculture and bird conservation. Concurrently, the structural changes in the farming industry where smaller farms are being replaced by larger ones (e.g., in the case of dairy farms) are accelerating. Progressively, many farming activities are assigned to contractors who are less considerate of bird conservation. This will have major consequences on the intensification of productivity and therefore on our ability to implement bird conservation measures. Further, the declining interest in beef and dairy by consumers is leading to low-intensity farmed grasslands being replaced by grasslands managed for biomass which translates into intensive and more frequent mowing, and the application of fertilizer to increase biomass.

Degraded landscape generates ever-increasing predation pressures including the recent increase in the populations of many neozoa. Further, there is a real threat of increased conflicts between the wolf and farmers. The wolf has a significant impact on the presence of free-roaming livestock in grasslands necessary to maintain low vegetation and suitable habitat for grassland breeding bird species.

Other threats have been identified, including 1) political regulations (primarily at a higher level, i.e., Federal State, and European) that favor the expansion of renewable energies on grassland bird protection, e.g., wind turbine projects or solar projects on sensitive bird habitats. 2) The continuous excessive reliance on the “voluntary principle” when it comes to bird conservation on private farmland. The voluntary principle has not brought any substantial progress in meadow bird protection in the last 30 years. 3) The decrease in the public interest or “sense of priority” toward bird conservation in the context of major ongoing crises, e.g., the pandemic, the war in Ukraine, etc. 4) The risk that the European Agricultural policy (e.g., CAP) will continue to ignore suggestions for sustainable low-intensity agriculture, focusing primarily on promoting high productivity at the expense of nature conservation and biodiversity. Nature conservation depends in part on a few (willing) farmers practicing low-intensity farming and it is not foreseeable that this type of farming will be used as a conventional practice on a broad scale. The CAP reforms in this direction are extremely slow and to date ineffective. 5) The lack of knowledge about bird species and populations by some farmers is particularly alarming. A large localized roosting population of

Lapwings can sometimes be interpreted as a “good population” when it often reflects an isolated case. On the other hand, the loss of grassland bird biodiversity and overall communities is going unnoticed.

11.2 Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg

In total, 8 participants took part in the HS survey for Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg. The majority of participants were active in nature conservation (6 participants), followed by monitoring (1) and research (1). The participants declared having expertise in Ornithology (4), ecology of wetlands and wet grasslands (2), and species conservation (2). Further, the vast majority of participants identified their level of expertise as advanced (Figure 35).

Figure 35: Diagrams showing the distribution of responses to Q2: What is your main field of activity? and Q3: what is your main expertise? Number of participants 8.

Current status:

Strengths – Regulated and monitored efforts for the conservation of grassland breeding birds in Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg have been implemented since 1986 (mid-1990s for Hamburg) when the first contractual bird conservation measures were established. Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg are aware of their high responsibility for grassland breeding bird conservation as they host a large proportion of the German breeding populations of many grassland breeding bird species. Indeed, due to their topography, Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg offer a multitude of coastal and inland habitats home to a diverse community of grassland breeding birds.

There is good knowledge about the occurrence and population status, and the most important breeding areas have been designated EU bird sanctuaries (SPAS, Vogelschutzgebiete). A multitude of approaches and tools are currently available for bird conservation in coastal and inland areas on privately or publicly owned land. In Hamburg, a special fund from the Authority for the Environment, Climate, Energy, and Agriculture (Sondervermögen in der Behörde für Umwelt, Klima, Energie und Agrarwirtschaft) is available for bird conservation.

Widespread conservation measures are diverse in Schleswig-Holstein including collaborative grassland breeding bird conservation measures (Gemeinschaftlicher Wiesenvogelschutz), decrees for the protection of bird species (Wiesenvogelerlass),

contractual nature conservation schemes (Vertragsnaturschutz), monitoring measures (Wiesenvogelmonitoring), predator control measures (Prädationsschutzmaßnahmen), and habitat enhancement measures (Biotopgestaltende Maßnahmen). Further, wet grassland breeding bird conservation benefits from good collaboration between farmers and conservation practitioners, a good network of nature conservation organizations, user associations (water, agriculture) sensitive to bird protection, and a relatively good political commitment. In addition, there are very committed full-time voluntary workers who are involved in meadow bird protection projects

Weaknesses – Despite all the conservation efforts deployed to date, the breeding success of many grassland bird species is not sufficient across Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg. Breeding successes are primarily hindered by intensive agriculture and high predation rates. Mammalian predator populations are excessively high across all agricultural land. Overall, reliable research and monitoring results are available. Nevertheless, additional research is necessary to understand the local impact of predation on bird populations, especially to develop suitable mitigation and conservation measures.

In a few cases where conservation efforts have been successful, funding for the implementation of conservation measures is often project-dependent (e.g., EU LIFE projects). This unreliability in funding availability needed for conservation is an additional challenge for long-term conservation, where funding gaps for the implementation of measures (e.g., predator control) must be avoided.

The intentionally lowered groundwater table in agricultural land is a major challenge for grassland breeding bird conservation, as many species require partially wet, and seasonally flooded grasslands for successful breeding. The persisting generalized excessive drainage of grasslands across Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg to optimize agricultural yields is a major challenge for conservation, and its effects on grassland breeding bird conservation are expected to worsen due to climate change.

Intensive agricultural practices and bird-unfriendly management of agricultural land are also widespread and constitute a major obstacle to conservation. The principle of voluntariness for farmers to engage in bird-friendly farming practices does not provide sufficient incentive to shift toward more sustainable and bird-friendly agriculture. Necessary farming restrictions for the protection of meadow birds are politically not enforceable.

Insufficient implementation of knowledge and expertise by decision-makers and a partial lack of understanding on the part of user associations for the issues relating to grassland breeding bird protection are recurrent in both Federal States.

Future perspectives:

Opportunities – There is a strong willingness of the environmental ministry of Schleswig-Holstein to invest in measures beneficial for grassland-breeding bird conservation. This creates hope for future opportunities to tackle the declining trends of grassland breeding bird populations across the Federal State.

Climate change and the increased drought periods led to an increased focus on topics of peatland restoration, rewetting of fen soils, waterlogging, impoundments, and water retention (Niederungsstrategie 2100). This opportunity has the potential to benefit the

conservation of grassland-breeding birds if addressed correctly, and synergies between climate change mitigation measures and wet grassland breeding bird conservation need to be developed.

The increased water scarcity for agriculture creates an additional opportunity to rethink agriculture and water management practices in wet grasslands. This should be combined with the deployment of measures to support bird-friendly agriculture in farmland.

Relatively large breeding areas for wet grassland breeding birds still exist in Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg. If bird conservation measures are implemented decisively, a successful recovery of bird populations is still possible. Nature conservation organizations and decision-makers often express their willingness to support bird conservation measures, however, the implementation is often too slow.

Threats – A major threat to the conservation of wet grassland breeding bird populations in Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg is the change of environmental baseline conditions and habitat loss due to climate change. For example, extended drought and heavy rain events have the potential to make the implementation of conservation measures difficult in the future. Adequate waterlogging is already becoming increasingly difficult under climate change even on publicly owned land where more significant measures can be implemented.

In a city-State like Hamburg, the loss of grassland to construction and infrastructure projects that cannot be compensated adequately elsewhere, the increasingly high impact of recreational activities on nature, and a growing metropolitan area are all threats to grassland breeding bird conservation.

The energy transition is increasing the demand for large photovoltaic and wind power plants, as well as associated power lines, which are potentially planned on permanent wet grasslands or risk to increase their fragmentation.

Meadow bird protection is not considered adequately in plans for nature-based climate protection. Paludiculture, often considered a nature-based solution, can also be considered a threat when bird habitat is shifting from wet grasslands to Cattail (*Typha sp.*) or Reed canary grass (*Phalaris arundinacea*) farms. This adds to the already high loss of high-quality and species-rich grasslands driven by increasing demands for food and biogas production.

While also considered as an opportunity, the increased interest in peatland restoration in lowland areas to mitigate the effect of climate change can become a threat if not implemented in a bird-friendly way. Thus, synergies between climate mitigation efforts and bird conservation measures need to be developed.

Insufficient funding for habitat restoration and implementation of conservation measures is also considered a threat to the future of wet grassland bird conservation in Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg.

Insufficient reproduction rates are leading to aging populations which can threaten the preservation of many populations in the long run.

11.3 North Rhine-Westphalia

In total, 13 participants took part in the HS for North Rhine-Westphalia. The majority of participants from were active in nature conservation (9 participants), followed by monitoring (1). The participants declared having expertise in Ornithology (8), and the ecology of wetlands and wet grasslands (2). Further, the vast majority of participants identified their level of expertise as as advanced (Figure 36).

Figure 36: The diagrams showing the participants' main field of activity (A), main expertise (B), and level of expertise (C). Number of participants 13.

Current status:

Strengths – The conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds in North Rhine-Westphalia is a longstanding tradition. The first program for wetland and wet-grassland conservation date to 1985, when the first network of wetland protection areas was established. These initial areas, designated first as nature reserves with only a few of them as EU SAPs at that time, increased throughout the years due to extensive land acquisition (i.e., into public ownership). In addition to the established SPAs, a network of protected areas of various sizes and statuses, as well as larger complexes of compensation areas, form a network of habitats fundamental for maintaining habitat connectivity across the Federal State that is particularly important for wet grassland breeding bird species like the Curlew and Meadow pipit.

Further, optimal conservation management for wet grassland breeding birds can be implemented on publicly owned land, including waterlogging, the creation of waterbodies, and the regulation of land use practices (e.g., mowing regulation, restriction of fertilizers and pesticides). The Federal State and municipalities provide funds for the implementation of bird friendly management measures, some of which are implemented by local farmers and contribute to good cooperation and acceptance of nature conservation and agriculture.

The Federal State of North Rhine-Westphalia provides annual funds dedicated to implementing measures of habitat maintenance and management in conservation areas and for funding additional conservation measures like the implementation of electric fences.

Experienced human capacities are present across the Federal State, in addition to an active network of biological stations. Biological stations have clear mandates for monitoring, coordinating management with farmers, and planning and implementing maintenance and

conservation measures. In some districts, extended mandates include the protection of clutches and the documentation of breeding success.

There is a strong collaboration among the main organizations active in bird conservation, including the AG Wiesenvogelschutz (Meadow birds conservation working group), Landesamt für Natur, Umwelt und Klima Nordrhein-Westfalen (LANUK, Untere Naturschutzschaftsbehörden (UNB), and district governments (Bezirksregierungen).

Management plans exist for a number of important bird sanctuaries, providing a framework to advance conservation measures.

The monitoring of all relevant breeding bird populations is conducted annually. As the vast majority of grassland breeding birds breeds in protected areas, the complete evaluation of the population size and trends of species like the Black-tailed Godwit, Curlew, Redshank, and Snipe is possible every year. This close monitoring enables conservation practitioners to closely monitor bird populations and quickly identify changes in trends.

The use of modern tools for clutch protection, such as drones, is being implemented in many projects.

And last, the ongoing debate on biodiversity, and insect biodiversity more specifically, benefits grassland breeding bird conservation by funding conservation measures in grassland important to the conservation of many bird species. This has been viewed as an opportunity to implement holistic biodiversity conservation measures benefiting both fauna and flora.

Weaknesses - The implementation of successful conservation measures is often hindered by the large proportion of privately-owned land in conservation areas (Naturschutzgebiete) and the resistance of farmers, farmer associations, and water managers (e.g., Dike Associations (Deichverbände)) to collaborate and change their practices.

Conservation areas are often too small, without buffer zones separating them from intensive agriculture, reducing them to small “islands” across the landscape where birds are capable to breed.

Only half of the areas designated as bird conservation areas can be considered in good condition. In many of these areas breeding success has not been sufficient for the last 15 years. The basic protection of bird conservation areas is insufficient, and the quality of grasslands keeps degrading since these areas were designated.

Conservation activities are primarily focused on a few core areas and little is done to protect grassland-breeding birds outside these areas, hindering, therefore, the conservation of species like the Northern Lapwing, which has a dispersed distribution statewide. In conservation core areas, a combination of a relatively high density of breeding birds and insularity has led to low breeding success rates due to predation. Outside these core conservation areas, grassland breeding bird conservation depends entirely on voluntary engagements (e.g., contracting farmers (Vertragsnaturschutz), marking nests, etc.).

After an initial momentum in wetland and wet grassland conservation programs, changes in the Federal State government led to a standstill, especially in the acquisition of land into public ownership, fundamental for implementing long-lasting conservation measures (e.g., water table optimization).

There are no district-wide land consolidation procedures (Flurbereinungsverfahren) through land purchase which is necessary to potentially allow the opening (removal of wood) and/or waterlogging of protected areas. Nature conservation, *per se*, today is not considered a reason for land consolidation procedures in North Rhine-Westphalia. In the past, there were cases of land consolidation procedures for nature conservation.

Contractual nature conservation, which is mainly relied on in North Rhine-Westphalia, has limited effects and cannot solve the basic problem of excessive water drainage. Additionally, this contractualization of nature conservation suffers from a heavy bureaucratization of procedures for farmers, districts, and biological stations.

While funding is available from the Federal State to implement a few conservation measures, funding can be considered largely insufficient. Some conservation measures, like mammalian-predator trapping or personnel costs to implement clutch and chick protection, are not funded. This is driving conservationists to increasingly depend on EU-LIFE projects for grassland-breeding bird conservation. Additionally, insufficient jobs (i.e., positions) are available for nature conservation, and often salaries are too low to be attractive.

North Rhine-Westphalia is characterized by intensive agriculture that strongly affects breeding and resting areas for many wet grassland breeding bird species. The work of biodiversity advisors from the Chamber of Agriculture is intended to improve communication between agriculture and nature conservation, but the offered measures (e.g., field bird island (Feldvogelinsel), flowering strips (Blühstreifen)) are often ineffective. Conservation efforts in wet grasslands were often too late for species such as the Snipe, Lapwing and Black-tailed Godwit. Inadequate conservation efforts transformed conservation areas into retreat areas for predators that contributed in the loss of these species.

Predation is also problematic in North Rhine-Westphalia and fencing or enclosure measures alone cannot achieve sustainable long-lasting improvement. Predator control through hunting is currently hindered by the lack of well-trained and instructed professional hunters. Further, the spread of the raccoon and the rapid increase in the red fox populations increase predation pressures.

Last, there are high local and regional recreational pressures on bird conservation areas, specifically along the Rhine River. Hunting activities constitute an important disturbance in core conservation areas.

Future perspectives:

Opportunities - The ongoing climate change debate provides an opportunity to rethink policies, agricultural practices, and nature conservation. It is undoubtedly an opportunity for a thorough rethinking of how wet grassland breeding bird conservation can benefit from changes in agricultural and land management practices.

A high concentration of the remnant populations of grassland breeding birds in SPAs can provide an opportunity for a better implementation of conservation measures as a last attempt to preserve these birds before their complete disappearance in North Rhine-Westphalia. However, long-term solutions can only be achieved in large-scale habitat improvements as it has been implemented in neighboring Federal States (e.g., Lower Saxony, Dümmer area).

Ongoing EU-LIFE projects, (e.g., LIFE-Projekt Wiesenvögel), constitute real opportunities to improve the conservation of grassland breeding birds, consolidate state-wide efforts, and establish collaborations with other projects within Germany (e.g., Life IP GrassbirdsHabitats).

A significant improvement in nature conservation in North Rhine-Westphalia can only be achieved with a stronger political commitment whether it is at a local, State, or federal level. The recent elections in 2022, where a Green Minister for the ministry of environment was appointed, provide hope to increase funding for nature conservation.

Through the coordination offices for the implementation of the Makos (similar “management plan”; concepts of measures, usually elaborated on a large scale for bird protection areas), more funding for personnel and measures as well as land acquisition will be available.

The use of electric fences locally can be considered as an opportunity to save a few breeding populations; however, this measure cannot be considered a long-term viable solution.

The ongoing cooperation across counties and neighboring Federal States need to be strengthened, as it constitutes a real opportunity to advance wet grassland breeding bird conservation. For example, experience in neighboring Bad Bentheim (Lower Saxony), shows that head starting Curlews can help stabilize the breeding population on farmland when combined with other complementary measures.

There is a right of first acquisition by public authorities in protected areas when farmland is available to be purchased §66 Vorkaufsrecht BNatSchG. This applies to the entire Federal Republic of Germany. However, due to a lack of financial resources, this is often not implemented.

Threats - The deprioritizing of conservation measures against new challenges is not specific to North Rhine-Westphalia, however, it can utterly jeopardize conservation efforts. For example, in the context of the ongoing war in Ukraine, global food supplies have been challenged and a general movement to maintain, and even increase, agricultural productivity has been engaged. This contradicts advocacy for a more sustainable agricultural production which does not jeopardize grassland breeding bird biodiversity, and highlights the threats of deprioritizing conservation efforts.

The development of renewable energy is a challenge for wet grassland breeding bird conservation, as competition for land will increase.

The intensification of agricultural practices continues unabated and around 80% of grassland breeding bird nests fall victim to such practices. Even in protected areas, there are no requirements in favor of grassland bird conservation (exception: conversion of grassland), because a large part of the land is privately owned and politicians and administrators do not want to enforce appropriate regulations. On public land, grassland breeding birds can be protected by corresponding usage dates, and biological station deploy major efforts to protect, in few cases, few clutches on private land.

The increased bureaucracy and economic pressure are driving farmers to withdraw from contractual nature conservation (Vertragsnaturschutz). The loss of competitiveness of nature conservation contracts restricts the scope for action by nature conservation as the

prices of agricultural products keep increasing. This asks for a reevaluation of such financial incentives provided for bird protection on agricultural land.

The general tendency of prolonged drought periods due to climate change, in addition to heavy rainfall events, constitutes a threat to the conservation of wet grassland breeding birds in the near future. Thus, it will be increasingly difficult to keep water levels optimal during the breeding period.

The unabated lowering of water tables will lead to an even more generalized water crisis in wetlands and wet grasslands as groundwater levels are excessively kept low and are not recovering. Water is critically lacking in many wetlands of NRW, while more water should be kept in the landscape for longer periods in backwater habitats and overflow structures. Further, a major threat is that water shortages will be addressed primarily with technical solutions for agriculture and society, but not with nature-based water management approach.

If the European populations of wet grassland breeding birds continue to decline, populations occurring in peripheral areas like North Rhine-Westphalia will be very exposed and will go extinct.

Further intensification of agriculture, the ongoing development of farming that prioritizes productivity over sustainability, and the loss of small farms that are increasingly replaced by large farms are all threats to grassland breeding birds in North Rhine-Westphalia.

The unpredictability of financial resources dedicated to conservation. Indeed, funding for wet grassland bird conservation is not always secured and changes in the political landscape (from community to federal levels) contribute to this financial uncertainty.

11.4 The Continental Biogeographic Region of Germany

In total, 22 participants declared having expertise in the continental biogeographic region of Germany representing the Federal States of **Baden-Württemberg**, **Bavaria**, **Brandenburg**, **Hessen**, **Mecklenburg-Vorpommern**, **Sachsen-Anhalt**, and **Berlin**. When the expressed opinions were State-specific or specific to a geographical location, we made sure to specify that and associated the statement with a geographical location.

We present here the results into two distinct sections—current status and future perspectives— based on the contribution of 22 participants. The majority of participants from the continental biogeographic region of Germany were active in nature conservation (12 participants), followed by monitoring (5), environmental education (2), research (1), environmental policy (1), and agriculture (1). The participants declared having expertise in Ornithology (14), ecology of wetlands and wet grasslands (3), flyway ecology (1), agriculture (1), agriculture research (1), landscape planning (1), and environmental policy (1). Further, the vast majority of participants identified their level of expertise as their expertise as advanced (Figure 37).

Figure 37: Diagrams showing the distribution of responses to Q2: What is your main field of activity? and Q3: what is your main expertise? Number of participants 22.

Current status:

Strengths – There is overall a good commitment to wet-grassland bird conservation across all Federal States in the continental biogeographic region of Germany (i.e., in Federal States included in this report, see above). This is reflected by the presence of skilled human capacities, a strong commitment of volunteers, and a good interaction between farmers and nature conservation practitioners.

Some species and populations have been the subject of continuous conservation programs over decades via, for example, the species conservation program in **Baden-Württemberg**. This continuity is essential to the implementation of successful conservation measures; however, it is still often lacking in many areas where the monitoring of bird populations and funding needed to implement conservation measures are intermittent.

The Federal State of **Brandenburg** is just starting its large-scale peatland restoration programs. These programs, if implemented efficiently, are very promising as the Federal State has a large potential for peatland restoration.

In the Federal State of **Mecklenburg-Vorpommern**, large programs of peatland restoration are improving breeding and feeding habitats for birds. Several thousand hectares of formerly intensively used grasslands have been rewetted. For example, large areas in the Peene and Trebel valleys (Peenetal and Trebeltal, fen valley systems) were rewetted in the last 20 years, creating hundreds of hectares of wetlands and wet grassland habitats for breeding and resting birds. In most cases, the rewetting led to a cessation of management so that other species than waders, like Terns, Rails, and Whinchat can also profit from these conservation programs. The Federal State is rich in small and large fens and several thousand hectares have the potential to be restored in the future to mitigate climate change.

In the Altmühlal, **Bavaria**, the situation is currently such that farmers are also in favor of raising the water levels and thus improving the water supply, because due to climate-related changes in the seasonal weather conditions, it is anyway barely possible to produce sufficient quantities of hay.

Increased attention to grassland breeding bird conservation in **Mecklenburg-Vorpommern** benefits directly from the LIFE Limicodra project and additional compensation

measures of the Nordstream 1 (Leopoldshafen polder). These activities provided significant measures for the conservation of waders and gave a platform that brings together stakeholders from across the Federal State and beyond, including ornithologists, various authorities and agencies (StALU-Staatliches Amt für Landwirtschaft und Umwelt, LUNG-Landesamt für Umwelt, Naturschutz und Geologie), farmers' associations, Ministry representatives, water and soil experts, UNBs, and NGOs (e.g., NABU among others).

In **Mecklenburg-Vorpommern**, the LIFE Limicodra was able to include the TopUp “Peatland-friendly water management and meadow bird protection” in the agri-environment-climate measures (Agrarumwelt- und Klimamaßnahmen (AUKM)) “Naturschutzgerechte Grünlandrichtlinie” for a pilot phase of 2 years (2021-22). Thus, to date, the program was applied by farmers on 360 ha and is planned to be permanently incorporated in the AUKM measures and applied statewide.

In **Mecklenburg-Vorpommern**, fewer human pressures compared to other Federal States directly benefits bird conservation.

In **Hessen**, cooperation with farmers in habitats valuable for bird conservation is extremely good. LIFE projects have contributed to developing this cooperation and established and constructive dialogue between farmers and nature and landscape managers (HALM applications). Through multiple LIFE projects, many habitat improvement activities have been implemented in recent years, including the creation and renaturation of water bodies, or habitat improvements through the creation of grass strips, etc. Hessen has a variety of relatively intact habitats (LRTs), such as mountain meadows, bristle grassland, calcareous grasslands, and moorland and wet meadows, which create a diverse mosaic of bird habitats.

In **Brandenburg**, conservation measures targeting the Great Bustard are found to be beneficial for other grassland breeding bird species like the Curlew.

Other strengths have been reported across Federal States in the continental biogeographic region of Germany, including; 1) A good database of bird populations and many areas profiting from extensive support (**Bavaria**); 2) A multitude of conservation instruments (**all Federal States**) including the establishment of no disturbance period during the breeding season, bird-friendly mowing, vegetation stripes; 3) widespread contractual conservation measures (**all Federal States**); 4) Extensive monitoring (**Hessen**, and other Federal States); 5) Large-scale conservation areas (Hessen, SPA Wetterau >10,000 ha); 6) Water table management on SPAs (**all Federal States**), and 7) predation management efforts (**all Federal States**).

Weaknesses – Similarly to other parts of Germany, grassland breeding birds in the Federal States in the continental biogeographic region of Germany suffer from the lack of willingness of the broader agricultural sector to engage in more sustainable use of wet grasslands. Agricultural practices are the main cause of habitat loss; intensive agriculture, the excessive drainage of wet grasslands, and the simultaneous and early mowing of large parcels are the main drivers of bird population declines. Nature conservation often lacks access to sufficient land and excessively relies on the principle of voluntarism.

The lack of flexibility in the implementation of the agri-environment-climate measures (Agrarumwelt- und Klimamaßnahmen (AUKM)) and their limited efficiency have been reported in **Sachsen-Anhalt**, **Mecklenburg-Vorpommern**, **Brandenburg**, and **Bavaria**.

AUKM are also poorly adapted to conservation objectives. Some requirements are simply not attainable, for example, in **Brandenburg** the land-owners' approval is required for increasing water levels in polders, however, some polders are owned by more than 200 people, and many of those cannot be found.

Agricultural subsidies still make intensive and soil-damaging farming much more profitable for farmers than the sustainable management of wet grasslands

There is little or no willingness of authorities to make even minor nature conservation requirements or to impose any regulations (e.g., local water retention)

Regulatory obstacles (e.g., in **Hessen**), where conflicting regulations between the water rights (Wasserrecht) and land consolidation laws (Flurbereinigung) hinder nature conservation.

The added effects of climate change, the excessive drainage of grasslands, and water extraction for irrigation (e.g., **Sachsen-Anhalt, Mecklenburg-Vorpommern**) create very poor habitat conditions for many bird species. Farmers are increasingly watering their crops and fodder.

High predator densities are a major challenge across **all Federal States**. Hunters are not motivated to participate in predator population regulation due to the German hunting territorial organization. In general, there is a lack of extensive predator control in wet grassland breeding areas by professional hunters. Further, the damage caused by predation on bird populations is sometimes played down, ignored, or inadequately dealt with (e.g., no hunting is allowed in National Parks). Protests against culling and predator removals also exist and can hinder the implementation of effective predation management.

Habitat fragmentation is a major challenge for wet grassland bird conservation. For example, in **Hessen**, the areas suitable for breeding meadow birds are found only in preserved residual areas, and 90% of wet grassland breeding birds breed in only three areas (Wetterau und Gersprenzaue im Grünland, Groß-Gerau im Ackerland). This exposes the breeding populations in these isolated areas to extreme predation pressure resulting in low breeding success rates.

In **Baden-Württemberg**, the level of knowledge on the distribution and conservation biology of many species is not sufficient, especially for species that are not currently rare or threatened with extinction. Not enough attention is given to breeding success, especially for songbirds.

In all of the continental German Federal States, Natura2000 commitments are insufficiently implemented. The Federal States rely on voluntary participation in AUKM, leading to measures that are often non-species-specific, and not targeted or effective. More specifically, in **Mecklenburg-Vorpommern**, the lack of compliance with Natura2000 obligations constitutes an obstacle to wet grassland bird conservation. Additionally, the M.-V. Ministry of Agriculture has no apparent willingness to promote projects for grassland bird conservation within State-owned areas (public ownership), although these areas could still be used for agriculture, albeit with some restrictions (e.g., increased water levels). This adds to overall less political will to improve wet grassland breeding bird conservation comparable to other Federal States.

Large-scale farms increasingly produce large-scale monotonous landscapes with negative consequences for biodiversity and bird conservation.

In **Brandenburg**, the nature conservation authorities give greater weight to forest and woody plant protection than to the maintenance of open spaces. This translates, in some cases, into foresting potential grassland bird breeding areas.

Poor communication and public relations are substantial problems for grassland bird conservation. For example, in **Hessen**, increased disturbance by nature-based tourism is a major problem. It is getting more difficult to protect sensitive areas from tourists and visitors even with an intensive public relations effort. Further, in **Brandenburg**, poor communication has led to a lack of acceptance of conservation measures by farmers. For example, there was no prior communication about the introduction of the new decree on the use of plant protection products (Pflanzenschutzmittelanwendungsverordnung), which prohibits the use of pesticides in nature conservation areas. Early communication about the designation of protected areas is also repeatedly inadequately carried out, leading sometimes to important protests. Poor communication has led to conservation programs, like the peatland-friendly land management (moorschonende Bewirtschaftung), being insufficiently accepted by the stakeholders.

Future perspectives:

Opportunities – The objective to make Germany climate neutral by 2045 will need, potentially, the rewetting of all drained peatlands across the country. Thus, driven by the urgency for climate mitigation measures, the restoration of fens and peatlands is increasingly attracting funding and interest. This trend can benefit the recovery of biodiversity of wet grasslands in general and more specifically of wet grassland breeding birds.

The consistent implementation of best practices and know-how accumulated from successful case studies is important to increase the efficiency of conservation efforts. This can benefit from new technologies and ongoing research, e.g., chick telemetry. Additionally, better exclosures and predator control measures are increasingly proving to be beneficial for the protection of breeding birds, chicks, and nests locally.

Continuous pressure from the European Commission and the Federal Government of Germany to implement more concrete conservation measures with clear quantitative targets is a promising opportunity to keep moving the conservation of wet grassland breeding birds forward.

The development of more effective agri-environment-climate measures (AECM; Agrarumwelt- und Klimamaßnahmen (AUKM)) for wet grasslands would be an opportunity to advance bird conservation measures. Win-win situations for nature conservation and agriculture are still possible by supporting higher water table levels in the continental biogeographic region in Germany.

EU LIFE projects and “after-LIFE” activities, with their associated activities in public relations, education, and capacity building, constitute a true opportunity for wet grassland breeding bird conservation.

The establishment of Natura2000 site managers and biological/ecological stations with mandates to support education, public communication, and stakeholder dialogue (e.g., with local communities, farmers, and hunters).

Grassland breeding bird conservation benefits from low-intensity agriculture in mountain grasslands. Maintaining this agriculture profitable, and preserving the current farmers, is an opportunity for bird conservation.

Reliable funding programs are available and provide opportunities to make a difference when stakeholders at all levels are better involved in supporting the programs and in designating protected areas.

Threats – The consequence of climate change on water availability, precipitation deficits, and prolonged drought are major concerns across the Federal States in the continental biogeography region of Germany. How climate change will affect the conservation of wet grasslands and associated bird communities is a major source of uncertainty and mitigation efforts need to be planned and engaged as soon as possible. Additionally, climate-change-related events might endanger coastal lowland grasslands, often located below sea level and protected by dikes. Hence, it is important to rethink conservation strategies and redirect conservation measures to less exposed areas, considered less “high risk” to floods and saltwater intrusions.

The intensive use of fertilizer and pesticides in agriculture, and the associated habitat degradation, biodiversity loss, and high insect mortality (both biodiversity and biomass) are also major threats recognized across the continental biogeographic region of Germany. No significant changes in agricultural practices have been implemented yet, and the way agricultural practices are evolving will lead to further degradation of wet grassland habitats and the loss of associated biodiversity.

Excessive predation whether from avian or mammalian predators (primarily, fox, and raccoon) is a major threat to conservation. More resources need to be engaged toward the proper management of predation to reduce its impact on the reproduction of grassland breeding birds.

The development of solar parks on grassland primarily destined for nature conservation is a major threat to bird conservation as this trend is expected to accelerate in the near future.

Uncertainty related to future political or economic situations is a major concern to bird conservation as many resources vital for the implementation of conservation measures are dependent on political decisions and the evolution of the economic situation of the concerned Federal States.

Unchanged practices and keeping the same course of insufficient, and sometimes ineffective, agri-environment-climate measures (AECM; Agrarumwelt- und Klimamaßnahmen (AUKM)), intensive land-use and un-adapted farming practices, slow decision making, and the sluggish reaction of responsible authorities (e.g., Federal State offices for the environment of Environment Ministries), are all direct threats to wet grassland bird conservation.

The loss of attractive flagship species, like the Black-tailed Godwit and the Curlew (which were extinct locally in some Federal States), jeopardizes the conservation of wet grassland

breeding birds in general. Flagship species are important for communicating conservation concerns to the public.

12 Case Studies: Lessons from Successful Wet-Grassland Breeding Bird Conservation in Germany

We have selected 11 representative case studies (Figure 38) to highlight the diverse and successful conservation efforts across Germany, showcasing approaches such as holistic conservation strategies (case studies 11.1, 11.2, 11.3, and 11.4), meadow bird conservation on private agricultural lands (Case Study 11.5), effective predation management (case studies 11.6 and 11.7), advanced telemetry studies (case study 11.8), bird-friendly operations in an airport area (case study 11.9), a political agreement advancing bird and biodiversity conservation (case study 11.10), and the development of a payment model for conserving birds on public land (case study 11.11).

Each case study provides a clear description of methods and approached use to tackle urgent conservation issues and provides recommendations. Additionally, references and contact information are included to allow a direct exchange with the Case study providers.

Figure 38: Thematic overview of the 11 case studies for wet-grassland bird conservation in Germany.

12.1 Meadow Bird Conservation Without Fences and Predator Management: Successes in the Swabian Danube Wetlands

Abstract

The Schwäbische Donaumoos (SD), situated in the Danube Valley between Ulm and Donauwörth, is a wetland area of international ecological importance, designated as a Ramsar site in 1976. Despite suffering from the effects of modern land use, including drainage and intensification, the SD remains a vital habitat for over 250 bird species, including numerous breeding species like Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* and Common Snipe *Gallinago gallinago*. Conservation efforts, particularly focused on meadow bird conservation since 2014, have shown promising results. Through the Meadow Bird Breeding Site Management project, measures such as nest protection and habitat restoration have led to a slowdown in the decline of key species like Lapwing and significant increases in breeding pairs of Snipe. Importantly, the success of these conservation efforts has been achieved without resorting to fencing or targeted predator management, highlighting the importance of suitable habitats in mitigating predation pressure. The findings underscore the necessity of prioritizing habitat preservation and creation for long-term species conservation, emphasizing the crucial role of natural landscapes in halting biodiversity loss.

Introduction

The "Schwäbische Donaumoos" (SD), a wetland area of international ecological significance located in the Danube Valley between Ulm and Donauwörth (Figure 39), was designated as a Ramsar site, "Danube Meadows and Donaumoos," in 1976, covering 10,000 hectares. The protected areas along the Danube and adjacent open marsh and fen areas provide a multitude of ecological niches and are home to over 250 bird species, including at least 140 breeding species. Typical meadow birds and wetland species such as Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* and Common Snipe *Gallinago gallinago* are found in the fen areas. Large waders are only present in small numbers, while Whinchats *Saxicola rubetra* and Corn Buntings, after a previous decline, are now sporadically encountered. Additionally, the area records high numbers of wintering and migratory birds such as Marsh Harrier, Rough-legged Buzzard, Short-eared Owl, Great Grey Shrike, and Crane. The diversity is complemented by numerous wader species such as Jack Snipe, Ruff, and Greenshank. The SD is not only renowned for its landscape and biodiversity but also for its significant role in nature conservation. The habitats in the SD have suffered significantly from the effects of modern land use. Drainage and intensification of the fen areas have led to the loss of extensive, flower-rich meadows and almost led to the extinction of meadow birds. About 20 years ago, a pioneering restoration project was initiated here through the rewetting of the Leipheimer Moos (180 hectares), which already made the area a trailblazer for effective peatland conservation in Bavaria. At that time, the importance of moors for climate protection was still little discussed. Nature conservation focused mainly on the protection of rare species such as the Snipe and the Great Bustard. The population of the Lapwing was also monitored in the area early on as part of the annual breeding bird survey by a voluntary ornithological working group since 1993, without foreseeing that this bird would become a concern for nature conservation today. The early recording of the Lapwing population led to the recognition of the decline and the initiation of corresponding conservation measures. Now, a

slowdown in this trend is evident, and recent years even indicate an increase in numbers, contrary to the nationwide trend with declines of over 95% since 1980.

Figure 39: Overview map of the Schwäbische Donaumoos highlighting the wetland area, accompanied by an aerial photograph of the region.

Method and Approach

Since 2014, meadow bird conservation has been specifically focused on in the SD, especially regarding the Lapwing, as part of the "Meadow Bird Breeding Site Management" project by the Government of Swabia (RvS), financially supported by the Bavarian Ministry of the Environment. The project includes the identification of breeding sites, contacting and advising affected farmers on protective measures, and the targeted "care" of nests, including marking and protection from cultivation (Figure 40). In addition, breeding habitats are maintained and, where possible, new ones are created. This also includes the establishment of extensive grazing for open land maintenance and the transformation of former gravel extraction sites, which have proven to be excellent replacement habitats.

Figure 40: An example of bird friendly management where a Northern Lapwing nest is marked and thus protected from destruction.

Results and Conclusion

In recent years, valuable data on Lapwing breeding success considering land use have been collected. About 70% of breeding pairs in the SD use fields as substitute habitats, with the population-sustaining breeding success in this environment being insufficient on average (<0.8 fledged young per breeding pair). In contrast, in grassland areas with extensive grazing or at secondary sites such as renatured flat banks and islands of former wet gravel extraction sites, a breeding success sufficient for population maintenance is achieved (>0.8 fledged young per breeding pair), even in dry years. It is noteworthy that neither fencing of nests nor targeted predator management (specifically forced fox shooting, etc.) is carried out in the SD, as the predation pressure in natural habitats apparently has less dramatic effects than in areas far from nature or for species in suboptimal habitats. Especially, extensively managed pasture areas and island locations have proven to be significant breeding hotspots (Figure 41). Foxes are rarely hunting for mice on wetlands, and grazing animals such as water buffalo and Highland cattle keep ground predators away and thus serve as natural protection for Lapwing and Snipe. Especially island situations in lakes can provide protection against predation and ensure high breeding success rates. From our experience, water in the landscape is the decisive factor, and nature itself shows us what it needs: In wet springs, the number of breeding pairs doubles (Figure 42) with breeding success rates of over 2.5 fledglings/BP. Even in these successful years, no additional measures such as fencing or predator management were carried out - the water level and the lower intensity of use alone were decisive.

Figure 41: Male Northern Lapwing during the breeding season in extensive pasture with Scottish Highland cattle. Grazing can create optimal vegetation mosaic, accompanied by an increased insect supply due to dung and indirect predator protection provided by the grazing animals, as they keep the fox away.

The ongoing increase in the breeding population of the Snipe in the SD also marks a significant milestone for nature conservation. As an indicator species for the success or failure of conservation measures, the Snipe plays a crucial role. The long-term efforts to clear the core areas of the low moors and to raise the water level in the Leipheimer Moos have had a positive effect on its population (Figure 42). Since the low point of 9 breeding pairs in 1997, a clear recovery has been recorded. By 2015, the number of breeding pairs had risen to 40 and since 2021 to almost 50 (Figure 42). Thus, the historically known values from the 1960s in the SD with 30 to 40 breeding pairs have now been exceeded. It is important to note that the Snipe formerly bred in a more extensive area of the lowlands, but today it is almost exclusively found in the nature reserves. This currently makes it dependent on regular landscape management measures such as mowing of wet meadows and clearing of wet peat bogs and depressions. Only through the rewetting of partial areas, stable (large) sedge fields can slowly develop and serve as essential habitat for the Snipe. The successful population recovery in the SD is all the more significant for species conservation given that the species population declined by 82% nationwide.

Long-term, a balance between predators and prey species in natural (large-scale) landscapes can only be achieved. Developments in the SD demonstrate that fencing and predator management are not necessary when suitable habitats exist. Water in the landscape plays a central role in the breeding success of meadow birds, as it reduces predation pressure. Emphasizing the importance of suitable habitats for breeding success is crucial, along with promoting measures for the protection and creation of such habitats. "Firefighting measures" such as fencing and active predator management may help in the

short term but unfortunately provide a financially favorable and less contentious alternative for policymakers. Therefore, the focus in meadow bird and general species conservation must always be on habitat preservation and creation to ensure long-term and permanent protection. Only then will it be possible to halt the decline in biodiversity.

Figure 42: Development of breeding population in the Schwäbische Donaumoos: a) Lapwing population with targeted management since 2014 and noticeable upward trend, including doubling of breeding pairs in particularly wet springs (blue bars); b) Snipe population with upward trend due to clearing since 1993 and rewetting since 2011.

Further Information

www.arge-donaumoos.de

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Cimiotti, Dominic V., et al. (2022): Wirksamkeit von Maßnahmen für den Kiebitz auf Äckern in Deutschland: Ergebnisse aus dem Projekt „Sympathieträger Kiebitz“ im Bundesprogramm Biologische Vielfalt. *Natur und Landschaft* (12), DOI: 10.19217/NuL2022-12-01, 537-550.

Recommendations

- Restore and maintain wetlands and grasslands with extensive grazing to support higher breeding success and natural predator protection.
- Focus on habitat preservation and creation over temporary measures like fencing and predator management for sustainable conservation.
- Advise farmers on protective measures for breeding sites to ensure agricultural practices support bird conservation.
- Regularly collect data on breeding success to refine and improve conservation strategies.

12.2 Meadow-Breeding-Bird Habitats in the Regentaläue, Cham, Bavaria

Abstract

The “Regentaläue” is a special meadow-bird breeding area in Bavaria. In addition to the still relatively widespread Curlew and Lapwing populations, Black-tailed Godwit and Redshank also breed successfully in this area. The conservation success in the area is the result of a combination of factors, including: a large number of meadows in public ownership where major conservation measures can be implemented, very close monitoring of breeding pairs, and close cooperation with farmers to implement small-scale structural measures such as artificial irrigation of swales in the core zone, and adequate cattle grazing.

Introduction

The “Regentaläue” covers 1,250 hectares (440 hectares of which are in public ownership) along the river Regen and, in addition to Lapwing and Curlew, harbors a relatively good population of Black-tailed Godwit and Redshank. Since 2010 the “Regentaläue” is a Naturschutzgebiet. The area is located in the district of Cham in eastern Bavaria and lies in the Regentaläue. It is part of the Natura2000-network and is characterized by a heterogeneous floodplain landscape with patchy changes in high groundwater levels and regular flooding (Figures 43 and 44). A pond system was created at the beginning of the 16th century and now contributes to its high ecological value. About 85% of the area is grassland, 50% of which are used extensively. The major federal conservation project “Naturschutzgroßprojekt Regentaläue” was carried out from 1989 to 2003 to protect the meadow breeding birds. Thanks to these conditions, and a very close on-site management, and good cooperation with local farmers, the populations of meadow birds are doing comparatively well (when compared to other locations across Bavaria).

Figure 43: The core zone of the nature reserve “Regentalau”. Foto: Peter Zach

Figure 44: The core zone with typical microrelief. Foto: Peter Zach

Method and Approach

In 1989, the Rötelseeweihergebiet and the Regentalau between Cham and Pösing were included in the Federal Government's funding program "Errichtung und Sicherung schutzwürdiger Teile von Natur und Landschaft mit gesamtstaatlich repräsentativer Bedeutung". The district of Cham assumed responsibility for the large-scale nature conservation project. 431 ha of meadows, ponds, and fields were purchased. In total, 9.5 million euros were provided for the project (75 % from the federal government, 15 % by Bavaria and 10 % by the district). As part of the designation of the nature conservation area, an additional approx. 1 million euros were invested in land purchases in 2009. As part of the project, over 30 Swales were created (Swales are grassy depressions that control stormwater velocity and infiltrate runoff where feasible).

The success of this project is based on the high proportion of land owned by the district that allowed the implementation of specific water-management measures in the core area and the establishment of a meadow breeding bird-friendly management. After the project was successfully completed, bird-friendly management practices continue, including good mowing management and continuous irrigation of the artificial shallow pond-systems that are now the basis for success.

Since 2010, the Black-tailed Godwits have been looked after intensively by highly committed volunteers. These volunteers accompany the farmers on the tractors during mowing and monitor the populations daily during the breeding season.

Since that time, short-term protection measures have also been taken: "nest premiums" for postponing mowing around the nest site or compensation payments for larger areas. These measures are designed for meadow areas that are not managed as part of agri-environmental measures. They are financed via "Kleinstmaßnahmen" by the district. Intensive monitoring was key to implement these short-time protection measures to protected clutches, nests, and young chicks.

Since 2014, three large areas (13 hectares, 6 hectares, and 3 hectares, respectively) have been fenced with electric fences every year to protect breeding birds from predators. Intensive hunting of predators, especially foxes, is practiced in the eastern part of the area (private hunting). In addition, four swales are artificially irrigated (all inside the fenced areas): three by overflow water from a pond complex and another by the use of pumps.

Grazing on an area of over 40 hectares with cattle (Rotes Höhenvieh) cannot yet be conclusively evaluated. However, so far, the Lapwing has been the main beneficiary. Black-tailed Godwit and Redshank have not yet used the pastures as a breeding site, curlews only in one case so far. In wet years (e.g., 2021), the willows were occasionally used by Lapwing and Redshank families for foraging. Two traditional Curlew breeding sites within the grazing-area project were abandoned. Songbird species in particular benefit from this grazing, e.g. Red-backed Shrike or migrating Whinchats and Yellow Wagtails. In 2023, the first breeding record of the Stonechat and the 3rd breeding record of the Corn Bunting in the Regental floodplain occurred on a pasture area with a late start of grazing (after June 15).

Results and Conclusion

The curlew population has been stable at a low level for almost 20 years (13 breeding-pairs), and breeding success is relatively adequate to good. The Regentaläue is the most important breeding area for the Black-tailed Godwit in Bavaria. Eight pairs breed in the area (2010: 4 breeding-pairs) and chicks are regularly fledged (Figure 45). With seven to eight breeding pairs, the Regentaläue is also the Bavarian center of distribution for the redshank (Figure 46). There are currently 120 pairs of Lapwings breeding in the area. The Lapwing population has been stable since 2010, with the exception of a low of 97 pairs in 2020 and 85 pairs in 2023. Lapwings also regularly achieve very good breeding success.

Figure 45: Black tailed Godwit breeding population and breeding success in the Regentaläue.

Figure 46: Redshank population in the Regentaläue. The photo on the right shows an adult with chick. Foto: Peter Zach

The number of Common Snipes has fallen continuously since 2010 (to a low of 3 breeding pairs in 2021). Due to the wet spring and the resulting favorable breeding situation in 2023, 12 breeding pairs were counted again in the original breeding areas in. If these areas are structurally developed more favorably (i.e., wetter) again in the future, the population can possibly be maintained or recover. The populations of Whinchat and Meadow Pipit are on the verge of extinction. In 2005, 25 pairs were still breeding here, but now only 1 to 3 pairs remain.

An important result of this project is that outstanding success is possible even in comparatively small and isolated areas thanks to appropriate land access, good biotope design and, above all, intensive management of the breeding pairs.

Further Information

https://www.landkreis-cham.de/media/1332/regentalaue_flyer_projekt.pdf

<https://www.landkreis-cham.de/natur-umwelt/regentalaue/>

Recommendations

- Large areas in public ownership that are managed in a meadow-breeder-friendly way
- Intensive, daily care during the breeding season
- Very good cooperation with local farmers
- A complex of swales, some of which are artificially irrigated
- Predation management through fencing and hunting

12.3 Successful Meadow Bird Conservation in the Dümmer EU Bird Sanctuary

Abstract

Since 1985, a total of 2,500 ha of private land has been purchased and rewetted in the Dümmer SPA. The wet-grassland provides now habitat for more than 20 meadow bird species. Populations of all these species are currently increasing against the national trends observed in Germany. This ongoing conservation effort in the Dümmer SPA constitutes one of the most successful meadow bird conservation examples in Germany and has been achieved through a consistent long-term strategy and a succession of interlinked nature conservation projects.

Introduction

Lower Saxony is considered to be the "meadow bird Federal State" in Germany. It is home to > 50 % of the total German breeding population of meadow breeding birds while covering only 14 % of the total country area (updated according to Belting et al. 2009, Melter 2004, Südbeck & Krüger 2004). Thus, the responsibility of Lower Saxony for the protection and conservation of meadow birds is very high. Due to changes in land use over the last few decades and increased predation rates, meadow bird populations have been declining sharply across Germany. In Lower Saxony, for example, the population of Black-tailed Godwit has fallen by more than 70 % since 1990. The situation is similar for almost all meadow bird species, not only in Lower Saxony but in almost all of northwestern Europe (Gerlach et al. 2019).

Even in Lower Saxony's bird sanctuaries that prioritize meadow bird conservation, the decline continues unabated in the majority of cases. Only in a few areas such as the Fehntjer Tief, the Lower Elbe, and the Dümmer populations have been stabilized. The Dümmer is therefore regarded as a beacon conservation project not only in Lower Saxony but throughout Europe. We believe that lessons learned from this example can provide an important impetus for understanding the ecological complexities of wet-grassland habitats and show how practical solutions for successful meadow bird conservation can look like (Belting 2021).

Method and Approach

The Dümmer is a shallow lake of 16 km², surrounded by around 50 km² of fens. The river Hunte flows through the lake and until 1953 the Hunte and the Dümmer lake regularly flooded the surrounding fen meadows. In 1953, the Hunte was diked together with the Dümmer. This put an end to the regular annual flooding. With the draining of the fens, agriculture was intensified, and many areas are now used for maize cultivation, especially since the 1970s. Formerly structured meadows are now converted to farmland. Further, extensive drainage led to peat mineralization and a strong shrinkage of the peat layer. By 1985, more than ten breeding species of meadow birds had gone locally extinct, and the remaining few species showed severe population declines (Ludwig et al. 1989, Belting 2021).

To improve the ecological conditions of the Dümmer area, 2,500 ha of arable land and farm grassland were acquired from the 1980s onwards, converted into grassland, and extensively rewetted with the aim of developing bird friendly habitats. This took place via six land consolidation procedures in the time period 1985-2007 and was embedded in various large-scale nature conservation projects (Ochsenmoor large-scale nature conservation project (1985-1996), Osterfeiner Moor E+E project (1994-2000), three EU LIFE Nature projects in Lower Saxony (1998-2000, 2002-2007, 2010-2022)). More than € 50 million has been invested in these projects to date. Remaining nature conservation measures are currently being implemented via the LIFE IP GrassBirdHabitats and the LIFE GodwitFlyway projects (both, ending by 2030).

With these projects, a total of 80 km of ditches were equipped by 50 adjustable weirs. 20 km of ditches, some of which are operated by water pumps, were built outside the SPA to prevent the negative effects of waterlogging on neighboring private properties. The dynamic water level that existed before the embankment is now being artificially restored through continuous, seasonally fluctuating water levels. Shallow flooding of the wet-grasslands in the winter months creates optimal bird habitats. A slight lowering of the water level, no more than 30-40 cm below ground level, in early summer enables grassland management. The old farm tracks now function as dams; various polders can be dammed according to the needs of the meadow birds. This creates a mosaic of habitats with different flooding regimes (Figure 47).

Figure 47: Waterlogging regimes in the Dümmer SPA. The diagram shows areas with permanent flooding, others with short- and long-term flooding.

The acquired public land has been leased back to 140 farmers, mainly the former owners. The wettest areas (approx. 150 ha) are not leased and are maintained by the State

Moorland Administration. Mowing and grazing are managed by the Dümmer nature conservation station to create optimal habitat for the breeding of meadow birds. Dry sites without breeding birds can be mowed from the beginning of June or grazed with higher livestock densities. Plots with breeding birds are usually not mowed or are only grazed at low densities. They are mowed after the fledglings have left the areas. This flexible system ensures a high level of acceptance among farmers. Several farmers have set up a new branch of their business to practice this type of farming. The IP LIFE project is currently developing a "meadow birds" result-based payment model for maintaining agricultural management as a key factor in habitat quality (see, case studies).

Results and Conclusion

Following the restoration of regular flooding, the levelling of the soil through low intensity mowing, the homogeneous farmed grassland was transformed into flower-rich wet meadow (Blüml et al. 2012). The populations of almost all staging waders and waterfowl have increased significantly. Numerous bird species that had previously disappeared have returned as breeding birds (Belting 2021). Declining trends of populations of Black-tailed Godwit and Lapwing are stabilized now and have been reversed since 2000 (Figure 48). All meadow birds have shown significant positive population trends and the breeding success confirms that the area has shifted from a population sink to a population source. This means that, on average, more young birds fledge than are required to maintain a stable local population.

Figure 48: Population development of five meadow bird species (Black-tailed Godwit, Lapwing, Curlew, Redshank and Snipe) in the Dümmer SPA between 2000 and 2023 (Source: Datenbank Naturschutzstation Dümmer/NLWKN).

Due to high predation rates in some years that led to large losses of chicks and clutches. We implemented an organized predation management scheme for the last 10 years now. Vole densities are currently much lower than before the rewetting due to winter flooding

and this usually results in low predator densities. However, ground predators, especially red foxes, polecats, stone martens, stoats, raccoons and raccoon dogs, are migrating into the area from neighboring fields. This shows that even relatively large conservation areas like the Dümmer SPA need a predation management scheme and are still too small to prevent negative edge effects.

Site management and monitoring have been key to the success of this conservation efforts. Unexpected and undesirable developments need to be identified early enough to be addressed correctly and this can be only done with through a thorough management and monitoring scheme.

In conclusion, positive population trends alone are not sufficient for long-term and successful meadow bird conservation. These trends need to be accompanied by the continuous management of the SPA for the maintenance of adequate breeding conditions. We identified 10 main management pillars for this success:

- 1) Large areas of continuous wet-grassland
- 2) High openness of the landscape with almost no vertical structures
- 3) Low disturbance
- 4) High water tables with temporarily flooded areas (i.e., open shallow pools)
- 5) Low or intermediate trophic level of soil
- 6) Mowing and grazing compliant to nesting distribution and timing
- 7) Sufficient grazing intensity or late mowing to maintain an optimal vegetation structure before winter
- 8) High heterogeneity of the landscape at the parcel level
- 9) Moderate predation rate
- 10) Well organized guardianship and monitoring.

These 10 management measures need to be applied simultaneously to ensure the success of conservation measures.

Further Information

<http://www.grassbirdhabitats.eu>

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Recommendations

The 10 management measures identified in this case study need to be applied simultaneously to ensure the success of conservation efforts. Often, missing one or two of these measures is sufficient to jeopardize the success of conservation efforts.

12.4 Management in the „Beltringharder Koog“: Combination of Measures for Habitat Improvement and Predation Management in a Natura 2000 Site at the West Coast of Schleswig-Holstein

Abstract

The Beltringharder Koog – both nature conservation and Natura 2000 site – is one of Schleswig-Holsteins most important bird sanctuaries. Therefore, site management aims at the optimization of breeding habitats for meadow and coastal birds. Due to a holistic management which includes aspects of predation management, breeding bird populations of lapwings, black-tailed godwit and common ringed plover are increasing.

Introduction

Schleswig-Holstein has a special responsibility for the protection of meadow and coastal bird species since an important percentage of the German population breeds here.

The Beltringharder Koog is part of the Natura 2000 network and the largest terrestrial nature conservation site in Schleswig-Holstein (Figure 49). It has an outstanding importance for endangered breeding birds of wet grasslands and coastal areas. Therefore, the management focuses on the improvement and preservation of favorable habitat conditions for these species (see management plan Kühl 2021).

The Beltringharder Koog (BHK) is divided into two parts: in the Northern part, north of the river Arlau, approximately 1.900ha, habitat management measures are conducted, and the southern part of approximately 1.500 ha, which is dedicated as wilderness area with no habitat management measures.

The Beltringharder Koog was one of the project areas of the LIFE Limosa project (2012-2023).

Figure 49: Map showing the Beltringharder Koog in Schleswig-Holstein, source wirbi.de.

Method and Approach

The main management measures are:

- Intensive monitoring of the breeding birds as important basis for the management of the nature conservation area
- Establishment of appropriate water levels before and during the breeding season by targeted accumulation of rainwater
- Creating shallow water zones
- Prevention of succession and reduction of vertical structures (removing of trees, bushes, scrubs)
- Seasonal extensive grazing by robust cattle, additionally with sheep in some areas
- Maintaining open areas by partial mulching after breeding season
- Predation management measures

Some of these measures are described in detail below:

- **Water management**

During the winter months, rainwater accumulates in areas where dams and drainpipes have been installed. During accumulation, strong impact of waves must be avoided. In spring, a gradual lowering of the water level provides ideal habitat conditions for breeding birds.

Additionally, a continuous improvement of ditches is necessary for irrigation and/or drainage of the Beltringharder Koog. The edges of the ditches are flattened so that breeding birds and their chicks are able to use the mud zones of the ditches for foraging.

During droughts in the breeding season, water is pumped into the breeding area by mobile solar to create shallow water zones in at least a small local area. However, the mobility of the solar pump is restricted and placement at different locations is rather laborious.

- **Extensive grazing**

The managed part of the Beltringharder Koog is grazed by robust cattle (0,5-1 cattle/ha) and additionally by sheep in some areas in later summer months. The grazing creates different areas with different abundance of nutrients, fauna and flora as well as open areas without higher vegetation and therefore optimal conditions for the breeding meadow birds. Areas with high vegetation density must be prevented to reduce hiding places for mammalian predators like foxes and raccoon dogs.

Currently, grazing starts around 1st of June depending on breeding action and reed growth and ends around 1st of October. Areas with high and intensive density and growth of reed are grazed earlier if possible (April/beginning of May). Grazing with sheep starts around mid of July in some areas.

- **Mulching**

Mulching after breeding season is necessary in areas, where intensive plant growth especially of reed occurs. Mulching reduces hiding sites for mammalian predators. Simultaneously, small scale structures like small, short and light reed-isles should be maintained to function as small hiding places for birds, especially for the chicks. Mulching is normally conducted by the leaseholder after the breeding season in August/September. In areas which are too wet, difficult to access and sensitive, special vehicles for landscape protection are used like tracked mowers or the motor mower `Brielmaier`.

- **Predation management**

Following measures are conducted:

- Reduction of reed and bushes to reduce hiding sites for mammalian predators
- Installation of mobile and permanent predator exclusion electric fences
- Active predation management by hunting

An active predation management project funded by the ministry of environment of Schleswig-Holstein started in October 2021. In this project, a professional hunter conducts hunting-related predation management, supported by regional hobby hunters. These measures mainly include hunting with traps and hide hunts. Before the start of the breeding season, some areas with dense vegetation cover are monitored with a drone with a thermographic camera to find raccoon dogs and foxes.

Additionally, since 2025 restricted hunting related management measures are conducted in the peripheral areas of the wilderness area bordering important breeding sites of ground nesting birds (MEKUN 2024). Observations with wildlife cameras documented an influx of

raccoon dogs and foxes from the wilderness area; which predate the eggs of breeding birds in the managed area.

Results and Conclusion

Due to these management measures – combined habitat improvement measures and predation management measures – key species such as black-tailed godwits, lapwings (Figure 50), and oystercatcher show an increase in breeding population and breeding success (see, Cimiotti 2024).

Figure 50: Number of breeding pairs of Lapwings (left) and black-tailed Godwits (right) in the grassland habitats north of the river Arlau in the Beltringharder Koog.

Further Information

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Mekun 2024: 2. Teilfortschreibung des Managementplans für das Fauna-Flora-Habitat-Gebiet DE-0916-391 „NTP S-H Wattenmeer und angrenzende Küstengebiete“ und das Europäische Vogelschutzgebiet DE-0916-491 „Ramsar-Gebiet Schleswig-Holsteinisches Wattenmeer und angrenzende Küstengebiete“ jeweils Teilgebietsbereich „Naturschutzgebiet Beltringharder Koog“ in Hinblick auf das Prädationsmanagement zum Schutz von Wiesen- und Küstenvögeln in der südlichen Sukzessionszone des Beltringharder Kooges. (only in German)

Recommendations

- Provide wet grasslands with short sward
- Minimize predation pressure by hunting management
- Protect optimal breeding habitats with electrical fences

- Evaluate management measures with an ongoing monitoring
- Never give up!

12.5 Result-Oriented Species Protection Program for the Protection of Meadow Birds on Private Agricultural Lands in Schleswig-Holstein

Abstract

In 2024, the Collaborative Meadow Bird Protection program in Schleswig-Holstein successfully protected over 1,400 meadow bird nests, focusing mainly on Lapwings, Eurasian Oystercatchers, and Common Snipes. The program relied on timely communication between farmers and conservationists, where local project sponsors, and more importantly, regional area supervisors play a central role. The program involved 177 farmers and included long-term monitoring and specific projects addressing unique conservation challenges.

Introduction

A significant proportion of the populations of meadow-breeding waders occur on privately owned grassland areas in Schleswig-Holstein. Therefore, a protection concept adapted to agriculture is important for the conservation of these threatened species. A collaborative Meadow Bird Protection (GWS) has been established as a suitable species protection program. With the help of both voluntary area supervisors and professional experts, nests and broods can be protected from losses due to mowing or cattle trampling. If a nest is discovered on a grassland area by the area supervisors, they contact the farmers, discuss the agricultural restrictions necessary to protect the nest, and offer the farmers compensation for adhering to the agreements. Once the birds have left the area, there are no further restrictions. The program is financed by the Ministry for Energy Transition, Climate Protection, Environment, and Nature of the state of Schleswig-Holstein.

This species protection program was already established in the late 1990s in the Eider-Treene-Sorge lowlands (ETS). It is now applied in nine different areas. It primarily benefits threatened species such as the Lapwing (Red List D 2), Common Snipe (Red List D 1), and Black-tailed Godwit (Red List D 1) (Ryslavy et al. 2020). These species have a significant share of the national breeding population in Schleswig-Holstein. Additionally, particularly endangered migratory bird species such as the Eurasian Oystercatcher, Common Redshank (Red List D 2), Corncrake (Red List D 1), and Short-eared Owl (Red List D 1), as well as a number of songbirds breeding in grasslands, are also considered. Since 2024, nests on arable land within these nine areas in Schleswig-Holstein can also be included in the program.

Method and Approach

In the Collaborative Meadow Bird Protection (GWS), only areas where a significant number of meadow birds breed on private grassland and arable land are considered. Agriculture should be a cause of loss or danger for the nests and broods, and the habitat should, in principle, be suitable for breeding species such as Lapwings, Common Snipes, and Black-tailed Godwits, among others. Since the GWS relies on timely communication between farmers and conservationists, there should be a local project sponsor, but more importantly, regional area supervisors. Project sponsors can be regional associations, local initiatives, or

similar entities. They apply for funding, manage the disbursement of funds, and provide a subject report. The area supervisors are familiar with the current breeding and family habitats and coordinate the management restrictions with the farmers so that the birds can breed undisturbed and raise their chicks. Once the birds have left the area, the farmer is released for further management restrictions. The commitment is only for the current breeding season, as breeding areas can change the following year. In most areas, at least some of the supervisors are professional ornithologists. The coordination of all project areas is carried out by the Michael Otto Institute in the NABU.

In 2024, the GWS was implemented in nine project areas in Schleswig-Holstein: Föhr, Langenhorn, Amrum, Pellworm, ETS, Haaler Au, Mieleniederung, Windbergener Niederung, and Oberalsterniederung (Figure 51). In 2025, additional areas in the vicinity of Haseldorf (Elbe) will be included.

Figure 51: Location of the project areas of the Collaborative Meadow Bird Protection in Schleswig-Holstein in 2024

The amount of compensation payments is based on the area occupied by meadow birds and the number of breeding pairs, as well as the specific restrictions regarding agricultural operations. Additionally, since 2024, a distinction has been made between organically and conventionally managed farms, with the former receiving a lower rate, similar to agri-environment schemes.

Results and Conclusion

In 2024, over 1,400 meadow bird nests were protected from agricultural losses in Schleswig-Holstein as part of the Collaborative Meadow Bird Protection (GWS). The focus was primarily on Lapwings, Eurasian Oystercatchers, and Black-tailed Godwit (Table 17).

Table 17: Number of protected meadow bird broods in Schleswig-Holstein. Others include: Corncrake, Short-eared Owl, Meadow Pipit, Yellow Wagtail, Whinchat, Mallard, Reed Bunting, Stonechat, Corn Bunting, Shoveler, Pheasant, Gadwall, Little Ringed Plover).

Species	Number of roTECTED broods in 2024	Average over the last 10 years
Northern Lapwing	826	519
Oystercatcher	340	162
Black-tailed Godwit	113	137
Curlew	54	59
Redshank	29	46
Other	57	-

In 2024, 177 farmers participated in the Collaborative Meadow Bird Protection (GWS). The project is accompanied by long-term efficiency monitoring in Meggerkoog (Eider-Treene-Sorge lowlands) and several other detailed projects focusing on specific protection aspects, such as predation on islands, cooperation projects with hunters, testing and implementation of predation fences, and studies on chick survival rates.

References and Further Information

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Recommendations

- A collaborative meadow bird protection program requires dedicated field contacts for effective monitoring and management.
- Such programs are vital the preservation of meadow birds in agricultural land.
- The program has the long-term benefits of increasing awareness and promoting sustainable practices among farmers.

12.6 Predation Management in the Special Protection Area “Moore und Heiden des Westlichen Münsterlandes”, North Rhine-Westphalia

Abstract

The Special Protection Area (SPA) “Moore und Heiden des westlichen Münsterlandes” (Natura 2000-Nr. DE-3807-401) is home to one of the last two vital subpopulations of Black-Tailed Godwit (*Limosa limosa*) of North-Rhine Westphalia, in addition to other important populations of meadow breeding birds. Impaired habitat quality and quantity caused by anthropogenic influences, as well as an increasing predation, are considerably affecting the breeding success of this species. Within the course of the project “LIFE Wiesenvögel NRW”, alongside comprehensive habitat optimization, a predation management consisting of various measures is currently being implemented.

Introduction

Special Protection Areas (SPAs) are the last refuge habitats for meadow birds, especially for Black-tailed Godwits (BTG, *Limosa limosa*) and Eurasian Curlew (*Numenius arquata*). In North-Rhine Westphalia (NRW), nearly all Curlews breed in SPAs, while small relict populations can still be found in intensive agricultural landscapes due to site fidelity. BTG populations with more than ten breeding pairs occur only in two SPAs, with the “Moore und Heiden des westlichen Münsterlandes” (MHWM) being one of them. In 2024, sixteen pairs attempted to raise chicks. Thus, this area carries the potential to re-establish a self-sustaining breeding population as a source for the eventual spreading of this endangered species nationwide. To improve the habitats of BTG and other meadow birds, the state-owned area of this SPA is extensively managed with usage regulations. Mowing is restricted to specific intervals and habitat improvements, like the cutting of trees and shrubs, are conducted regularly and supervised by the biological station (Biologische Station Zwillbrock e.V.). Nevertheless, all measures take time in organization, financing and implementation whilst the BTG populations in NRW and Germany are still rapidly declining.

The overall breeding success in the MHWM SPA is heavily affected by predation. Surveys with camera traps of Curlew nests revealed high predation rates (from 2022-2024, 62-71%), with Red Foxes (*Vulpes vulpes*) and Martens (*Martes sp.*) being responsible for most of the nest losses. The monitoring of fifteen breeding pairs of Curlew showed that only one to five fledged chicks are reared each year. Furthermore, flocks of Carrion Crows (*Corvus corone*) have been regularly observed preying on nests, especially those of BTG.

Our observation showed that habitat improvement is insufficient to achieve a stable population of BTG, it has to be complemented by the implementation of a predation management program. Thus, in the framework of the project “LIFE Wiesenvögel NRW”, passive and active measures for predation management are being implemented, as well as the monitoring of breeding birds, the predation of nests, and predator species. The decision to actively and lethally remove predators instead of using only passive measures was taken after careful consideration of the experiences of other meadow breeding projects such as “Wiesenvögel LIFE” in Lower Saxony or “LIFE Limosa” in Schleswig-Holstein. The fencing of breeding areas is costly and time-intensive, and only small areas can be covered. Thus, an intensive hunting of predators (especially by trapping and subsequent ethical killing) in the breeding areas of meadow birds has been proven to be indispensable to preserve the local populations of species like the BTG.

Method and Approach

The MHWM is divided into several hunting grounds with different tenants. To establish a predator management based on concrete pipe traps (Figure 52), the project’s professional hunter (temporarily employed for the project duration) and the Biological Station Zwillbrock e.V. organized an exchange with the hunting tenants. Afterwards, each hunting ground and its tenants were visited by the professional hunter and the regional project employee to select sites for concrete-pipe traps and camera traps. Furthermore, the camera traps were prepared for a standardized predator monitoring at game passes from the 1st of February until the 30th of April. After that, tenants were offered mandatory courses for permission to carry out trapping, with five courses taking place from 2022 to 2024. Contact with the hunting tenants is continuous, and a joint meeting is also convened once a year to discuss problems, progress, and plans. In MHWM, 26 concrete pipe traps (with adjustable trigger weight, raccoon safety devices, and catch detector) were installed on around 1 400 ha. Those traps are active during the permitted hunting periods in accordance with the Federal State hunting law.

Figure 52: An adult Black-Tailed Godwit (left photo) and one of its predators, a Red Fox (right photo), shortly before entering a concrete-pipe trap.

In addition to the traps, hunting from hide takes place, sometimes in parallel across hunting grounds. The previously prohibited hunting of Crows was introduced due to the fact that since 2022 an increasing number of young Crows and, from 2023 on, breeding adult Crows have preyed and specialized on BTG clutches and chicks in particular. Lease agreements were amended and an exemption from the landscape plan was obtained.

Hunting is now possible in accordance with the entire hunting season of the State Hunting Act. In two exceptional cases in 2024, hunting of non-breeding young Crows was also possible during the breeding season under the supervision of the Biological Station. A sufficient distance between shooting and meadow bird clutches was ensured and the behavior of the meadow birds was observed during shooting to exclude disturbance-caused nest losses.

Due to financial and personnel limitations, protective fencing is currently only being used in a small area. However, as breeding success must be increased in the short term in order to maintain the breeding bird populations and predator management can take time in showing significant effects, the fences are used as a “fire-fighting” measure. Every year, around 15 hectares of focal breeding area are fenced with electric sheep fences, divided into three fences within a sub-area of 250 hectares. The power supply is provided by a combination of batteries and solar cells, which guarantees at least three kilovolts on the strands.

The monitoring of both meadow birds (breeding pairs, breeding success) and predators (counting of individuals per species at game passes, Figure 53) is conducted yearly to be able to determine the effects of the predator control measures.

Further, in order to create awareness of the necessity of the measures, it is openly communicated that predator management takes place in the SPA. Moreover, the regional nature conservation associations were invited to an information exchange and belong to the regional project advisory board.

Figure 53: Monitoring of predators at game passes from the 1st of February to the 30th of April each year (2022-2024). Definition of an event: An individual that moves in front of the camera within 5 minutes and triggers several times is counted as one event. If several individuals of a species are in front of the camera at the same time, each individual is counted separately. Thus, $n = x$ corresponds to the sum of all predator events during the exposure period. “Raptor” corresponds to the sum of birds of prey including Crows. The high numbers of this category at two sites display flocks of Crows.

Results and Conclusion

In the project areas, Red Foxes, Stone Martens, Polecats and Crows in particular have a major influence on the birds’ reproductive success. The recorded data provide evidence of very high populations of these predators. In the MHWM, the all-year-round protection of Red Foxes in the directly neighboring Netherlands adds to the local populations and there is strong evidence of continuous migration of foxes from the Netherlands towards the MHWM.

The camera monitoring results confirm the suitability of the sites where concrete-pipe trap were installed, with regard to the use of space by predatory mammals. Concrete-pipe traps usually must weather for about a year after installation, as their odor can lead to avoidance by predators. Although, it is still possible for inexperienced animals to be caught with a bait, Red Foxes in particular can mostly only be caught from the second year onwards. As a result, only four Red Foxes were caught so far (2024), in addition to four Polecats and 22 Stone Martens. However, the total number of eliminated Red Foxes was significantly higher because of the additional hide hunting. This was remarkable to notice, as the tenants are only hunting on a voluntary basis.

Due to the short period of time since the introduction of predation management, it is not yet possible to make any reliable statements on the effects of hunting. However, it is noticeable that the number of predation incidents by Red Foxes in 2024 has decreased

significantly compared to the two previous years. The upcoming trapping season will show how efficient the concrete-pipe traps are after weathering and whether any adjustments need to be made. As predators are constantly migrating into the protected area, predation management is expected to be a long-term task. In order to hunt more efficiently, the working hunting tenants need to be supported by a permanently employed professional hunter across all hunting grounds. Such an approach has already been successful in projects such as at the Dümmer (Lower Saxony, Loonstra 2024). Invasive predator species like the Raccoon and Raccoon Dog are also monitored. These two species need to be controlled not only with regard to meadow birds, but other endangered species, too.

From 2022 to 2024, 35 meadow birds bred within fenced areas and 25 nests hatched. Losses occurred by Martens due to a temporary voltage loss and predation by Crows. The successful predation attempts after voltage loss indicated learning effects, this applies also to Crows which focus on the predation of birds inside the fences. Accordingly, the most sustainable solution, or at least a necessary supplement for the installation of fences, is the hunting of the respective predators. Regarding predatory mammals, intensive monitoring and maintenance of the fences are necessary to prevent possible loopholes as seen by the Martens.

During the Crow hunting within a breeding season, only twelve non-breeding individuals could be shot in 2024. Although the flight paths of the flocks had been scouted beforehand, behavioral changes occurred due to subsequently cultivated fields in the surrounding area. However, it was possible to observe a temporary avoidance behavior of the Crows after the two days (12th of April, and 16th of May) of hunting. At the start of the regular hunting season in 2024, more than fifty individuals could be shot during a hunt across all territories.

In summary, intensive hunting of predators is essential to achieve the legally binding objectives of the SPA. Because of the high densities of predators and low hatching and fledging success of meadow birds, swift actions needed to be taken, and an active predator management program had to be implemented. In addition to predator management, habitat optimization measures must also continue to be carried out. However, it is important to underline that apart from random observations, the causes of chick loss are still a knowledge gap that should be further investigated.

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Project Homepage: <https://www.life-wiesenvoegel.nrw.de/>

Homepage Biologische Station Zwillbrock e.V.: <https://www.bszwillbrock.de/>

Recommendations

- Cooperation with hunting tenants and support from professional hunters are necessary to implement a successful predator management plan.
- Additional fencing is often required for small core areas.

- Transparency and communication with all stakeholders are necessary.
- Research into the causes of chick losses is urgently needed.
- Long-term implementation of all measurements including monitoring is necessary for successful conservation.

12.7 Predation Management of Hedgehogs Through Hedgehog-Dogs on East Frisian Islands

Abstract

Islands are important refuge habitats for endangered breeding bird species, such as the black-tailed godwit (*Limosa limosa*), pied avocet (*Recurvirostra avosetta*) and northern lapwing (*Vanellus vanellus*). Specifically, the East Frisian Islands within the Lower Saxon Wadden Sea National Park maintain important source populations of key species through their naturally predator free environment and high-quality habitats. To further improve habitats of specifically grassland breeding species, measures to regulate the water level and vegetation cover of grassland were realised. However, breeding success was heavily influenced by predation pressure of immigrated and introduced mammalian predators such as the fox, ferrets and hedgehogs. Thus, an intense predation management was initiated on Norderney, followed by other islands. Surprisingly, hedgehogs were identified as major predators of clutches and thus measures focussing on relocating hedgehogs to the mainland were enforced. Specialised hedgehog-dogs were trained to locate the animals with high efficiency. The measures successfully decimated the hedgehog population and direct improvements on breeding success were recorded. The monitoring and management of hedgehog populations continues in order to avoid the initiation of new reproduction hotspots and to ensure a sustainable improvement of the breeding success of endangered bird species.

Introduction

The Wadden Sea National Park protects an internationally important ecosystem, providing diverse and dynamic habitats spanning mudflats, salt marshes, dunes and beaches for millions of migrating, roosting and breeding birds. Europe-wide, the populations of grassland and ground breeding birds are strongly declining as a direct consequence of intensified agricultural management during the last decades, characterised by intense drainage. Thus, in Germany favourable breeding conditions are mostly limited to protected areas with a high relative importance of Lower Saxony.

Due to the special protection status as a National Park, the Wadden See and its islands have the responsibility to maintain and establish self-sustaining breeding populations of characteristic species, ideally with an excessive breeding success and thus functioning as a source population that can buffer losses on the mainland. On the islands within the National Park, grassland birds such as the Bar-tailed Godwit *Limosa lapponica* breed in former salt meadows that were enclosed by dikes. This created polder areas that are now extensively used by cattle or mowing while making sure land use matches the breeding ecology of focal species.

In the frame of the LIFE IP GrassBirdHabitats and LIFE Meadow Birds projects different measures to improve the habitat quality were carried out on East Frisian Islands Borkum, Norderney and Langeoog, including the management of water level and vegetation growth. These areas on the islands are important refuges for ground breeding birds, as mammalian predators are naturally absent. Observations of pied avocets (Figure 54) on islands in small lakes in Schleswig-Holstein suggested a hatching success fluctuating around 80% (Hötker and Segebade, 2000), and identified foxes as a main predator of breeding colonies specifically on the mainland (Hötker and Segebade, 2000). Thus, a hatching success of 80 % was assumed as a baseline for colonies in optimal habitat on the East Frisian Islands as well. However, hatching success and predation pressure varies tremendously between different colonies in similar settings, with mainly avian predators and extremely low breeding success in the Leyhörn avocet colonies on the mainland (Freise et al., 2006). Different studies do however agree, that predation is a main reason for clutch loss, followed by flooding and unfavourable weather condition. Contrary to the assumption of naturally predator-free islands, hatching and breeding success on Norderney, the first island with frequent monitoring of breeding success, were not sufficient to maintain the population of avocets with an unexpected low average breeding success of 0.08 (from 2006 - 2012). A breeding success of 0.4 fledgelings per pair is required to maintain the population (Freise et al., 2006). The predation pressure was classified as high, apparently endangering local breeding birds. Due to these findings, the Lower Saxon Wadden Sea National Park administration decided to act and investigated predation abundance and pressure, identifying and executing measures against predators on several islands and monitoring of characteristic ground breeding species.

Figure 54: Low breeding success of pied avocets initiated the predation management on East Frisian islands. Foto Rudolf Großmann.

Method and Approach

In 2008, the predation management was initiated on Norderney, successfully targeting mainly ferrets, cats and rats through live traps. During the first years, the importance of hedgehogs as nest predators was realised and concepts to eliminate this species from the island were enforced since 2010. The management was accompanied by informative meetings for the public to increase acceptance. The project area initially spanned the eastern island but was then extended over the whole island, including areas that are part of the National Park but excluding human settlement areas (Figure 55). The predation management was accompanied by a breeding success monitoring to evaluate the efficiency of measures.

Figure 55: Positions of hedgehog findings on Norderney from 2010 to 2023. Darker colors indicate a more recent finding. It is evident that eastern areas were first successfully freed from hedgehog populations, while recent findings concentrate around human settlements. Systematic monitoring took place in the red project area, while hedgehogs encountered by chance outside this area were also translocated to the mainland. A concentration along streets can be noticed (map provided by BIOS)

The goal of the first project phase was the reduction of hedgehog population and the establishment of hedgehog-free areas. This was accomplished by a combination of live traps, spotlight assessments/ thermal imaging cameras and hedgehog-dogs initially from August to October and later starting in April. The baited live traps were installed in regular intervals across the project area and proved to be especially effective with high hedgehog densities during the first years of the management. The spotlight was used on roads and in open habitats by three to seven persons that followed transects in 20-50 m distance, and later in the project thermal imaging cameras complemented this search. This method was more efficient with declining hedgehog densities. The hedgehog-dogs were first introduced into the managing plan in 2014.

Two dogs (Figure 56) were specifically trained for the hedgehog search in protected areas that are populated by sensitive breeding birds. The dogs were alternated after every two hours of work to avoid exhaustion. This also limited the search area investigated by the dogs which was thus concentrated on forest and strongly vegetated areas where flashlights were less useful. After experiences from the first year, the dogs were used during the night and without leashes, as these proved to be obstructive in dense vegetation. Dogs were permitted to search an area of 30 to 50 m around the trainer along transects of 50-100 m distance.

Figure 56: Hedgehog-dog and trainer (Foto by BIOS).

The specific number of dog-operations and area of operations per season depended on experiences from the previous year. For example, in 2016 at the beginning of the dog-project, 31 operations were conducted and in 2023 only nine were needed. This reflects the successful elimination of hedgehog populations on the island (Figure 57). The focus areas were shifted from the eastern island at the beginning of the management to measures on all National Park areas on the island during phase 1, to a focus on areas adjacent to human settlements in the second project phase which aims to prevent reimmigration into hedgehog free areas (Figure 55). In the last five years (2019-2023) only areas close to the settlements were completely checked to prevent immigration while all other project areas (except for the most eastern area) were checked partially.

Hedgehogs that were collected during the management were relocated to the mainland and released in suitable habitat in agreement with the local nature conservation authority. The age and sex were determined if possible.

The management was transferred to the islands Borkum since 2013 and Langeoog since 2017 as well, which have important breeding populations of key species such as the black-tailed godwit. Since most data are available for Norderney, this report focusses on results from this island.

Figure 57: Hedgehog counts in the different project areas from 2010 to 2023. Across Norderney the management successfully reduced and eliminated population in the project area as well as outside the project area (red). Transparent lines and points indicate an incomplete sampling of the area, while solid points and lines indicate a complete sampling.

Results and Conclusion

Introduced and immigrated predators (specifically ferrets and hedgehogs) were successfully reduced as a consequence of the management. After the first years of concentrating on the eastern island, it was evident that hedgehogs rapidly repopulated the project areas. Thus, areas across the whole island were targeted at the same time to increase the efficiency. Specifically, areas close to wooded and densely vegetated habitats were identified as reproduction hotspots and roads or other linear structures facilitated reimmigration to more eastern project areas. Already after the first year of using trained dogs, the dogs proved to be very efficient in subsequent years for finding hedgehogs, specifically in densely vegetated areas. Since 2016, most findings were contributed to the dogs. However, it was noticed how hedgehogs were continuously able to spread from the town area to surrounding areas. As private property was not entered and individuals in the town were only collected upon chance encounters, this incomplete coverage of a major reproductive hotspot will likely require a continuous monitoring of hedgehog populations on the islands. However, despite these difficulties, the hedgehog population was extremely reduced and reproducing populations (classified by sex ratio and number of juveniles) were mostly eliminated. The effect of the management was immediately visible through increasing breeding success in avocets which were monitored over the longest consecutive period (2006-2023), but also in black-tailed godwits and oystercatchers (Figure 58). Since 2012, no predation events through hedgehogs or ferrets were recorded and hatching success of avocets was mostly between 65,5 % and 85,5 % from 2012 to 2017, close to the expected value of 80 %. However, in the winter of 2016/2017 foxes immigrated from the mainland, resulting in an immediate reduction of breeding success in avocets. A separate management of the fox population was initiated and breeding success started to increase again (Figure 58a). For both the oystercatcher (Figure 58b) and black-tailed godwit (Figure 58c) breeding success increased considerably after the management onset on a representative monitoring area (Grohdepolder), however only data

from 2008 are available before the measures were enforced. For the godwits however, breeding success seems to decline steadily after the fox invasion, although hatching success was close to 90 % (after Mayfield 1975) in the last five years. Other factors next to predation pressure such as intense weather events, flooding and yet undetermined reasons may drive this trend.

Figure 58: Breeding success of characteristic species on Norderney. Breeding success (in juveniles per pair) of avocets (A) was monitored on the whole island. Low breeding success in 2011 and 2015 was due to flooding events. Data for oystercatcher (B) and black-tailed godwits (C) are representative for the Grohdepolder. The dotted blue line represents the species-specific breeding success value necessary to sustain the population. Blue bars indicate that this value was exceeded and grey suggests insufficient breeding success.

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Recommendations

In conclusion, the monitoring has shown the sensitivity of ground breeding species to the introduction of mammalian predators, but also the effectiveness of predation management using a combination of life traps, infrared/flashlights and trained dogs was demonstrated and proved to be very successful. Especially the dogs increased the efficiency considerably and targeting all project areas in the same season (i.e. not only focussing on eastern areas) from the beginning of the breeding season was an important improvement of the methodology. However, due to restricted accessibility in the town area and the suspected remains of hedgehogs in gardens, reimmigration to sensitive breeding habitats is expected. Thus, constant monitoring of the population on a low level (e.g. through infrared drones and flashlight) in the following years is necessary. As a result of the experiences and finetuning of methods on Norderney, the hedgehog management on Borkum and Langeoog was very efficient and populations declined rapidly with no more predation events on godwit eggs recorded.

12.8 Telemetry Studies on the Curlew *Numenius arquata* in Bavaria

Abstract

In order to find out more about the habitat use of curlews in the Bavarian breeding areas, a multi-year GPS telemetry project has been implemented by the LBV since 2016. In this project, over 40 adults and almost-fledged curlews were tagged. In 2019, the additional tagging of curlew chicks with radio-transmitters allowed for exploring this early life stage and the main causes of chick loss. These projects were carried out by the Landesbund für Vogel- und Naturschutz in various breeding areas across Bavaria and financed by multiple funding entities.

Introduction

The Eurasian Curlew *Numenius arquata* (Figure 59) is a flagship species of particular interest for Bavarian meadow bird conservation. To counter the consistently low reproductive success, many different conservation efforts and projects are deployed in the Bavarian breeding areas (von Lindeiner et al., 2023). Two different telemetry studies on Curlews are currently underway in Bavaria by the Landesbund für Vogel- und Naturschutz (LBV), using different methods and targeting different life stages. Both studies aim to shed light on local and supra-regional causes of population decline and consequently derive efficient protective

measures. In the first project funded by the Bavarian Nature Conservation Fund, over 40 curlews have been tagged with modern GPS transmitters since 2016.

Figure 59: Curlew with a GPS-tag in the Regentaläue in May 2024. Photo: P. Zach

In the second project, curlew chicks are fitted with radio telemetry transmitters to find out more about their movements and habitat utilization. This second project is financed by various annual funding at a local level, coming from the nature conservation administration (Higher nature conservation authorities). Both projects are carried out in several meadow breeding areas in Bavaria and are made possible through cooperation with local stakeholders (such as Lower nature conservation authorities, landscape conservation organizations, “Gebietsbetreuer” (www.gebietsbetreuung.bayern), and the many active members in the LBV.)

Method and Approach

GPS-Telemetry: The advent of modern, solar-powered lightweight GPS transmitters—capable of collecting and transmitting data for years—enabled the launch of this research project in 2016. As part of this project, over 40 adults and almost-fledged curlews were tagged. The questions to be addressed included the analysis of migratory threats and the implementation of protective measures at stopover sites, wintering areas, and along migration routes. Additionally, the focus was on tracking the behavior and movement of Bavarian juvenile birds in subsequent breeding seasons and understanding the causes of mortality. The study also examined post-breeding movement patterns of adult curlews compared to juveniles, as well as their habitat requirements in the breeding areas. A project steering group consisted of representatives from all participating regional nature

conservation authorities, the Bavarian State Office for the Environment, and the Nature Conservation Fund. Regional experts were also involved.

The project ends in 2024 and scientific publications and a comprehensive final report are currently being prepared (already published: Mateos Perez Bianco De Araújo et al., 2024; the project is also part of these international publications: Donnez et al., 2023; Pederson et al., 2022).

Radio-Telemetry: Curlew chicks were fitted with small radio transmitters immediately after hatching (Figure 60). From then on, their locations were checked daily. The chicks were located using hand-held antennas. In two study areas, we additionally used stationary radio telemetry technology (by trackIT Systems).

Figure 60: Curlew-chick with small radio-transmitter. Photo: M. Schwark.

This project started in the “Altmühltal” in 2019 and was implemented in three other areas in the following years. The reason for initiating these projects was the high loss rate of chicks due to unknown causes. The focus of these projects was therefore, 1) analyzing habitat use and preferred habitat structure until the young birds fledge and 2) the causes of chick losses (Figure 61). In addition to the knowledge gained, the location data of the curlew families are a fundamental basis for short-term mowing management. Particularly in areas with small fields, some of which are mowed frequently and by many different farmers, losses due to mowing can be successfully and efficiently prevented.

Figure 61: Locating the curlew chicks with a hand antenna (left). Often only the transmitter and the rings are found when chicks are predated (right). Photos: V. Rupprecht

Results and Conclusion

GPS-Telemetry: By tracking curlews in six different project areas and focusing in particular on juvenile individuals, we gained many exciting insights and findings. The full scope cannot be presented here, but a few examples are given below: At the local level, for example, feeding areas could be identified and different structures and sub-areas proved to be particularly important during the various phases of the breeding period (Figure 62). By tagging almost-fledged juveniles, it was also possible to show that curlews are still highly vulnerable to predation even during the fledging phase. We show, therefore, that significantly fewer juveniles actually leave the breeding grounds successfully contrary to what was previously assumed. The curlews remain in the wintering area in the 2nd calendar year and sometimes show extensive exploration behaviour on the breeding sites in the 3rd and 4th calendar years. Breeding attempts are the exception during this period. The data also showed different requirements for nocturnal resting sites across the breeding season between adults and juveniles. While good and nearby overnight roosting sites were identified in a few meadow breeding areas, the curlews from other areas sometimes traveled long distances to nocturnal roosting sites. A clear potential for improvement was identified here. In addition to breeding and feeding areas, nocturnal resting areas should also be considered in future planning.

Figure 62: Example of a roosting site of Curlews on a cornfield. The points show the GPS data of two different curlew individuals. Up to 80 curlews, almost the entire local population, were counted on site at dusk. Map © Datenquellen: Bayerische Vermessungsverwaltung, Europäische Union, enthält Copernicus Sentinel-2 Daten 2018, verarbeitet durch das Bundesamt für Kartographie und Geodäsie (BKG)

Radio-Telemetry: Here, too, only a selection of the extensive insights and results of the radio telemetry can be presented (Figure 63). Firstly, in addition to the scientific findings, radio telemetry also has an important function in the management of mowing. Particularly in the case of chicks, which become increasingly mobile after the third week of life, it became apparent that some losses could not have been prevented without telemetry. It was also found that, when danger (such as an agricultural machine) approaches, the chicks, especially in dense vegetation, tend to crouch rather than run away until they are fully capable of flight. In addition to the areas mown frequently and early for silage, mowing in mid-June and early July as part of AUM also poses a considerable risk. At the same time, it could be shown that the mowing mosaic has an important function in the habitat and that families, in the absence of areas with short vegetation, also move long distances to less well-managed areas or areas that are not protected from predators by electric fences. As the telemetry almost completely prevented losses due to mowing, the importance of predators became particularly clear. Despite intensive efforts, the majority of the chicks were predated and only a few fledged. In many cases, the evidence points to mammalian predators, but the stationary radio telemetry antennas were able to document losses during the day and some transmitters were located in nests of birds of prey. On site, the data is used to adjust mowing dates, optimize the design of electric fences, create targeted attraction areas (e.g. using water pumps or mowing mosaics) and remove structures that are used by predators or favor them.

Another positive effect of both projects is that, through these "close-up" data, a personal connection to the curlews can be established among the public and decision-makers.

Figure 63: Example of data generated by the stationary Telemetry-System in the project-area "Altmühltal". The points show the locations of the chicks, different colors represent different individuals. Map © Datenquellen: Bayerische Vermessungsverwaltung, Europäische Union, enthält Copernicus Sentinel-2 Daten 2018, verarbeitet durch das Bundesamt für Kartographie und Geodäsie (BKG).

Further Information

<https://www.lbv.de/naturschutz/arten-schuetzen/voegel/grosser-brachvogel/stationaere-telemetrie-technik-fuer-bedrohte-brachvoegel/>

Recommendations

- In addition to foraging and breeding areas, suitable nocturnal roost sites should also be included in the management of meadow bird habitats.
- To enable safe mowing in and around the breeding areas, the movement and behaviour of the families must be accurately determined. As the chicks grow older, they become more scattered across the area.
- Predation is the main cause of chick loss in Bavarian breeding grounds and plays a significant role in affecting the bird's life cycle.
- Telemetry data provides a unique insight into the "daily lives" of the birds, offering a strong emotional connection to the public and decision-makers.
- Successful implementation of telemetry projects requires a variety of stakeholders and effective area management.

12.9 Munich Airport: Flight Operations and Bird Protection

Abstract

The combination of a major airport and a European bird sanctuary (SPA) may appear contradictory. Nonetheless, this pairing has been working effectively at Munich Airport for several decades. The sparse meadows bordering two runways serve as vital core habitats for numerous meadow breeding bird species, and despite the continuous flight operations, they provide favorable conditions for successful breeding.

Introduction

The extensive area around the two runways of Munich Airport is considered an important breeding area for meadow birds in Bavaria (Figure 64). This was recently confirmed by the "7th State-wide Meadow Breeding Birds Mapping in Bavaria 2021" (LfU, 2023). The occurrence of breeding meadow birds in high density depends largely on the quality of the habitats, such as the predominant vegetation of the airport meadows. Special biotope management, known as long-grass management, makes it possible to reconcile what at first glance appear to be conflicting objectives - the prevention of bird strikes and the protection of meadow birds. Due to the extensive mowing regime and the avoidance of pesticides, high-quality meadows were established around the runways, providing optimal habitat for birds such as the Eurasian Curlew *Numenius arquata* where birds can reproduce and feed. The mowing regime in place is adapted to ground-nesting birds and is in two stages (except for safety zones, apron areas, and areas directly adjacent to taxiways and runways), namely a high cut from mid-July, after the meadow breeders have finished breeding, and a low cut in the fall.

On the airport meadows, breeding birds face different conditions compared to other areas: Meadow breeding birds are not disturbed by the active air traffic and even benefit from the prevailing site conditions of the airport premises. For instance, access to and movement on the runways adjacent to the airport meadows, is heavily regulated for reasons of aviation safety. Additionally, the airport premises are protected by a closed security fence, preventing any disturbance of the breeding birds by pedestrians and free-roaming dogs. Furthermore, active predator management is implemented on the airport meadows and in the surrounding area, which has a positive impact on the breeding success of the meadow breeders. For example, native predators such as foxes or mustelids are targeted with live traps on the airport meadows, and their population in the vicinity of the airport is deliberately kept low.

Figure 64: General map of Munich Airport showing the perimeter of the "Nördliches Erdinger Moos" bird sanctuary (light blue) and the airport meadows next to the runways (turquoise) ©Bayerische Vermessungsverwaltung, Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt

Method and Approach

In 2006, a survey of the breeding bird community, conducted in accordance with the methodological standards outlined by Südbeck et al. (2005), was carried out in the meadows surrounding the two existing runways at Munich Airport. The survey confirmed the presence of significant meadow bird species, including the highly endangered and strictly protected Eurasian Curlew *Numenius arquata*, Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus*, and Corn Bunting *Emberiza calandra*. Based on these results, the EU bird sanctuary "Nördliches Erdinger Moos" (NEM) was established in 2008 by law under order number 7637-471. Consequently, the 4,525 hectares at and around the airport became a significant element of the European Union's Natura 2000 network, attaining a high protection status as a Special Protection Area. A total of 40 conservation target species were identified within this area. The airport meadows, encompassing a total of 666 hectares, serve as the primary habitat for meadow breeding bird populations within the SPA.

Since 2006, annual surveys of the Munich airport meadows have been conducted, with a focus on recording the population size, habitat use, and breeding success of the Eurasian Curlew and Northern Lapwing. The annual mapping of the airport meadows is carried out on behalf of Munich Airport by Büro H2 - Ökologische Gutachten (Büro H2: Heckes et al. 2023). These surveys have been conducted for 18 consecutive years, resulting in a unique dataset. Additionally, annual population surveys are performed in parts of the NEM bird sanctuary to monitor bird population developments in the SPA area outside the airport perimeter. This extensive database enables precise statements about population developments and trends.

Results and Conclusion

The survey data from recent years confirm the high significance of the Munich airport meadows for a variety of meadow breeders and their protection. For instance, nearly 100 breeding pairs of the Eurasian Curlew (2006: 55 breeding pairs) can now be recorded annually on the meadows. This area hosts the largest population of Eurasian Curlew in Bavaria, ensuring a stable population (Figure 65). Corn Buntings and Skylarks *Alauda arvensis* also have stable populations in this SPA. In 2023, 99 Eurasian Curlew breeding pairs, 79 Northern Lapwing breeding territories, 226 Skylark breeding territories, 19 Corn Bunting breeding pairs, as well as 11 Common Quail *Coturnix coturnix* breeding pairs have been reported on the airport meadows (Heckes et al. 2023).

Figure 65: Population development of selected meadow breeders on the airport meadows since 2006 (Heckes et al. 2023) * Although fluctuations in the breeding population of avifauna occur regularly, these are largely unrelated to the airport and can be attributed to natural or other causes that may also affect other areas in Bavaria.

The airport meadows do not only represent valuable habitat for conservation target species of the NEM bird sanctuary. Other important meadow breeding birds also find suitable breeding and rearing habitats in the SPA. A pair of the endangered Black-tailed godwit *Limosa limosa* now regularly breeds on the airport meadows and young birds can be regularly recorded (Figure 66). The Grey Partridge *Perdix perdix* is another species that is also worth mentioning because, with 24 breeding pairs recorded in 2023, it is now one of the regular breeding bird species on the airport meadows (Heckes et al. 2023).

Outside the airport fence, the ecological compensation and replacement areas (A/E areas) at Munich Airport within the bird sanctuary represent a crucial habitat for meadow breeders in an often heavily utilized agricultural landscape. The decline in bird populations within this SPA mirrors the negative population trends observed across Germany. Nevertheless, breeding successes, such as those of the Northern Lapwing, continue to be recorded in the A/E areas (Heckes et al. 2023).

Figure 66: Photo of a Curlew at Munich Airport's airfield (left) and a fledgling Black-tailed Godwit from the study year 2023 (right) © Dirk Ullmann.

This case study illustrates how Munich Airport contributes to the preservation of meadow breeding birds in Bavaria, specifically within the SPA “Nördliches Erdinger Moos”. Importantly, it demonstrates that highly anthropogenic areas can still benefit bird conservation when managed appropriately. While the airport meadows cannot replace natural wet grasslands and meadows, they can still provide a significant contribution to the conservation of important bird species.

Further Information

<https://www.munich-airport.de/naturschutz-87317>

Heckes et al. (2023) Büro H2 Ökologische Gutachten Hess + Heckes GbR: Die Avifauna der Grünflächen im Bereich der Verkehrsflächen Flugbetrieb, Erhebungsphase 2023 (Im Auftrag der Flughafen München GmbH). München.

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Südbeck, P., H. Andretzke, S. Fischer, K. Gedeon, T. Schikore, K. Schröder & C. Sudfeldt (Hrsg.) (2005): Methodenstandards zur Erfassung der Brutvögel Deutschlands. Radolfzell (Im Auftrag der Länderarbeitsgemeinschaft der Vogelschutzwarten und des Dachverbandes Deutscher Avifaunisten). Radolfzell.

Recommendations

- Extensive mowing regime adapted to ground-breeding birds
- A closed security fence and a strict ban on entering the airport meadows (no disturbance from visitors and free-roaming dogs)
- Active predation management

12.10 Der Niedersächsische Weg, a Political Agreement to Advance Nature Conservation in Lower Saxony

Abstract

The Niedersächsische Weg is an ambitious meadow bird conservation program currently developed in Lower Saxony. The aim is to elaborate a state-wide conservation program for meadow bird conservation to tackle declining populations in a cooperative approach where nature conservationists, public authorities, and farmers work together. As of October 2023, the conservation program resulted in adjustments in the federal nature protection law and the provision of new funding opportunities. A road map for future meadow bird conservation with population goals of target species, key areas for implementation, as well as necessary measures with clear prioritization, is currently being formulated.

Introduction

As a reaction to a growing public awareness followed by the announcement of a public referendum to support efforts for nature conservation, a milestone agreement between the federal government of Lower Saxony (Federal State ministries), farmer's associations, and environmental NGOs was achieved in 2019. This agreement initiated the Niedersächsische Weg (NW, the Lower Saxony Path, Figure 67), a contract to enhance the conservation of nature, biodiversity, and waters. The initial aims of the NW were already integrated into the federal nature conservation law (NNatSchG). Among those, is the agreement to elaborate an ambitious meadow bird conservation program to improve the conservation status of wet-grassland breeding birds, and reverse the negative population trends. The State Agency for bird protection (NLWKN) was tasked to develop this ambitious concept in cooperation with all partners of the NW.

Figure 67: Contract partners of the Niedersächsische Weg: (from left to right: BUND, farmer 's association, federal agency for agriculture, Ministry for Agriculture, NABU and Ministry for the Environment. Source: „Der Niedersächsische Weg“ | Nds. Ministerium für Ernährung, Landwirtschaft und Verbraucherschutz (niedersachsen.de), Picture: ML/Timo Jaworr [25.08.2023]

Method and Approach

First, key areas for wet-grassland bird conservation in Lower Saxony were identified using the latest monitoring data for the target species like the Black-tailed Godwit (*Limosa limosa*),

Northern Lapwing (*Vanellus vanellus*), Common Snipe (*Gallinago gallinago*), Eurasian Curlew (*Numenius arquata*), Redshank (*Tringa totanus*), Whinchat (*Saxicola rubetra*) and Corncrake (*Crex crex*). All available data sources were compiled to identify core areas of these species (Figure 68). Those areas comprise mostly agricultural land (mainly grassland, but also arable land) and certain areas of (semi-) natural habitats, such as peatland or saltmarshes. These key areas were designated to act as priority areas for future implementation of wet-grassland bird conservation and are, therefore, directly linked to certain funding opportunities.

Figure 68: Key areas for meadow bird conservation in Lower Saxony (NLWKN, unpublished).

In order to formulate clear goals for this program, target values for population sizes of the species mentioned above were identified. On the scale of Lower Saxony species-specific minimum population targets already exist as part of the *Strategy for Species and Habitat Protection* of Lower Saxony (NLKWN, 2011). Based on those values, minimum population targets for single SPAs of the key areas were determined including species-specific information on local, historic, and recent distribution and population sizes.

An analysis of existing conservation efforts was carried out to examine the efficiency of the single instruments and measures that have been applied so far in Lower Saxony. For the instruments that were deemed unsuccessful, either because they were ineffective or because they were not applied only at a small scale, a revision and enhancement were proposed and partly already carried out. Further, a conceptual roadmap is currently being developed to provide a framework for how to best implement and combine existing and future instruments. This roadmap will clearly prioritize measures that have proven to be effective. An evaluation plan will ensure that the program and its implementation are critically reviewed and will provide the opportunity to readjust it.

Results and Conclusion

The program is still in development, therefore, few results can be described so far. The evaluation of existing conservation measures and instruments are summarized in Table 18.

Table 18: Analysis results for existing measures and instruments in meadow bird conservation in Lower Saxony. An Explanation for the assessment is given and the scale of implementation in the past is indicated (green: large scale; yellow: medium scale; red: small scale)

Instrument/ measure	Explanation	Scale of implementation in LS (as of July 2023)
<i>Measures with high effectiveness</i>		
Legal protection of SPAs	Key SPAs are legally protected to 95 %, but only on 24 % of the area regulations for meadowbird conservation are in place (only 2 % with strong regulations)	●
Purchase of land + lease contracts with regulations	Long-term effects – in many cases requirement for re-wetting and habitat management; 45 % of key SPAs is public land, but only on 30 % the lease contracts include regulations for meadowbird protection	●
Predation management	Extensive and effective predation management only in few areas	●
Large-scale water management	<i>In progress</i>	●
Local supervision of Protected areas	<i>In progress</i>	●
<i>Measures with low effectiveness</i>		

Instrument/ measure	Explanation	Scale of implementation in LS (as of July 2023)
AECMs (AUKM)	Implementation of potentially effective AECM (GI22 and partly NG4) only on a small scale; low level AECM (GL11 and GL21) on a larger scale, but not effective for meadow birds; for some AECM no sufficient data for evaluation were available; BS2 was potentially effective for whinchat on arable land, but not directed into the important areas	●
Clutch and chick protection	Protection of single clutches does not effectively improve breeding success; few local successes in areas with large scale implementation; farmer's willingness to cooperate was quite high due to low efforts	●

Some of the instruments that are less effective so far have already been revised and improved. The clutch and chick protection for example has undergone a thorough revision and realignment worked out by the cooperative working group resulting in a new concept. This concept replaces the small-scale protection of single clutches on a few square meters with more extensive measures, that should improve chick survival by providing an area for foraging. However, due to the cooperative approach a compromise was made allowing for exceptional maintenance of small-scale measures. Additionally, a new funding scheme was developed for financing the clutch and chick protection projects and compensating for farmer's income loss. A link to the comprehensive concept is given below. The implementation of the new concept will start in several areas in 2024.

Responding to some shortcomings in the past, the CAP funding instruments (GLÖZ, Eco-schemes and AUKM) were adjusted in Lower Saxony for the recent funding period (2023-2027) and opportunities for meadow bird conservation were slightly improved. The meadow bird conservation program integrates some measures (especially GLÖZ 8, Eco-schemes 1a and 1d, and the AUKM GL2, GL4, AN9, and NG GL) and links their implementation to the key areas of meadow bird conservation.

Our results show that the measures that are considered effective for long-term conservation were implemented only in a few areas to reverse the current negative population trends of bird populations. Voluntary and cooperative conservation measures on private land, such as clutch and chick protection or the AUKM, were not sufficiently effective, mainly because of sporadic implementation and results. Thus, our results underline the importance of using public land for meadow bird conservation where the implementation of major, long-term, and large-scale conservation measures is possible e.g., water level optimization, among others.

The future concept will prioritize such large-scale and long-term approaches and clearly formulate to what extent conservation measures have to be implemented in order to reach minimum population goals. Area requirements and the necessary funding budget will be estimated and the role and responsibility of responsible stakeholders, especially the Federal State of Lower Saxony, will be identified.

As part of the program’s conceptual outcome, several *meadow bird conservation module sheets* were produced acting as mosaic pieces of a technical manual that will include all necessary measures for successful meadow bird conservation (Figure 69).

Figure 69: Example for meadow bird conservation module sheet (NLKWN, unpublished).

Additionally, guidelines were provided to the nature conservation agencies (UNB) on how to better implement the available voluntary instruments for meadow bird conservation. The whole program is intended to be finished by the end of 2023.

Concrete outcomes of the NW and the meadow bird conservation program in terms of conservation results will be visible in a couple of years at the earliest. The outcomes so far are mainly the starting and intensification of communication and negotiations between different stakeholders, especially between nature conservation, politicians, and agriculture. For the realization of the NW the Federal State of Lower Saxony allocated a budget for creating several temporary jobs, 34 of which are at the federal agency for nature conservation (NLWKN). Two FTEs over three years (plus a one-year prolongation) were established for the development, implementation, and evaluation of the meadow bird conservation program.

Further Information

Official documents and information on the Niedersächsische Weg are published on the website of the Ministry for Environment, Energy and Climate Protection of Lower Saxony: www.umwelt.niedersachsen.de/niedersaechsischer-weg/mehr-natur-und-artenschutz-durch-den-niedersaechsischen-weg-193973.html

Recent information and conceptual content of the meadow bird conservation program can be found here: [Wiesenvogelschutz | Nds. Ministerium für Umwelt, Energie und Klimaschutz \(niedersachsen.de\)](https://www.wiesenvogelschutz.de/)

Recommendations

- Public engagement can significantly contribute to nature conservation by pressing for strong political commitment.
- Despite decades of conservation efforts and millions of euros spent for wet-grassland bird conservation in Lower Saxony, significant state-wide results have not been reached. Conservation efforts need to be upscaled.
- Voluntary conservation schemes on private land are often insufficient. Conservation measures on public land are, therefore, essential for effective state-wide wet-grassland bird conservation.
- Programs like the NW are starting points for progressing in conservation, but activities and strategies must be perpetuated and institutionalized in order to keep up the pace needed for reversing population trends.

12.11 Payment Model "Meadow Birds": Basic Principles of a Result-Based Payment-Model of Agricultural Services on Public Land

Abstract

In the Dümmer European bird sanctuary (SPA), comprehensive nature conservation measures have succeeded in halting the decline in meadow bird populations. The Dümmer is now one of the most important meadow bird sanctuaries in Europe. On 2,500 hectares of public wet-grassland managed by leaseholders, significant increases in the populations of many meadow bird species have been achieved. However, due to a lack of long-term economic viability, the maintenance of management, which is necessary to create favorable habitat conditions for meadow birds, is at risk. For this reason, a payment model consisting of three modules (maintenance premium, rush premium, meadow bird premium) was developed in cooperation with the farmers of the Dümmeriederung, the Landvölker, and the operating offices of the chambers of agriculture.

Introduction

Meadow birds are highly endangered throughout Europe and show unfavorable conservation levels nationwide due to habitat loss, inadequate habitat quality, and additionally exacerbated by high predation pressure. This has resulted in negative population trends for decades, leading to the local extinction of breeding populations and an increasing reduction in numbers. Nonetheless, Lower Saxony bears a special responsibility for the protection and conservation of wet-grassland and meadow birds being home to a high proportion of the populations of many of these bird species in Germany.

Optimum habitat quality in the wet-grassland bird SPAs is essential for an urgently needed reversal of the declining trends in bird populations. These success factors for wet-grassland bird conservation are already known (see, Südbeck & Krüger 2004; Belting 2021) and must be implemented holistically. The quality of the breeding/nesting habitat of wet-

grassland breeding birds is directly dependent on agricultural management and maintenance. However, grassland management is no longer cost-efficient and sustainable, partly due to changes in the current CAP (Common Agricultural Policy in the EU) period and low agricultural yields on areas optimized for meadow birds (i.e., rewetted areas). Neither hardship compensation (Erschwernisausgleich) nor agri-environmental and climate measures (AUKM) are granted on public land, so the loss in biomass productivity due to rewetting cannot be compensated for farmers/tenants. The tenants react by reducing their expenditure on grassland management, as a result of which the habitat quality for meadow birds deteriorates significantly and breeding sites are lost. In Lower Saxony, this affects more than 20,000 hectares of permanent grassland and 8,000 hectares of land within EU bird sanctuaries, with negative consequences for wet-grassland bird conservation.

The significant population increases required to achieve favorable conservation levels by 2050 as outlined by Lower Saxony (Figure 70) cannot be achieved under the current conditions. This is where the development of an economically viable payment model "meadow birds" comes into play on an area-specific basis, as a first step for the Dümmerniederung SPA.

Figure 70: Current population sizes of meadow birds in Lower Saxony (Krüger & Sandkühler 2022) and target values (year 2050) for favorable conservation status.

Method and Approach

The Dümmerniederung (EU-SPA) with 2,500 ha of wet-grassland in public ownership is the habitat for almost 1,500 breeding pairs of the highly endangered meadow birds Black-tailed Godwit, Lapwing, Curlew, Snipe, Redshank, and Ruff. The continuing positive population trends (Figure 71) run counter to the national trends. As part of LIFE projects (LIFE Vernässung der westlichen Dümmerniederung, LIFE Wiesenvögel, LIFE GrassBirdHabitats,

and LIFE GodwitFlyway), the area has been successfully developed as a source area for meadow birds and their protection.

The management (and maintenance) of wet-grassland areas suitable for wet-grassland breeding birds requires three main factors: 1) sufficient farming intensity for optimal vegetation structures, 2) low or intermediate trophic level of soil, 3) mowing and grazing compliant to nesting distribution. Conversely, this means that habitat quality is directly dependent on the agricultural management.

In February 2023, all farmers who are tenants of public grassland areas in the Dümmer SPA and representatives of the Landvolk and Chambers of Agriculture were invited to a meeting. The aim was to engage in an inclusive conversation with everyone and discuss the current and future management situation against the backdrop of wet-grassland bird conservation.

Figure 71: Population development of five meadow bird species (Black-tailed Godwit, Lapwing, Curlew, Redshank and Snipe) in the Dümmer SPA between 2000 and 2023 (Source: Datenbank Naturschutzstation Dümmer/NLWKN).

This resulted in three working groups: management, utilization, and funding. The working groups met monthly between March and September 2023. The management working group dealt in detail with the management of wet-grassland areas with the clear objective of creating annual breeding habitats for meadow birds. On the subject of management, the difficulties of land management due to waterlogging and the partial dominance of rushes were discussed. The utilization working group investigated and evaluated the wide range of utilization and recycling options for grassland growth. The funding working group developed and discussed the content and design of payment models that reward based on results (target of high meadow bird populations). The results of these working groups were incorporated in a comprehensive draft strategy articulated around a payment model.

The payment model "Meadow Birds", which is made up of three payment modules, is currently being calculated (as of April 2024, you can follow-up with the authors on the progress of the consultations). The draft of this meadow bird support model was presented to the Ministry of the Environment of Lower Saxony and subsequently to all tenants, the districts as the lower nature conservation authority, and the landowners.

Results and Conclusion

The development of the payment-model was based on the premise that it should be designed in such a way that the habitat conditions necessary for meadow birds are reliably created by farmers at the beginning of the breeding season (Figure 72) and at the same time the expenses incurred by farmers are compensated via the model.

The achievement of optimal vegetation structures and characteristics is achieved on the one hand via the Habitat maintenance-payment of expenses premium and on the other hand via the Rush payment (to control *Juncus effusus*; Soft rush or Flatter-Binse in German). If these two factors are implemented optimally, the landowners receive the Meadow bird premium (see below).

The payment model is made of three components:

1. **Habitat maintenance payment:** the maintenance service is determined in monetary terms; the services are only remunerated if the area is in very good or good maintenance condition on the reference date. Areas in unsatisfactory condition do not receive any payments.
2. **Rush payment:** Areas heavily overgrown with rushes (*Juncus effusus*) are unfavorable for bird colonization. For this reason, only areas with less than 1,000 rushes per hectare receive a premium. The farmer must therefore either reduce the rush densities beforehand or keep it permanently cut short.
3. **Meadow bird payment:** The more birds breed on the land, the more money the farmer receives for his leased land.

Figure 72: Optimization of habitat for meadow birds through appropriate management and maintenance of wet grasslands.

Outlook

This result-based payment model could be financed via a Natura 2000 premium; alternatively, nature conservation programs or species protection programs would also be conceivable. After a pilot phase and annual evaluation, this model should be transferred to other meadow bird areas in Lower Saxony.

Further Information

<http://www.grassbirdhabitats.eu>

Belting, H. (2021): Erfolgreicher Wiesenvogelschutz am Dümmer. In: Erfolgskontrollen im Naturschutz. Naturschutz und Biologische Vielfalt Heft 171: 377-392. Bundesamt für Naturschutz (Herausgeber)

Südbeck, P. & T. Krüger (2004): Erhaltungssituation und erforderliche Schutzmaßnahmen für Wiesenvögel in Niedersachsen - Bilanz und Ausblick. In: Krüger T. & P. Südbeck: Wiesenvogelschutz in Niedersachsen. Naturschutz und Landschaftspfl. Niedersachs. Heft 41: 106-123.

Recommendations

- The definition of success-based nature conservation benefits, is that meadow birds should be given a value that motivates farmers to align their business activities with the goal of meadow bird conservation (i.e., optimal habitat conditions = high number of breeding birds).
- When meadow bird conservation, nature conservation, and farmers have the same goal: The farmer becomes one of the main actors of bird conservation acting as a “bird farmer”.

13 A Roadmap for the Conservation of Wet-Grassland Breeding Birds in Germany

This roadmap aims to preserve the 11 bird species included in this multi-species Strategic Conservation Plan (SCP), restore their habitats, and overall revitalize biodiversity in wet-grasslands and meadows. It is the result of collaborative efforts from Germany's broader conservation community, including academics, practitioners, NGO members, statutory agencies, and public administration.

This roadmap provides strategic guidance for future conservation measures rather than prescribing specific interventions for individual Special Protection Areas (SPAs) or conservation sites. It identifies all relevant SPAs and conservation areas essential for wet-grassland bird conservation within Germany's Atlantic biogeographic region and Bavaria, while the designation and implementation of targeted actions remain the responsibility of the Federal States and local stakeholders, to be detailed in the management plans for each area.

This roadmap offers a comprehensive assessment of current conservation practices and instruments designed to tackle the challenges facing wet-grassland breeding bird conservation. Its purpose is to stimulate constructive dialogue and support the adaptation of these instruments, ultimately strengthening conservation efforts for wet-grassland birds. The assessment draws significantly from the Germany-wide Horizon-Scanning (HS) survey, which provided invaluable insights and perspectives from the broader conservation community. Furthermore, the roadmap is grounded in the expertise and lessons learned from 11 successful case studies featured in the SCP.

All recommendations reflect proven methods and approaches that have successfully recovered or maintained bird populations or mitigated habitat degradation.

13.1 Assessment of the Main Conservation Practices

This constructive assessment is conducted on the information presented for Lower Saxony and Bremen, Schleswig-Holstein and Hamburg, North Rhine-Westphalia, and Bavaria. It aims to highlight beneficial practices that have had or continue to have the potential to advance the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds, and underline weaknesses that need to be addressed. Details can be found in the Federal State-specific sections, with quantitative data when available.

This non-exhaustive assessment does not include all practices carried out across Germany. Other practices or approaches might be worth including in future assessments.

1. Natura 2000 sites, SPAs, and other Protected Areas

In Germany, nature conservation areas are designated into four main categories: nature protection areas, landscape protection areas, national parks, and biosphere reserves, which collectively cover about 36% of the country's surface area. However, only 64% of these areas have partial or full protection status with usage restrictions. Additionally, Private Protected Areas (PPAs) owned by various entities (e.g., foundations, nature conservation

associations, conservation-minded private landowners, and churches) complement these areas, although they face legal hurdles for official recognition.

Two key aspects are pivotal for the tangible contribution of SPAs and other conservation areas to bird conservation: the level and type of protection status, and the reinforcement of protection measures, particularly on privately owned land. The most important wet-grassland and meadow bird breeding areas in Germany have been designated as Special Protection Areas (SPAs), thereby receiving some level of conservation attention. However, optimal conservation efforts are still lacking in many SPAs. Often, only a selected few SPAs, where significant populations of flagship species remain, receive the bulk of conservation attention. While this seems an obvious way for the allocation of limited resources, it also can contribute to the loss of habitat connectivity. This loss of connectivity is crucial to consider, as it is often vital for sustaining robust metapopulations, which rely on the interconnectedness of habitats to support genetic diversity, facilitate movement, and ensure the long-term viability of species. Further, a comprehensive quantitative assessment of the specific management implemented in SPAs for wet-grassland bird conservation is often absent. This gap is primarily due to limited resources and the need for large-scale projects to finance such efforts and provide dedicated capacities to assess the implementation of management restrictions tailored for the protection of wet-grassland breeding birds.

2. Management Plans for Protected Areas

Management Plans (MPs) are essential instruments for grassland-breeding bird conservation and habitat improvement. Both Habitats (Council Directive 92/43/EEC) and Birds Directives (Directive 79/409/EEC) encourage Member States to set MPs for protected areas. In Germany, these tasks are delegated to the Federal States that have the responsibility to lead such efforts.

MPs for conservation areas in Germany show considerable heterogeneity in both development and implementation. Their ambition, quality, and effectiveness—especially for wet-grassland bird species—are strongly influenced by the availability of financial and human resources. While EU LIFE-funded projects (e.g., in Lower Saxony) can support the development of MPs, gaps in financial resources and political commitment often hinder their effective implementation. This is particularly evident in the enforcement of management restrictions on privately owned land within Special Protection Areas (SPAs).

3. The European Common Agricultural Policy

Conditionality replacing previous greening requirements is the key measure of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) for the period 2023-2027. Conditionality ensures that farmers receiving direct payments must comply with certain environmental and other requirements. This includes aspects of the former greening requirement, but also incorporates them into a broader system of conditionality.

The basic premium support from the CAP 2023-2027 is reduced when compared to the previous funding period, and eco-schemes are poised to play a crucial role. Similar to Agri-Environment-Climate Measures (AECMs), eco-schemes are voluntary for farmers. However, Member States now have significantly more flexibility in designing these schemes

to fit their specific needs and priorities. Germany has established seven voluntary nationwide eco-schemes. Nevertheless, these initiatives are expected to have only a marginal impact on the conservation of the 11 wet-grassland breeding bird species considered in the conservation plan. Based on their distribution and habitat preferences, only the Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* and the Curlew *Numenius arquata*, Whinchat *Saxicola rubetra* or Corncrake *Crex crex* might see marginal benefits from the implementation of eco-schemes. However, these potential benefits remain to be proven, underscoring the need for a comprehensive assessment of the impact of eco-schemes on bird conservation, and the establishment of more ambitious and targeted eco-schemes to effectively conserve wet-grassland breeding bird species.

Further, Germany needs to strengthen the financial compensation for bird-friendly management restrictions in Natura 2000 and protected areas. This implies increasing the share of the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD, Pillar 2 of the CAP) destined for the management of Natura 2000 and wet-grassland breeding bird SPAs. Payment models as compensations for farmers practicing bird-friendly management on both public and private land in Natura 2000 areas should be eligible to be financed through Natura 2000 payments.

4. Agri-Environment-Climate Measures

The management requirements of the Agri-Environment-Climate Measures (AECMs) serve several goals: climate protection and adaptation to climate change, protection or improvement of the environment and biodiversity, as well as the protection of natural resources, the water balance, and drinking water. Each Federal State has tailored its Agri-AECMs to local needs and priorities, with the goal (among others) of preserving and enhancing habitats for meadow and wet-grassland breeding birds. The measures vary in their specificities, management restrictions, and funding rates, reflecting unique challenges and opportunities in each Federal State. A one-to-one comparison is not helpful and often not feasible.

Some strong measures have been offered by each of the Federal States highlighting their commitment to the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds. The most important measures and their potential benefits to species found in agricultural land like the Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus*, the Whinchat *Saxicola rubetra*, and the Corncrake *Crex crex* have been included in the Federal States' respective chapters. However, their benefits still need to be proven and to date previous and recent AECMs did not contribute to halting the loss of any species. AECMs need to be adequately financed and tailored to increase benefits for wet-grassland breeding birds. For example, the protection of chicks and clutches (see below) in agricultural land needs to be compulsorily linked to the payments perceived by farmers under Pillar 1 of the CAP. This can automatically provide momentum for this measure and provide a much-needed push for the conservation of bird species breeding in agricultural land.

A thorough evaluation of the impact of AECMs on wet-grassland bird conservation is essential to inform future decisions and ensure adequate financial support for these voluntary initiatives (refer to the Horizon Scanning Survey results on voluntary measures for more context). While there are a few local case studies available, a comprehensive meta-analysis is still needed. This analysis should aim to quantify the benefits of AECMs on wet-grassland

bird conservation, providing a robust foundation for evidence-based policy and funding decisions.

5. Social and Political Initiatives

Social and political initiatives for the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds have demonstrated significant potential and have shown promising results in various contexts. These initiatives, as presented in Federal State specific sections and in the case studies, often involved collaborative efforts between government agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), farmers, and local communities, all working towards a common goal of preserving biodiversity and enhancing habitats.

Key factors that contributed to their success include:

- Collaborative approaches involving a wide range of stakeholders, including farmers, conservationists, and policymakers, ensure that initiatives are well-rounded and consider the needs and challenges of all parties involved.
- Legislative support where strong environmental policies and regulations provided the legal backbone for conservation efforts. For example, the EU's Habitats Directive and Natura 2000 network offer frameworks for protecting critical habitats.
- Education and awareness campaigns about the importance of biodiversity can garner public support and encourage participation in conservation efforts.
- Educational programs where training and education for farmers and landowners on best practices for habitat management can lead to more effective conservation outcomes.
- Community involvement as community-led projects often have a deeper understanding of local ecosystems and can tailor conservation efforts to specific needs.

While social and political initiatives have shown potential, they also face several challenges:

- Long-term commitment and sustained efforts to accomplish these initiatives.
- Funding constraints as adequate financial support is essential to develop these initiatives.
- Stakeholder conflicts as balancing the interests of different stakeholders, such as farmers and conservationists, can be complex. Establishing effective communication and conflict resolution mechanisms is crucial.

6. LIFE-funded Projects: Development and Implementation

The EU-LIFE instrument is the backbone of wet-grassland breeding bird conservation in many Federal States in Germany. Project-related LIFE funding allowed the maintenance and management of habitats in many SPAs, funded the development of MPs, funded the implementation of predation management programs, and in some cases provided the necessary resources to acquire land into public ownership to allow the implementation of major rewetting measures. This funding benefited the conservation of umbrella species like

the Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa limosa*, the Curlew *Numenius arquata* or the Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus*. This is shown in the case studies and across the Federal State's specific chapters.

Over the past 25 years, approximately 150 million Euro have been invested in LIFE projects focused on conserving the populations of wet-grassland breeding birds, as outlined in this conservation plan. This substantial investment encompasses various levels of Federal State co-funding and is derived from the data included in this SCP. Most of the projects were specific to individual Federal States, with only a few initiatives involving multiple Federal States or other European Member States. Given the migratory nature of these birds and the necessity for more comprehensive and holistic conservation efforts, there is a pressing need for large-scale cooperative projects, as seen in the two LIFE projects led by Lower Saxony (LIFE IP GrassBirdHabitats, and LIFE GodwitFlyway). Such collaborative projects are essential to effectively address the increasingly complex global and regional conservation challenges.

7. Clutch-and-Chick Protection

This practice is among the most widespread across Germany and is primarily used for species with a wide distribution across large agricultural areas where instruments like fencing are costly or not applicable. The practice is usually supported by Biological/Ecological Stations, local conservation offices, and NGOs. It is seen as complementary rather than a primary tool for breeding bird conservation, requiring more holistic efforts for long-term success.

Recent evaluations in Lower Saxony and other Federal States showed limited success of this practice due to small protection areas around nests, which only safeguard nests from immediate physical destruction but does not provide sufficient habitat in good quality to secure long-term chick survival. New concepts are being developed and tested to replace small-scale clutch-and-chick protection with larger measures to improve chick survival by providing additional foraging areas.

To maximize the effectiveness of this practice, greater coordination and standardization of best practices among Federal States are essential, ensuring consistency and enabling more efficient implementation across diverse regions. Ongoing evaluation of these practices—tailored to different landscapes and species—will also be critical, requiring robust data collection and long-term tracking of key indicators such as chick survival rates, in addition to hatching rates. To support these efforts, dedicated federal funding instruments for coordinated monitoring should be established, fostering a more adaptive and evidence-based approach to conservation.

The success of this practice heavily depends on the active cooperation of farmers, as their involvement is central to its implementation. To foster broader participation, it is crucial to simplify the process of engagement—reducing administrative burdens—and to provide adequate compensation that reflects the value of their contributions. By addressing these key factors, we can encourage more farmers to adopt and sustain these practices, ultimately enhancing their overall effectiveness.

8. Predation Management

Across Germany, there is a notable absence of an overview of effective strategies for predation management in wet-grassland breeding bird sanctuaries, Special Protection Areas (SPAs), and other conservation zones. Large-scale, coordinated approaches are limited to a few key areas, such as the SPAs Dümmer and Untere lbe in Lower Saxony, the Beltringharder Koog in Schleswig-Holstein and the historically mammalian-predator-free islands that are part of the Wadden Sea National Park. In most conservation areas, predation management is implemented to varying degrees and through diverse methods that involve a combination of habitat management measures, strategies to exclude predators from breeding areas, and initiatives to reduce mammalian or avian predator populations through both lethal and non-lethal means.

Predation management is an intricate and multifaceted aspect of wet-grassland bird conservation, encompassing several critical dimensions. Effective predation management, therefore, demands a holistic approach that integrates societal, financial, and ecological considerations, along with a deep understanding of legal frameworks and public sentiment.

The **societal dimension** presents significant challenges, as many stakeholders, including conservationists and the general public, are often opposed to the culling or hunting of predators, especially charismatic species like foxes. Public perception and ethical considerations play a crucial role in shaping these attitudes, making it essential to engage in open dialogue and education to build consensus.

The **financial dimension** is equally challenging. Predation control and management are typically expensive activities, and funding is often secured through short-term, project-based grants. This lack of long-term financial stability can hinder the sustainability and effectiveness of predation management efforts, necessitating more reliable funding mechanisms.

The **ecological dimension** adds another layer of complexity. Predation pressures can shift dynamically among different predator species and types following the removal or alteration of resources within the food chain. For instance, reducing the population of one predator species can inadvertently facilitate the proliferation of other predators, leading to unintended consequences. This requires a nuanced understanding of ecosystem dynamics and careful planning.

Furthermore, some predator species responsible for significant losses of bird chicks are themselves protected by law, such as raptors like the Marsh Harrier *Circus aeruginosus*, Red Kite *Milvus milvus*, Black kite *Milvus migrans*, and the Common Buzzard *Buteo buteo*. This legal protection adds an additional layer of complexity, as conservation efforts must navigate regulatory constraints while addressing the predation issue.

There is significant potential for enhancing the implementation of comprehensive predation management programs in key conservation areas. Increased exchange of expertise (see section below, Moving Forward), such as through the establishment of professional hunter networks, and the allocation of dedicated budgets to address predation are crucial. In the vast majority of SPAs, the conservation of wet-grassland breeding bird species cannot be effectively achieved without integrating robust and lasting predation management strategies.

9. Monitoring

Wet-grassland breeding bird populations are monitored across Germany both within Special Protection Areas (SPAs) and outside of them. However, this monitoring is carried out by the individual Federal States with disparities in financial, institutional, and human capacities. Monitoring bird populations in SPAs across Germany is mandated to be conducted every six years, focusing primarily on "trigger species"—those listed in Annex I of the EU Birds Directive and regularly occurring migratory species that require special conservation measures. Federal State authorities bear the responsibility to ensure that sufficient financial resources are allocated to effectively monitor both the inventory and trends of bird populations within SPAs. Targeted monitoring of wet-grassland breeding bird populations outside of SPAs is conducted sporadically across Germany. When implemented, it heavily relies on datasets and projects conducted by consultancy agencies, academic institutions, NGOs, or, to a lesser extent, state-funded programs for rural development.

Overall, for the 11 species included in this conservation plan, good monitoring data is generally available across Germany. This data is often supplemented by project-related telemetry studies, such as GPS tracking, which provide detailed insights into the movements and behaviors of specific species. Additionally, associated breeding success data is available for a few local populations of flagship species, such as the Black-tailed Godwit and Curlew. These comprehensive monitoring efforts ensure a robust understanding of the conservation status and needs of these important wet-grassland breeding birds.

10. Public Land Management via Contracts

The management of publicly owned land in grassland Special Protection Areas (SPAs) can serve as a model for sustainable nature conservation, particularly for the protection of wet-grassland breeding birds. The conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds often requires substantial measures (e.g., extensive rewetting measures) that cannot be carried out on privately owned land.

In Lower Saxony, our analysis found that up to two-thirds of publicly owned grasslands are subject to bird-friendly management obligations (see Section on Lower Saxony and Bremen). Of these, 49% are leased under usage restrictions explicitly designed to support nature conservation, particularly for wet-grassland breeding birds. However, such detailed quantitative data is lacking for other Federal States. We know that similar practices exist elsewhere: in North Rhine-Westphalia, publicly owned land in protected areas is leased under nature conservation regulations, while in Schleswig-Holstein, land within the "Wiesenvogelkulisse" is managed with a focus on breeding birds, often including bird-friendly lease obligations. Yet, comprehensive data on the extent of publicly leased land supporting bird and nature conservation remains unavailable. To address this gap, a critical first step would be to secure funding for a nationwide assessment quantifying how publicly owned land across Germany is managed for wet-grassland breeding bird conservation. This would not only clarify current practices but also help identify opportunities to scale up successful strategies and improve conservation outcomes.

The acquisition of land into public ownership in core areas for wet-grassland breeding birds should be strongly encouraged when possible, while it alone cannot be considered the solution to preserving bird biodiversity. Land in public ownership has proven to be a crucial

step in implementing profound, long-term habitat optimization measures necessary to safeguard core areas where populations of wet-grassland breeding birds still thrive. By securing these lands, conservation efforts can ensure that essential habitats are protected and managed effectively, ultimately benefiting the entire biodiversity of wetland and wet-grassland ecosystems.

It is important to highlight that adequate financing mechanisms must also be accessible to effectively manage publicly owned land. In certain Federal States, there is an increasing challenge in finding and retaining farmers who are willing to exploit public wet-grasslands. This issue arises primarily because farming these areas is often not profitable for farmers, rendering the current business model unsustainable.

11. Species-specific action plans

Species-specific action plans are detailed strategies designed to address the conservation needs of particular species that are threatened or endangered. These plans typically include a comprehensive set of measures aimed at protecting and recovering target species. Key components include population monitoring, the assessment of threats, habitat conservation and restoration recommendations, establishing research and data collection strategies, and establishing funding and resource allocation priorities.

Germany currently lacks comprehensive, species-specific action plans at the national level for all of the 11 species. This gap hinders the development of a cohesive, Germany-wide strategy for protecting populations of many flagship species, which are often in critical conditions.

Key issues stemming from this absence include:

Lack of National Targets: Without overarching action plans, it is challenging to establish clear, measurable targets for species protection and recovery across the country.

Limited Coordination: Effective conservation often requires coordinated action among the Federal States. However, the absence of a national framework can lead to fragmented efforts, reducing the overall impact of conservation initiatives.

Varying Priorities: Each Federal State may have its own priorities and approaches to conservation, leading to discrepancies in how measures are implemented across different regions.

Addressing these issues through the development of national species-specific action plans could enhance the effectiveness of species protection efforts, ensure more synergies across Federal States, and facilitate better leverage of financial resources for conservation.

13.2 Valuable Insights and Future Outlook: A Comprehensive Horizon Scanning Survey

The **Horizon Scanning** (HS) survey provided valuable insights on the current status and future outlook for wet-grassland breeding bird conservation in Germany by providing a platform for a direct input from the wider conservation community.

The HS was conducted end of 2022 for each of the Federal States in the Atlantic biogeographic region and for the Continental biogeographic region of Germany, separately. With the participation of 76 professional conservation practitioners, the survey received great attention and summarized the opinion of the wider conservation community constituted by ornithologists, ecologists, and farmers who are actively collaborating with nature conservation projects (Maasri et al. 2023).

Overall, wet-grassland breeding bird conservation in Germany benefits from significant assets. There are **extensive competent human resources**, including volunteers, across the entire territory with an active network of nature conservation, biological, and ecological stations. Usually, these stations have clear mandates for bird population monitoring, coordinating the management of conservation areas with farmers and local authorities, communicating and engaging with the local communities, and planning and implementing maintenance and conservation measures. This territorial implementation resulted in a good knowledge of species occurrences and population status in most of the important Special Protection Areas (SPAs). Further, wet-grassland bird conservation benefits from a multitude of tools adapted to private and publicly owned land, among those, agri-environmental-climate measures (AECMs) providing financial support to farmers to contribute to the protection or enhancement of biodiversity. However, the efficacy of measures implemented on private agricultural land (e.g., arable land and pasture grassland) is debatable and widely criticized among the conservation community. Often, case studies differ greatly and there is a wide consensus that AECMs need to be revised and better adapted to the protection of wet-grassland breeding birds.

The role of **public versus private land ownership** in the conservation of wet-grassland birds is a topic of extensive debate among practitioners. It is evident that the most effective and sustainable conservation measures are typically implemented on publicly owned lands. These areas are often managed, with few exceptions, to optimize water-table levels, which are crucial for the conservation of wader species. However, this approach faces significant challenges, primarily related to financing and the availability of land for acquisition.

Notable successes have been achieved in regions such as Lower Saxony and Bremen, and North Rhine-Westphalia, where this strategy has been in place for several years. Nevertheless, this solution alone is insufficient to halt the decline of bird populations across Germany.

Intensive agriculture leading to homogeneous grasslands, extensive use of fertilizers and pesticides, and frequent and heavily mechanized mowing are the direct cause of the decline of wet-grassland breeding bird populations across Germany. This is sustained by 1) a lack of willingness of the broader agricultural sector to engage in more sustainable use of wet grasslands and 2) European subsidies awarding primarily high productivity at the expense of biodiversity and the sustainable use of natural resources.

The **current agricultural practices** constitute the major obstacle to bird conservation in Germany. The principle of voluntariness for farmers to engage in bird-friendly farming practices does not provide sufficient incentive to shift toward more sustainable and bird-friendly agriculture. Further, authorities do not impose sufficient restrictions to support bird conservation and the few conservation areas where bird populations are stable are often small and deprived of buffer zones separating them from intensive agriculture. Habitat fragmentation and conservation activities that are limited to a few core areas hinder the conservation of widespread species like the Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* and expose the few remaining source populations to high risks of extinction.

Conservation efforts are increasingly facing growing populations of **mammalian and avian predators**. Indeed, the breeding successes of many wet-grassland breeding birds are currently hindered by high predation rates. Mammalian predator populations, including introduced (and often invasive) species, are excessively high across all agricultural land. Some predator control measures, like hunting, are often controversial. Passive predator control measures (including fencing and enclosures), are widespread but costly and difficult to apply to large areas.

Conservation practitioners in Lower Saxony and Bremen advocate for more active predation management, including the involvement of professional hunters. Other regions recognize the challenges of predation but do not emphasize active management as strongly, and in some cases, note the difficulties in implementing effective predator control. However, recent projects in North Rhine-Westphalia and Schleswig-Holstein started experimenting with the implementation of programs involving active predation management and the implication of professional hunters.

Overall, wet-grassland bird conservation suffers from a **lack of a nationwide strategy**. Many individual projects are being implemented across the country; however, there is no overarching framework for wet-grassland breeding bird conservation. In a few cases where conservation efforts have been successful, funding for the implementation of conservation measures is often project-dependent. This **unreliability of funding** needed for conservation is an additional challenge for long-term strategies where funding gaps for the implementation of measures must be avoided. Often, conservation measures consist of immediate short-term actions (e.g., nest protection) instead of long-term solutions like the development of more holistic sustainable practices to recover wet-grassland habitats. The low awareness of the urgency of wet-grassland breeding bird conservation among stakeholders and decision-makers is alarming.

Other hurdles for conservation have been identified, including:

- 1) High local and regional recreational pressures (e.g., along the Rhine River floodplain).
- 2) Decreasing interest of farmers to practice low-intensity and bird-friendly grassland management in nature conservation areas because of little financial compensation and support.
- 3) Bureaucratic obstacles in accessing European, National, and Federal State funding.

4) Regulatory obstacles where conflicting regulations between water rights and land consolidation laws hinder the implementation of conservation measures.

Acknowledging the current problems hindering the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds is fundamental, however, **identifying future threats and opportunities is indispensable** to tackling upcoming climatic, social-economical, and societal challenges. We attempt here to present the future threats and opportunities for wet-grassland breeding bird conservation as perceived by the community of conservation practitioners.

Climate change is undoubtedly a major threat to wet-grassland breeding bird conservation. Fewer, delayed, and more heavy precipitations and extended drought periods are already being observed across Germany. Competition for water allocation between nature, agriculture, and society is expected to increase in the near future. The combination of these factors creates major challenges to maintaining suitable breeding habitats for many wet-grassland breeding bird species. The unabated lowering of water tables will lead to an even more generalized water crisis in wetlands and wet-grasslands as groundwater levels are excessively kept low and are not recovering. Water is critically lacking in many wetlands of the Atlantic biogeographic region of Germany, while more water should be kept in the landscape for longer periods, e.g., in backwater habitats and overflow structures. Further, a major threat for the future is that water shortages might be again addressed primarily with technical solutions for agriculture and society and not with sustainable nature-based water management approaches.

The **energy transition** is increasing the demand for large photovoltaic and wind power plants, as well as associated power lines and infrastructure. The development of renewable energy is a challenge for wet-grassland breeding bird conservation as competition for land is expected to increase, and permanent grasslands often end up being selected to construct such power plants. Connectivity between the remaining protected areas is increasingly threatened creating additional hurdles for maintaining viable breeding populations. The current political guidelines often prioritize the expansion of renewable energies over bird protection and sensitive bird habitat conservation.

Intensive agriculture, identified previously as the main factor behind the current decline of wet-grassland breeding bird populations, is still considered a major future threat to conservation. The **intensification of agricultural practices** continues unabated. The acceleration of structural changes in the German farming industry where smaller farms are being consolidated and replaced by larger ones will have major consequences on the intensification of productivity and therefore on the ability to implement bird conservation measures. Additionally, due to climate change the mowing season often starts earlier, the period between the cuts is shorter and the frequency thus higher, often with now more than five cuts per year even in northern Germany. Further, many farming activities are now being assigned to contractors who are less considerate of bird conservation. This agricultural intensification, producing degraded landscapes, is fueling the expansion of predators.

Additionally, other future threats to the conservation of wet-grassland breeding bird conservation have been identified including:

- The **deprioritizing of conservation measures against new challenges** that can utterly jeopardize conservation efforts. For example, in the context of the ongoing war on Ukraine, global food supplies have been challenged and a general movement to maintain, and even increase, agricultural productivity has been engaged. This

contradicts advocacy for low-intensity agricultural production and highlights the threats of deprioritizing conservation efforts.

- The increasing loss of attractive flagship species, like the Eurasian Curlew *Numenius arquata*, jeopardizes the conservation of wet grassland breeding birds in general. Flagship species are important for communicating conservation concerns to the public.

The **ongoing debate on climate change**, its implications for both agriculture and nature conservation, and the associated measures that need to be deployed to mitigate its effects on our ecosystems and societies are seen across Germany as **an opportunity to rethink policies, agricultural practices, and nature conservation**. This was clearly a common topic across all Federal States in the Continental and Atlantic biogeographic regions of Germany. Increasing drought periods brought back the subjects of peatland restoration, rewetting of fen soils, waterlogging, impoundments, and water retention to the front row. This is an opportunity that has the potential to significantly benefit the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds if addressed correctly, and **synergies between climate change mitigation measures and bird conservation** should be developed. It is well known that major funding from the European Commission and the German Federal Government is, and will continue to be, mobilized to halt the effects of climate change and to transition towards a decarbonized society. The nature conservation community sees this as an opportunity to join efforts and deploy measures that benefit both nature conservation and climate change mitigation. Wet-grassland breeding birds should be direct beneficiaries of the restoration of wetlands and wet grasslands when restoration measures are implemented adequately to restore and recover biodiversity.

Further, the increased water scarcity for agriculture creates an additional incentive to rethink agriculture and water management practices in wet grasslands. Public opinions have also shifted. The increased recognition by the public of the need to restore wet grasslands to mitigate the effects of climate change combined with the **desire for ecological agriculture** are opportunities to transform current agricultural practices. Undoubtedly, consumers are more critical of the environmental footprint of agricultural products.

Change is also being noticed through **stronger political commitments towards nature conservation** and more specifically towards wet-grassland breeding bird conservation. This was the case in all major Federal States of the Atlantic biogeographic region of Germany where, recently, noticeable changes occurred and constitute an encouragement to advance bird conservation and wet-grassland habitat recovery.

Other opportunities to advance wet-grassland breeding bird conservation include:

- 1) The ongoing cooperation among neighboring Federal States that still need to be strengthened.
- 2) The intensification of **efforts to restructure the Common Agricultural Policy (EU-CAP)** to promote and support low-intensity agriculture and increase funding instruments for nature conservation.
- 3) The continuous pressures from the European Commission and the Federal Government of Germany to implement more concrete conservation measures with clear quantitative targets.

In conclusion, and without any surprises, the **HS results** confirm the predominant detrimental impact of agricultural intensification on wet-grassland breeding bird populations (Figure 73). Participants from across the Continental and Atlantic biogeographic regions in Germany identify intensive agricultural practices and predation to be major drivers of the decline of bird populations and consider intensive agriculture to be the main threat to the future of bird conservation. This is accompanied by major concerns about the consequences of climate change on wet-grassland and wetland availability, and upcoming conflicts over water allocation that will arise between nature conservation, agriculture, and society. Without addressing these major challenges and reforming the subsidies provided to the agricultural sector to encourage more sustainable and bird-friendly practices, the future of wet-grassland bird conservation in Germany is very gloomy.

Figure 73: Diagram illustrating the main Strengths, Weaknesses, Threats, and Opportunities for wet-grassland breeding bird conservation in Germany.

Overall, the expressed opinions were relatively homogeneous across Federal States in the Atlantic and Continental biogeographic regions. It is however noticeable that participants for Schleswig-Holstein, Lower Saxony, and North Rhine-Westphalia designate the ongoing strong political support to wet-grassland bird conservation as an opportunity for a brighter future. However, this is highly dependent on European and national political decision making and may change with electoral periods. The energy transition toward a more decarbonized society, while urgent and necessary, is considered across Germany as a challenge that might have negative repercussions on wet-grassland bird conservation. Competition for space to build wind and solar power plants, and related infrastructure, will increase. This is an honest plea to decision-makers to consider nature conservation requirements when developing new strategies for this energy transition.

Emerging opportunities and a positive outcome can still be achieved as Germany benefits from a substantial widespread and dynamic network of conservationists and institutional implementation across its territory. These valuable capacities will further empower the German conservation community to reverse the decline of wet-grassland bird species. High hopes have been communicated regarding the opportunities to develop synergies between climate change mitigation measures (e.g. restoration and rewetting of bogs, fens, and other wetland ecosystems) and bird conservation. This opportunity should not be missed as it provides both scale and funding to make a significant and durable change for wet-grassland bird conservation. Further, wet-grassland breeding bird conservation in Germany will benefit most from a nationwide strategy. Such a strategy will provide a framework to guide and align objectives, mutualize efforts, and facilitate the development of project consortia. These are all encouraging opportunities to move bird conservation forward and recover wet-grassland biodiversity.

13.3 Moving Forward

In this section we discuss the main aspects that can help move forward the conservation of wet-grassland and meadow breeding birds in Germany. We underscore six priorities (Figure 74) and provide elements to act. This is a non-exhaustive selection of priorities that should be revised at 5-year increments to be able to adjust to new developments and challenges.

Figure 74: Six priorities to move forward the conservation of wet-grassland and meadow breeding bird conservation in Germany.

1. **Holistic Approach to Conservation.** The effectiveness of any individual conservation measure is significantly constrained when isolated from a comprehensive holistic approach to conservation. A flyway approach is essential when addressing the conservation of migratory species, exposed to dangers along their entire lifecycle. However, in breeding areas, habitat optimization should serve as the cornerstone of any conservation effort. Through expert analysis across this SCP and proven experience in one of the largest conservation areas for wet-grassland breeding birds in Germany, ten key conservation measures (Figure 75) have been identified. To ensure a successful and

optimal holistic approach to conservation, these measures need to be implemented concurrently.

Figure 75: Through expert analysis, ten conservation measures have been identified that must be implemented concurrently to ensure a successful conservation approach for wet-grassland breeding birds.

- 2. Establish Bold Objectives.** While the recommendation to establish bold objectives might seem purely semantic, it is crucial to acknowledge that wet-grassland bird conservation in Germany currently lacks ambitious, overarching goals. Significant projects have been developed in the Atlantic biogeographical region of Germany, where most of these species breed, however, few initiatives associated more than two Federal States, have national scopes, or integrated flyway-scale components. This limitation is particularly challenging for the conservation of migratory bird species that rely on a network of interconnected habitats across Europe and the East Atlantic Flyway.

Moreover, no projects are currently scaled to the national level or even to the Atlantic biogeographic region, despite the similarity of challenges and the need for shared solutions (further discussed in point 6 on cooperation). Establishing bold objectives through large-scale national projects will 1) enable the mobilization of substantial resources, 2) increase the exchange of experiences and know-how, 3) facilitate the development of innovative environmental schemes, and 4) leverage new financing models, just to name a few. A clearer understanding of achievable nationwide conservation goals in Germany is essential, as the continuation of current practices has failed to reverse the population decline of these 11 species and is unlikely to do so in the near future.

- 3. Climatic Challenges.** Climate change is reshaping the conservation of wet-grassland birds in Germany. The main challenges have been highlighted in the Horizon Scanning survey and are of ecological, societal, and economical nature. However, climate mitigation and adaptation measures present significant opportunities to implement large-scale initiatives that simultaneously benefit wet-grassland biodiversity and climate goals. These measures are expected to attract substantial financial investment and political support.

Climate mitigation projects, including the rewetting of raised bogs and fens, are expected to have an overall positive effect on wet-grassland breeding bird populations. Therefore, developing synergies between climate mitigation measures and bird conservation offers a strategic opportunity to significantly increase funding for nature conservation.

Climate mitigation projects should not be approached solely from a carbon calculation perspective. Instead, they should integrate carbon sequestration with a holistic approach aimed at enhancing biodiversity and the overall ecosystem services provided by wet grasslands.

This is the next major challenge that the conservation community needs to successfully tackle by developing new initiatives and cross sectorial projects to provide the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds with new opportunities to advance conservation priorities.

- 4. Financing Conservation.** The availability and stability of financial resources are critical for the success of conservation efforts. Throughout this SCP, financial limitations have consistently been highlighted as the primary obstacle to implementing numerous conservation measures, including predation management programs, fencing and exclosures, and even consistent monitoring activities.

Many conservation initiatives are project-dependent, meaning their long-term sustainability is often threatened by the fluctuating availability of resources. This financial instability can lead to interruptions in conservation activities, which can have detrimental effects on the success of conservation efforts.

To address these challenges:

- 1) Increase cooperation among the Federal States in Germany to enable organizations and stakeholders with limited human resources to access large-scale European funding (e.g., EU LIFE, Interreg or Biodiversa+).
 - 2) Explore funding opportunities related to climate mitigation, such as rewetting and moorland restoration initiatives, and carbon crediting on wetlands. These programs not only support conservation but also contribute to broader climate goals, making them attractive to a wider range of funders.
 - 3) Consider other innovative financing mechanisms, including green bonds, conservation trust funds, and payment for ecosystem services (PES). These models can provide a steady and reliable stream of funding for long-term conservation projects.
 - 4) Develop business models that integrate birds as a valuable component of sustainable farming practices. This approach can create economic incentives for farmers to adopt conservation-friendly methods, such as maintaining habitats that support bird populations.
5. **Research and Innovation.** To enhance the conservation of wet-grassland breeding birds, it is essential to prioritize research that addresses the knowledge gaps regarding their niche requirements, not only in breeding areas but also in staging and non-breeding areas. Germany, with its significant potential for research and funding, can play a pivotal role in mobilizing scientists and resources to conduct extensive studies on telemetry, habitat requirements, and feeding requirements. These three themes are crucial for improving the breeding success of these birds. Also, the evaluation and implementation of practices like headstarting, as short-term solution, can further benefit some of the 11 species included in the SCP, ensuring a comprehensive and effective strategy for their protection. Finally, removing hurdles between academic research and applied conservation will facilitate better data usage and the integration of innovative approaches, including Artificial Intelligence (AI) for advancing conservation and monitoring purposes.
6. **Better Cooperation and Collaboration.** The shared challenges and solutions across Germany, coupled with the uniform institutional organization among German Federal States, underscore the need for a more unified approach to wet-grassland bird conservation. Although cooperation and knowledge exchange are already in place, strengthening this collaboration can significantly enhance conservation efforts for these birds.

Key benefits include:

- **Setting and Achieving National Goals:** Establish clear, nationwide objectives and work collectively to meet them.

- **Facilitating Knowledge Exchange:** Foster the sharing of expertise and best practices among all stakeholders involved in conservation.
- **Synchronizing Conservation Efforts:** Coordinate initiatives and pool resources to maximize impact and efficiency.
- **Supporting Small-Scale Organizations:** Assist smaller organizations in accessing large-scale national and European funding opportunities.
- **Advocating for Policy Changes:** Promote stronger advocacy to modify eco-schemes and Agri-Environmental Climate Measures (AECMs) that directly benefit the 11 bird species covered by this Species Conservation Plan (SCP).

To structurally enhance cooperation and collaboration, consider the following approaches:

- **Establish Species-Specific Task Forces:** Create dedicated teams that meet regularly to address the unique needs of each species.
- **Establish Thematic Task Forces** where experts of different disciplines (Conservationists, Farmers, Scientists, Climate change experts, Policy Makers) meet regularly to exchange and develop sustainable solutions for an overarching concept of water management, climate change effects, biodiversity loss, only to name a few.
- **Formalize an Exchange Platform:** Develop an umbrella platform to facilitate communication, coordination, and the advancement of conservation strategies for wet-grassland breeding birds across Germany.

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The project focuses on the protection of grassland birds such as Black-tailed Godwit, Lapwing and Curlew, and their habitats. The aim is to create and connect optimal breeding and non-breeding areas along the East Atlantic Flyway.

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